

A SEMIOTIC STUDY OF
DURO LADIPO'S
MYTHICO-HISTORICAL PLAYS

BY

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ABSTRACT

The work is presented in two parts. The first part which contains the first two chapters is a background study.

The semiotic background of the work is the burden of Chapter One. Here the general theoretical and methodological concepts applied in the second part are examined. Chapter Two presents an informational survey of the dramatic network within which Duro Ladipo operates. A biographical sketch as well as a brief discussion of his repertory is included to place the discussion in the chapter as a whole in proper perspective.

The analysis of Duro Ladipo's plays is done in Part Two of the thesis. Chapter Three, which is the first in this Part, focuses on the musico-poetic code. The structuralization of festival songs, children's songs, war songs and chants is discussed under traditional musico-poetic structures while the opening and closing glees, and dialogised and non-dialogised songs are discussed under neo-traditional musico-poetic structures. Apart from adding colour to the performance

as a whole, it is discovered that the musico-poetic structures (including dancing and instrumentation) facilitate a cognitive understanding of the events and characters.

In Chapter Four, the lineal structure of setting is treated as a sub-code while the main code resides in the lineal structure of the events. The general patterns in the movement of events from the exordium through the climax to the dénouement are considered in the examination of the sequential and consequential structures of intrigues and conflicts. It is shown that there are gappings and overlappings in the general plotal progression of the plays. Though we agree with Seagre (1981: 94) that such a plotal structure is a distinctive feature of drama in general, we submit, however, that the improvisational approach of the theatre is also partially responsible for it.

In Chapter Five, the characterizational features, such as names and physical appearance, behavioural features and overall plotal functions (actantial roles), are first examined before their structuralization in the iconization of eight characters are considered. It is

discovered that a balanced portraiture is painted of the protagonists and antagonists. This, it is noted, is made possible by the entrenchment of the notion of binary opposition as a philosophy among the Yorùbá.

In the conclusion the archetypal essence is identified as the central significating idea in the plays. The concept of archetypal essence is said to encapsulate such concepts as heroism, tragedy, transmogrification/suicide "death" and "non-death" and apotheosization. The relevance of this to the contemporary situation is highlighted and the predicament of our present society is said to be traceable to the lack of archetypal values in our leaders. We also try to show the significance of Duro Ladipo by highlighting his achievements on the entertainment and aesthetic levels and we finally submit that Duro Ladipo is a highly competent dramatist. The advantages of the semiotic approach for the study are emphasized and directions are given for further studies of the plays in the tradition.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this my first major work to
Unity and Love
among the cream of the Ogundeji Family.

Oh

The pristine head of
David, Adeniji and our mothers
Sleep not in heaven

Èyin lomo kètùkètù
Èyin lomo kẹyẹkẹyẹ
Èyin lomo òkètùmulàrì
Omọ Kẹyemíkankan
Omọ afìjòkùndọdẹ-àparò
Omọ akáparò-tarátará
Èyin lomo kílukúlu aṣọ
Omọ òdùòdù aṣọ
Omọ òdù òdù ilẹkẹ
Omọ òdù ò rínú kọrọ míì síì
Omọ rírí ní yín tí í maṣọ wọmì
Omọ Kẹkẹ ta dídùn aṣọ lèdìdì èniyànan
Èyin lomo òpó ò gbọran
Baba wa ní a kojú ẹ sígìì ...

Oh the pristine head of
David, Adeniji and our mothers
Arise ... arise ... arise

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È ẹ pẹ fún wa o, a á máa ri yín bá o. Àşẹ.

'Dòtun Ogundéji.

CERTIFICATION

We certify that this work was carried out by Mr. Philip Adédòtun OGUNDEJI in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

A SEMIOTIC STUDY OF DURO LADIPQ'S
MYTHICO-HISTORICAL
PLAYS

	PAGE
TITLE PAGE	i
ABSTRACTS	ii
DEDICATION	v
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	vi
CERTIFICATION BY SUPERVISOR	xi
TABLE OF CONTENTS	xii
LIST OF FIGURES	xvii
 INTRODUCTION	 1
0.1 Objective	2
0.2 Scope	5
NOTES	5
 PART ONE: BACKGROUND STUDY	
	6
 CHAPTER ONE	
SEMiotics: THE THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	7
1.0 Introductory Note: Historical Perspective	7
1.1.0 TEXT	12
1.1.1 Context Extra-text and Intertext	18
1.1.2 Written Text versus Performance Text	21
1.1.3 Binary Opposition	23
1.2.0 SIGNIFICATION	24
1.2.1.0 Modes of Signification	30
1.2.1.1 Iconic signification	31
1.2.1.2 Indexical signification	35
1.2.1.3 Symbolic signification	37

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PAGE

	1.2.1.4 Collateral Relationship between the Three Modes of Signification	40
1.3	WHY SEMIOTICS?	43
	CHAPTER ONE NOTES	46
CHAPTER TWO		
THE DRAMATIC CONTEXT OF DURO LADIPO'S WORKS		
2.0	Introductory Note: Yoruba Drama	51
2.1.0	LABELS	53
2.1.1	Folk Opera	54
2.1.2	Popular Theatre	56
2.1.3	Travelling or Itinerant Theatre	57
2.1.4	Modern or Contemporary Theatre and Modern- Traditional Theatre	58
2.1.5	Professional theatre	60
2.1.6	Nigerian Theatre?	62
2.1.7	The Ogunde Dramatic Tradition and Movement	63
2.2.0	RISE AND DEVELOPMENT	65
2.2.1	Roots	67
2.2.2.0	Development of Dramatic Forms and Styles	76
	2.2.2.1 The Operatic Plays	77
	2.2.2.2 The Transitional Style of the Concert Party Era	79
	2.2.2.3 The Contemporary Situation	82
2.3.0	CREATION OF PLAYS	84
2.3.1	Collective Creation	84
2.3.2	Problem of Collective Creation: The Critic's Perspective	86
2.4.0	PLACES AND MEDIA OF PERFORMANCE	87
2.4.1	The Live Stage	88
2.4.2	Other Media of Performance	89
2.4.3	Comparison of the Performances on the Live Stage and the other Five Media	90

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	PAGE
2.5.0 DURO LADIPO: THE MAN AND HIS REPERTORY	93
2.5.1 The Man Duro Ladipo	93
2.5.2.0 Duro Ladipo's Repertory	109
2.5.2.1 Plays	109
2.5.2.2 Performers	114
CHAPTER TWO NOTES	117
PART TWO: ANALYSIS	
CHAPTER THREE	124
MUSICO-POETIC CODE	125
3.0 INTRODUCTORY NOTE	125
3.1.0 TRADITIONAL MUSICO-POETIC STRUCTURES	128
3.1.1.0 Songs	129
3.1.1.1 Festival Songs	130
3.1.1.2 Children Songs	140
3.1.1.3 War Songs	147
3.1.2 Chants	152
3.2.0 NEO-TRADITIONAL MUSICO-POETIC STRUCTURES	157
3.2.1.0 Extra-plotal Beginning and Ending	157
3.2.1.1 The Opening Glee	159
3.2.1.2 The Closing Glee	169
3.2.2 Dialogised Neo-traditional Songs	176
3.2.3 Non-dialogised Neo-traditional Songs	181
3.3.0 OTHER MUSICO-POETIC STRUCTURES	186
3.3.1 Some Features of Spoken Dialogues	186
3.3.2 Exclamatory Call and Response	186
3.3.3 Instrumentation and Dance	192
3.4 Concluding Notes	199
CHAPTER THREE NOTES	200

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	PAGE
CHAPTER FOUR	
PLOTAL CODE	205
4.0 INTRODUCTORY NOTE	205
4.1.0 SETTING	212
4.1.1 Macro-setting	212
4.1.2.0 Micro-setting	214
4.1.2.1 Àfin (The Palace)	218
4.1.2.2 Igbórò (The Sacred Grove)	221
4.1.2.3 Ojà (The Market-Place)	226
4.1.2.4 Other Micro-settings	228
4.2 THE PLOTAL EXORDIUM	230
4.3.0 PLOTAL PROGRESSION: DEVELOPMENT OF CONFLICT	242
4.3.1.0 Introduction of Conflict	242
4.3.1.1 Direct Introduction of Conflict: <u>Oba Mórò</u> , <u>Oba Kò So</u> , <u>Morèmi</u> and <u>òsun</u>	243
4.3.1.2 Indirect Introduction of Conflict: <u>Obàtálá</u> , <u>Béyí ò Şe</u> , <u>Ajaqun-ńlá</u> and <u>Obá Wàjà</u> .	249
4.3.2.0 Development of Conflict	257
4.3.2.1.0 Development of Conflict Through Intrigues	258
4.3.2.1.1 Unilateral Intrigues	258
4.3.2.1.2 Bilateral Intrigues	265
4.3.2.2 Development of Conflict through Direct Confrontation	268
4.4 THE <u>DÉNOUEMENT</u> : RESOLUTION OF CONFLICT	271
4.5 ADAPTATIONAL STRUCTURE	277
CHAPTER FOUR NOTES	285

TABLE OF CONTENTS

xvi

	PAGE
CHAPTER FIVE: CHARACTERISATIONAL CODE	290
5.0 INTRODUCTORY NOTES	290
5.1.0 CHARACTERIZATIONAL FEATURES	295
5.1.1.0 Characterizational Identificatory features	296
5.1.1.1 Names	297
5.1.1.2 Costume, Make-up, Props and Setting	301
5.1.2 Overall Plotal Functions and Behavioural Features	304
5.2.0 THE PROTAGONISTS	308
5.2.1 Sàngó	308
5.2.2 Mọ̀rèmi	321
5.2.3 Ọ̀bàtálá	331
5.2.4 Baálẹ̀ Apòmù	333
5.3.0 THE ANTAGONISTS	336
5.3.1 Ọ̀ba Ìgbò	336
5.3.2 Èsù	339
5.3.3 Aolẹ̀	341
5.3.4 Ọ̀yófẹ̀sì	345
CHAPTER FIVE NOTES	350
CHAPTER SIX	
CONCLUSION	355
CHAPTER SIX NOTES	366
BIBLIOGRAPHY	368
APPENDIX	389

LIST OF FIGURES

	PAGE
Fig. 1: Inclusiveness of Text, Context and Extra-text	20
Fig. 2: The triangle of Signification	25
Fig. 3: A Classification of Yorùbá Drama. ...	52
Fig. 4: The Sequential Structures of Micro-setting in the plays.	217
Fig. 5: A Summary of the Countings of the Occurrences.	218
Fig. 6: The Structure of the Looseness in <u>Obàtálá's</u> plot.	263
Fig. 7: The Structure of the Looseness in <u>Ajagun-álá's</u> plot.	264
Fig. 8: A Comparison of Propp Souriau and Greimas' Character's Overall Plotal Function. ...	291
Fig. 9: The Binary Oppositional Analysis of the Codification of Şango's Character. ...	319

INTRODUCTION

0.1 Objective

Duro Ladipo is widely known as a dramatist.

Though there is a good deal of writing in the form of brief comments, articles, papers, and chapters in books on him (cf Beier 1967, 1970, Owomoyela 1970, Welch 1972, Banham and Wake 1976, Olatunji 1978, Armstrong 1978, Jeyifo 1984 and Olatunji 1985 etc.), there is up till now no major work on him. The present work is therefore out to fill this major gap.

The main objective of this work is to analyse his mythico-historical plays using semiotic methods. The work is in two parts. The first part provides background information (on the semiotic methods employed and on the general context of Duro Ladipo's works) that helps to put the analysis which constitutes the second part in proper focus. In the second part, the musico-poetic, plotal and characterizational codes are investigated to discover the significating and structural patterns which facilitate the making of meaning.

The present work is one of the few applications of semiotic methods to a group of texts rather than to an individual text as commonly practised. It is therefore

impracticable to give detailed attention to all the significating structures as is the practice in semiotic analyses (e.g. Barthes 1974). Emphasis is therefore placed on general structures common to the texts under analysis.

0.2 Scope

Duro Ladipo's theatre belongs to what we refer to as the Ogunde dramatic tradition and movement in this work (cf 2.1.0-2.1.8 below). At its roots are both the pre-colonial eégún aláre theatre and the "native air opera" or "sacred cantata" of the pre-Ogunde period¹. Ogunde is however the acclaimed pioneer of the contemporary phase of its chequered development, hence the label Ogunde dramatic tradition. Other well-known practitioners in the movement include Kọla Ogunmọla, Oyin Adejọbi, Akin Ogungbe, Moses Ọlaiya Adejumo, Lere Paimo, Işọla Ogunşọla and Adeyemi Afọlayan. General trends and issues in the tradition and movement form the subject matter of the second chapter of this work.

There are not less than thirty-six full-length plays, and many short plays on radio and television in Duro Ladipo's repertory². Using the source of the plot

as criterion, one can classify the plays into four broad categories, namely, biblical plays, plays adapted from other literary sources, social plays, and mythico-historical plays. These categories are discussed in detail in section 2.5.2.1 below and it is with the last category that this work is concerned. It is sufficient to note at this point that a good number of the plays belong to the last group. In fact, plays in other categories usually tend towards achieving the skilful qualities of the mythico-historical plays.

The mythico-historical plays are based on Yorùbá myths, legends and histories about archetypal figures and other events related to Yorùbá beliefs. The life, heroic and non-heroic deeds, death and "non-death" of the archetypal figures culminating in their transmogrification and/or deification usually form the threadonic structure of the plays. The following eight plays have been selected for analysis in this work: Oba Mórò, Oba Kò So, Obá Wàjà, Morèmi, Obátálá, Béyíí ò Še, Ajagun-ńlá and Ọsun. These plays, like many others in the Duro Ladipo repertory, and in fact in the Ogunde dramatic tradition in general, are first and foremost performances. The known written texts are either

transcribed, translated, or adapted directly or indirectly from recordings of performances. Available audio- and audio-visual recordings of the plays from the archives of the Institute of African Studies, University of Ibadan, and television houses have been used in addition to the available written texts. Photo-play performances of some of the plays are also used as supportive texts.

PART ONE

BACKGROUND STUDY

CHAPTER ONE

SEMIOTICS: THE THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

1.0 Historical Perspective

Semiotics is usually defined as the science of signs. "Semiotics is concerned", says Eco (1976: 7), "with everything that can be taken as a sign". It is, in the words of O'Sullivan et al (1983: 210), "the study of the social production of meaning from sign systems". As a method of text analysis, semiotics does not focus only on the formal organization of the text, but also on the internal organization of the significating systems and the dynamics of the process of meaning and establishment of sense (cf Pavis 1982: 13). Put another way, semiotics identifies and relates the componential significating patterns of the texts to one another before studying the relationship of the textual structures to larger structures (i.e. society) in an attempt at grasping the total meaning.

The study of signs has, according to Kowzan (1968: 52), been popular in the philosophy and history of the sciences. Hippocrates and the Stoics, Plato and Aristotle, Saint Augustine and Descartes, Leibnz and

Locke, Hegel and Humboldt are among those who are said to have dealt with the idea of signs. According to Kowzan (1968: 52), other sciences which the study of signs has engendered include "semiology ... semasiology, semantics and sematology". He, however, further notes that semiology and semiotics have enjoyed a richer and longer career than others.

"Semiology" and "semiotics" were formally proposed at the opposite sides of the Atlantic at the beginning of this century. The Swiss linguist, Ferdinand de Saussure called it "semiology" while the American philosopher, Charles Sanders Peirce, called it "semiotics". Though the Saussure's perspective is sociological and linguistic while that of Peirce's is philosophical and logical, the two words "semiotics" and "semiology", refer to the same discipline today (Guiraud 1971: 2, Fiske and Hartley 1978: 37 and Abrams 1981: 170). The Saussure's term (sémiologie) has been retained by the Parisian semioticians while the Eastern European, Italian and American semioticians have stuck to Peirce's term (Scholes 1982: 147).

On the level of theoretical development itself, one can say that semiotics developed out of structuralism

which in turn evolved out of formalism. The progression from formalism to semiotics is, however, not easily divisible into its three phases. This is to say that there is a complex type of overlapping among them, so that one cannot easily identify where one ends and another begins. This overlapping is more acute in the structuralism/semiotics interaction than in the interaction of the two with formalism. This situation is perhaps clearly borne out by the fact that Roman Jakobson who was one of the foremost Russian formalists also belonged to the Czechoslovakian Prague School that actually developed "the first systematic structuralist-semiotic approach to the study of art" (Deak 1976: 83). Structuralists such as Roland Barthes of the Parisian school and Jan Mukařovský of the Prague school are also known as semioticians. In fact Abrams (1981: 171) clearly says that "many current semioticians are also structuralists". Formalism and Structuralism merge continuously by direct methodological analogies and interactions which make a sharp division appear neither possible nor necessary (Striedster 1977: 430). And Hawkes (1977: 124) considers semiotics to be the most fruitful concept deriving from the general structuralist

enterprise of the last two decades and not easily distinguishable from it.

Taking Eco's definition quoted above into consideration, one realizes that the semiotic field is quite large ranging from

the communicative behaviour of animals (zoo semiotics) to the analysis of human bodily communication (Kinesics and proxemics) olfactory signs (the "code of scents") aesthetic theory and rhetorics.

(Hawkes 1977: 124).

Even symptoms, as in the case of medical semiotics, and behavioural and value systems such as etiquette and mode of dressing, are also studied by semioticians¹.

Semiotics studies all cultural process as a process of communication made possible by a basic system of signification (Eco 1976: 8, 22). The process of communication and the system of signification are dialectically related. There is no doubt that every work of art has a potentially communicative function and that this function is complicated in the representational arts. What is true, in this sense of the communicative function is also true of the underlying

significatory system. The situation is more complex in drama and theatre than in most other arts as we will show in this work.

Semiotics should be considered an improvement on pure structuralism which leans towards formalism because it concerns itself not only with the production of meanings out of the structural relations that exist within any sign system but because it also relates "the production of meanings to other kinds of social production and to social relations" (cf O'Sullivan et al 1983: 210).

We will now go on to discuss the relevant cardinal notions of semiotics. Since according to Scholes (1982: 1), the humanities may be defined as those disciplines primarily devoted to the study of text, semiotics as a humanistic method and theory "is in the first place text-centred" (O'Sullivan et al. 1983: 211). We will therefore first of all discuss text in semiotic terms before we go on to discuss signification.

1.1.0

TEXT

Text is usually conceived as a composite structure through which meaning is passed from an addresser to an addressee and as made up of signs organised by certain conventions, rules or codes².

The written language is the common example of text and it is the only thing seen as such by the formalists and certain structuralists. Other brands of structuralism also consider oral or spoken speech as text³. Texts in oral speech are manifested in supralinguistic organization so that they can easily be recaptured when needed. This is how oral text caters for the crucial criterion of the spatial condition (Lotman and Uspensky 1978: 234-235). Experience has however shown that despite the supra-organization, in many cases, the oral text is not as rigidly fixed as the written text, so that each performance of the same text usually results in variations. The message, however, always remains constant despite the variations. The variations can be accommodated since as O'Sullivan et al. (1983: 238) have shown, the word "message" is often used instead of

"text". Lotman and Uspensky (1978: 235) have noted that the development of audio recording instruments has removed the necessity "for a text to be graphically expressed"⁴. The recorded text can always be played back when needed. Of course, there is also the usual advantage of transcription.

The semiotic text is not limited to either the written or oral texts. It can be plastic or musical, mimetic or architectural. According to Bouisacc (1976: 104) who analysed the circus performance as text, a text is

any permanent set of ordered elements, either sentences, objects, actions, (or combination of any of these) of which the co-presence (or collocation) is considered by an encoder and/or a decoder as being related in some capacity one to another through the mediation of a logico-semantic system.

This quotation is a succinct description of what a text is from a semiotic viewpoint. By "logico-semantic system" Bouisacc means the same thing as what we have earlier in this section described as "conventions, rules

or codes". Code is preferred to other terms in semiotics. According to Scholes (1982: 143), the code is a "system of thought ... that enables us to make sense of an event". A text is usually a network of codes (or sub-codes) that allows for the production of meaning within the addresser/addressee's socio-cultural experience (Eco 1976: 57, and O'Sullivan et al 1983: 238). We will expatiate further on the nature of codes in our discussion of signification. It is, however, sufficient to note here that the basic rubric of text analysis from the semiotic angle lies in discovering the codes and/or subcodes that make up the text. This is why the major sections of this work are devoted to discussing the codes that constitute the texts.

In literary texts, meanings are aesthetically transmitted. According to Lotman (1976) "the aesthetically functioning text" is a text whose semantic weighting is greater, not smaller, than non-literary texts". And according to Guiraud (1971: 28) literary texts are poly-semantic while non-literary texts are mono-semantic; the poly-semantic text consists of

connotative codes while the mono-semic text is made up of denotative codes. The "semantic weight" of a theatrical performance is greatest. Alter (1979: 247) describes the theatre as a "semiotician's nightmare". She says "theatre is a two-faced semiotic monster, each face presenting a different network of sign systems". McGuire (1980: 48) testifies to this when she says that "theatre is made up of codes (linguistic, spatial, gestural, scenographic, illuminating etc.) co-existing in a dialectical relationship with non-theatre". Kowzan (1968), for example, establishes thirteen sign systems or codes as basic components of theatre. They are "word", "tone", "mime", "gesture", "movement", "hair-style", "costume", "accessory", "make-up", "decor", "lighting", "music" and "sound effect". These theatrical codes can be collapsed into six for economy. The suggested classification will look like this in comparison with the Kowzan's.

"NEW"	KOWZAN
Linguistic code	- word, tone
Acting code ⁵	- movement, gesture, mime
Musical code	- music and sound effects
Illuminational code	- lighting
Costuming code	- costume, make-up, hair-style
Setting code	- decor, accessory

Two other codes are added to cater for the type of analysis presented in this work. These are Characterizational and Plotal codes. These eight code systems can further be grouped into three broad classes, A B and C in line with the nature of our data and analytical procedure as follows:

- A - Linguistic code
- Characterizational code
- Plotal code

- B - Musical code

- C - Setting code
- Illuminational code
- Acting code
- Costuming code.

Whereas the study of codes in group C requires the

experience of live-performance or, to some extent, reliance on audio-visual recordings, those codes in A can be conveniently based on the written text and audio-recordings of the performance. The musical code in group B is a medial category in that part of it can be studied under live performance (i.e. the instruments and dances), while the song content can be studied on the poetic (i.e. linguistic) level of class A.

In our analysis, the linguistic, or more properly in literary terms, the poetic code, is treated along with the musical code. This is possible because poetry along with dance and instrumentation is, as we will further discuss in chapter three (3.0), an integral part of Yorùbá music. The nature of our data and the literary orientation of this work make emphasis on codes in category A unavoidable. As our analysis will reveal, since the treatment of the poetic code is given prominence in our discussion of music, we have decided to label the code, musico-poetic. As already said in the opening section (0.2) to this work, a substantial part of the texts constituting our data is derived from audio-recordings, which do not provide information useful for analysis in the area of category C. The few analyses

done in the area of category C are based on few audio-visual recorded plays supplemented by photo-play texts and personal experience as a member of the Yorùbá theatre audience. Such analyses are on costuming, setting and acting codes. The illuminational code is not discussed at all, considering the nature of our data. Thus for this work the main codes analysed are:

 Musico-poetic code

 Plotal code

 Characterizational code

Other codes are discussed as sub-codes; costuming code is, for example, treated as a characterizational sub-code while the setting is treated as a plotal sub-code.

1.1.1 Context, Extra-text and Intertext

The semiotic conception of context, extra-text and intertext are based on the general structuralist principle of relation between systems. The idea that the existence of a system depends on its relation to other systems is the kernel to structuralism and semiotics.

The notion of context, according to Yai (1981: 6) is coterminous with that of text. The two common views about

context are those of context of situation and context of culture. The first one refers to the immediate social situation and environment of the text while the second refers to the wider socio-political and historical circumstances and conditions of the text (O'Sullivan et al. 1983: 53). The first one can also be called micro-context and the second macro-context. The macro-context which encompasses the micro-context is also known in semiotics as extra-text. The notion of the context (the micro-context) and extra-text (the macro-context) is related to that of intertext⁶. The notion of intertext holds that one or more texts are usually found lurking in another text. The texts found lurking in another text can either be taken as particularly being part of the context or generally that of the extra-text depending on their relational proximity to the particular text under study. Whatever the case may be, the text being analysed and others found lurking in it, known as "sub-text" in semiotic parlance, form parts of the extra-text as a whole. The inclusiveness of the above concepts can be represented as follows:

- T₀ - Particular text being analysed.
 T₁ - Other texts that are directly related to T₀
 C - Context of situation (or micro-context)
 T₂ - Other texts indirectly related to T₀
 ET - Extra-texts (cultural context or macro-context).

Fig.1 Inclusiveness of text, context and extra-text

The implication of the semiotic notions of text and extra-text as explained here is that, the literary

text, the object of analysis, is seen as an integral part of the total cultural activity which is the extra-text. So that as Shukman (1976) has noted we are able to consider the author's consciousness and the audience's expectation along with the problem of literature as a manifestation of culture.

1.1.2 Written Text versus Performance Text

Theatre semioticians have considered the problem of written versus performance text. In fact it is these two aspects of theatre semiotics that Alter (1979: 247) refers to as the two faces of the semiotic monster called theatre. The common stand on this issue can be represented by that of Pagnini (1970) and Kowzan (1976) as presented by McGuire (1980). Pagnini, using Chomskian terminologies defines the written text (dramatic) as the "deep structure" of the performance text. Kowzan on the other hand sees the written text as "the invariable of the final staging". These views place the written text in a special relationship to the performance text (cf Eco 1977: 108 and Elam 1980: 208). The written text is however incomplete, it is lifeless, and dramatic

actions in it are only latent. The stage directions which usually accompany the written text cannot cope with the purpose they are intended to achieve. A lot depends on the director and actors who have to interpret such directions within the scope of their experiences. As Elam (1980: 208-209) has rightly noted, though it is true that "The written text constrains the performance in obvious ways ... it is equally legitimate to claim that ... the performance or at least a possible or 'model' performance, constrains the dramatic text in its very articulation". Paolla Gulli Pugliatti's view, that the dramatic text should be considered as a "linguistic transcription of a stage potentiality which is the motive force of the written text" (Elam 1980: 209), is quite relevant to the situation of the written texts in our data. It has already been pointed out in section 0.2 above that the known written texts in the Ogunde dramatic tradition are either directly or indirectly derived from the performance through transcription and/or translation. We can therefore, in principle, not afford to rely on a notion that places the written text above the performance text in this work. Though the present work is substantially literary in orientation

we cannot afford to neglect the theatrical aspects which flesh up and give the dramatic aspects their life. We completely agree with Elam (1980: 209) that

the written text/performance text relationship is not one of simple priority, but a complex of reciprocal constraints constituting a powerful intertextuality.⁷

1.1.3 Binary Opposition

The notion of binary opposition which was borrowed by literary structuralists from their linguistic counterparts is also crucial to semiotic textual analysis. Tamir-Guez (1978: 241) puts the case thus: "The necessary condition of binary opposition is that the existence of one element requires the co-existence of its opposite". Binary opposition is regarded as the primary or "fundamental operation of the human mind, basic to the production of meaning ... the smallest common denominator of all thoughts" (Culler 1975: 15, Tamir-Guez 1978: 241). The methodological primacy of binary opposition process, according to Culler (1975:

15), indicates its place as a "fundamental operation of human thought" and therefore of human semiotics.

As Macguire (1980) noted, the discussion of theatre has been generally polarised along the lines of binary opposition. written text versus performance, scholars versus practitioners, historians versus reviewers. In the making of a round character within a literary text, the good and bad aspects of human nature are presented, and in the development of a plot there are usually two forces at loggerheads to complicate issues and make the story interesting. Binary opposition can, however, be misleading if the qualitative distinction it organises are irrelevant. The moral involved in the use of this notion is to desist from establishing merely "elegant structures" (Culler 1975: 16).

1.2.0

SIGNIFICATION

Also known as "codification" (Guiraud 1971: 24-25) and "semiosis" (Barthes 1967: 48 and Eco 1976), signification can simply be defined as the process of sign formation, "the act which binds the signifier and

the signified, an act whose product is the sign" (Barthes 1967: 48). "Signifier" and "signified" are Saussure's terminologies which have been given other names by other scholars. Examples of such names include "signan" and "sign vehicle" for signifier and "signatum", "significatum" and "sign function" for signified". Another common way of conceiving the process of sign formation, usually acknowledged as Piercian (Eco 1976: 59), is to see it as "a triadic relation, which may be further analysed into three dyadic relations, two basic and one derivative" (Lyons 1977: 96).

Fig. 2 The triangle of signification

A-C in the above diagram, is the derivative dyadic relation comparable to the former Saussurean signifier/signified relationship. Hence our use of the Saussurean

terminologies. It is therefore clearly shown that the two ways of conceiving signification are not necessarily exclusive. We have followed Lyon's (1977) simple conception of the triadic relation, which he adapted after "a traditional analysis of signification - the one that is expressed in the scholastic maxim: 'vox significat [rem] mediantibus' ... 'the word signifies [the thing] by means of mediating concepts'". It should, however, be noted that what he labelled as "sign" and "significatum" have been altered to signifier and signified respectively because of our interest in showing that the two ways of construing signification are not necessarily exclusive of each other. In fact the mediating "concept" (B) between the signifier (A) and signified (C) (which creates the other two dyadic basic relations) can be construed as the sign itself, the fused form, (or total concept) of the two components. The triadic conception of signification, though simple in itself has become problematic owing to the different interpretations given to it by different scholars ranging from Pierce himself to Ogden and Richards and Frege (cf Lyons 1977: 96-99 and Eco 1976: 59-62). The scholars do not only

disagree on the terminologies but also on the positioning of each node on the triangle.

The signifier is the immediate perceptible aspect of the sign standing for or referring to the signified which may not be immediate. The problem has usually not been in what constitutes the signifier but in what constitutes the signified. Some see it as the object to which the signifier refers, others see it as the idea or concept itself. Though it is possible for a signifier to be referring to an object, it is, however, also true that not all things that can be signified are objects (cf Eco 1979: 66-68).

The relationship between the signifier and the signified is no doubt a dialectic one. In the actual sense of it the sign is indissoluble. Its separation into signifier and signified is only for theoretical and pedagogic convenience. The correlation according to Barthes (1967: 48) does not even exhaust the significating process or "semantic act, for the sign derives its values also from its surroundings" i.e. from other signs with which it is syntagmatically and paradigmatically related in the text and extra-text⁸.

Before we go on to look at the three types of signs

identified in our texts, let us place the concept of "code" within the significating process. If "code", according to Eco (1976: 49), "provides the rules which generate signs as concrete occurrence in communicative intercourse", then the domain of code in signification is in correlating the signifier to the signified. It is actually in the ground or motivation on which the two components, signifier and signified, are united that code as sign generating system operates. When we therefore talk of the code as a system we mean the significating patterns in a text or group of texts, which allows for the attachment of meaning (signified) to the sign vehicle (signifier) (Elam 1980: 50 etc.).

/ Signification is essentially a conventional process. This is why Eco (1979: 28) asserts that "The laws of signification are the laws of culture". The correlation between the signifier and the signified, the code, is usually agreed upon by the society. It is usually a societal property. This is what makes communication possible. Such conventional relationships between the two components of the sign are usually taken as either motivated or unmotivated (Also known as 'arbitrary' 'non-arbitrary' Lyons 1977: 99-108). It is on these

principles of motivation and convention that types of signs or mode of sign productions to be discussed in the next section are based.

But it is important to note that the ideas of motivated sign and unmotivated sign, or their respective conventions as the case may be, are not exclusive of each other as they seemingly look. The so-called unmotivated signs in some, if not many, cases are originally motivated. According to Guiraud (1971: 27):

... very often the specific principle of a sign is motivated, although historical evolution tends to obliterate that motivation. And to the extent that the original motivation is no longer perceived the sign comes to function by virtue of convention alone.

It is perhaps such signs whose motivation are lost in history that are often referred to as "unmotivated signs". The case of the linguistic sign which is commonly agreed to be unmotivated or arbitrary may perhaps not be completely so. There are, for example, cases of "onomatopoeia" and "ideophones" (both phonosemantic in nature) where the phonological signifiers

and their senses or meaning, the signified, share a certain degree of correlation and are therefore at least partly motivated. The differences that exist between an onomatopoeic signifier of a particular sound from language to language which have always been cited to argue for the arbitrariness of onomatopoeic signification may partly be explained by the phonological and cultural differences. This is probably why /mèéè/ in Yorùbá differs from /baa/ in English despite the fact that both are onomatopoeic signifiers of the same signified cry of a sheep.

1.2.1.0 Modes of Signification

The three modes of signification identifiable by the types of relationship between the signifier and the signified postulated by Pierce and discussed below are the iconic mode, the indexical mode and the symbolic mode.

1.2.1.1 Iconic Signification

The relationship between the signifier and the signified in an iconic signification is based on similarity or fitness. So that this relationship is,

as will soon be shown, unlike that of symbolic signification, motivated. In Pierce's words (as quoted in Elam 1980: 21),

An icon is a sign which refers to the object that it denotes merely by virtue of characters of its own and which it possesses Anything whatever, be it quality, existent individual or law, is an Icon of anything, in so far as it is like that thing and used as a sign of it.

The fact that this definition is an elastic one is further borne out by the three categories of icon which Pierce identifies - the image, diagram and metaphor. The relationship between the signifier and the signified in the three types of iconic signification, no doubt, varies considerably. In the image, for example, we can have concrete objects as signifiers, while the diagram (signifier) is often a sketch or outline on paper. Metaphor on the other hand is traditionally restricted to the literary and linguistic context. We therefore have to reconsider the definition for our own purpose in this work.

Examples usually cited of iconic signs (signs derived from iconic mode of signification) include photographs and life portraits. These two examples are all right according to the new definition that will soon be presented. As discussed by Lyons (1977) onomatopoeia can also be cited as examples of linguistic icons. In accordance with the Peircean definition, Lyons considers ideophones like "dither", "dodder", "quiver", "slink", "gloom" and "grumpy" etc. as cases of secondary onomatopoeia, i.e. secondary icons, since onomatopoeia is seen as primary icons. Lyons, (1977: 104), however, also notes that.

All these examples of secondary onomatopoeia in which the sound of the spoken word-form is felt to be appropriate to the meaning of the lexemes of which they are forms, though the words do not actually denote sounds or source of sounds, illustrate the phenomenon traditionally known as sound-symbolism (or phonaesthesia).

We will, for our purpose, in this work restrict the scope of iconic signification to signs where the

similarity between the signifier and the signified is direct and apparent, so that examples of secondary onomatopoeia or icons and metaphors in general will not be taken as instances of iconic signification under this definition. Abstract paintings, drawings and images belong to the metaphoric mode - the connection between their signifier and signified is usually indirect and not apparent - they are therefore not iconic under our own definition. But life painting, drawing, images and photographs are considered as examples of iconic signification because the relationship between the signifier and signified is usually direct and apparent.⁹

The various carved images of the trickster god Eṣù in Yorùbá religious tradition are considered, under our new definition, as iconic signifiers of the god himself. The description of Eṣù's long protruding occiput found in different Eṣu myths and praise poetry is usually portrayed in such carvings. The various carved masks used by the itinerant eégún aláré dramatists are also icons of the characters being personified during performances. Examples of such

masks include the Tápà mask with the Yàgbà facial marks characteristic of the Nupe, who are one of the immediate neighbours of the Yorùbá to the north (and are generally known as Tápà by them). The òyinbó, white man's mask has a long nose and tufty hair to match (cf Adedeji 1969 and Götrick 1984).

Before bringing to a close this discussion on iconic signification, it should be mentioned that the theatre is a "perfect domain" of iconization (Elam 1980: 22ff). The actor-character (signifier-signified) relationship is, no doubt, an instance of a good iconic signification. As will be shown at length in Chapter Five, costumes, hand properties (and other items of decor) can on one hand be seen as part of the iconising elements in the actor-character relationship. In fact, the actor-character signification can in itself be taken as an iconic text¹⁰. In his discussion of this subject Elam (1980: 22-23) notes that:

✓
For film
The theatre is perhaps the only art form able to exploit what might be termed iconic identity: the sign vehicle denoting a rich silk costume may well be a rich silk costume rather than an illusion thereof created by pigment on

canvas and image conserved on celluloid or a description.

In the theatrical tradition which Duro Ladipo operates the costumic significations are indeed instances of auto-iconization, where the costumes signify themselves. The òfi, etù, sányán and àdirẹ textile materials used in building big agbádá and dàndóógó, both large overall garments, are real and not illusions.

1.2.1.2 Indexical Signification

The relationship between the signifier and the signified in the indexical signification is either causal or just sequential. The relationship is therefore also motivated. Indexicalization is, in a sense, central in the signification process, for the very nature of the signifier in referring to the signified is indexical in all significations. The pointing function, no doubt, underlies signification. An example usually given as a good instance of indexical signification is that of the smoke which indicates the fire at its source. To an adventurer in the forest, the smoke will not only **indicate** the fire but also the person who makes the fire. Another common example is that of the knock on

the door that indicates the presence of a person by the door (cf Elam 1980, Hawkes 1977, O'Sullivan *et al.* 1983 etc.). The òpá àṣẹ, (staff of authority), of an oba, when present at a social ceremony is an indexical signifier of the oba's consent to the activities and/or of royal connection in general. The sending of a cap, (filà), or ring (òrùka), usually worn by someone, as part of an arokò¹¹ to another person is an indexical signification that assures the receiver that the messenger, and therefore the message, is actually sent by the sender, the owner of the cap or ring.

Symptoms as noted by Lyons (1977) are, no doubt, instances of indexical significations, pointing to their causes or sources. The states or situations indicated by symptoms can be "an emotional state (fear, anger, sexual arousal or readiness etc.), a state of health (suffering from laryngitis etc.), a state of intoxication or whatever will be described as symptomatic of that state" (Lyons 1977: 108). It is in this area that medical semiotics operates and the symptoms no doubt find a way in the theatrical art of miming and gesticulation where they are employed by the

performer in impersonating the character's state and general condition or where they are used to "tell lies" - "truthful lies"¹². Another domain where indexical signification glaringly operates in the theatrical and dramatic arts is in the lineal structures, especially the plot, which are no doubt based on causality and sequentiality.

1.2.1.3 Symbolic Signification

In symbolic signification, the relationship between the signifier and the signified is usually considered to be unmotivated, arbitrary and only conventional. Both Saussure and Pierce agree that the linguistic sign is the proper example of unmotivated signification, though it is only Pierce who designated such signification as symbol. It is believed that the word "tree" (or igi in Yorùbá), for example, has nothing in common with the object or concept to which it refers. We have already discussed how one can see onomatopoeia as somehow related to what it refers to and can therefore be considered as instances of motivated signification under the iconic mode (cf 1.2.1.1 above). We have also pointed out that most of the signs usually regarded as unmotivated and

only conventional might have originally been motivated in history.

In extra-linguistic symbolization, of the type found in Yorùbá àrokò, there is usually a sort of indirect and hidden motivation, that can only be contextually explained. This is unlike in the iconic signification where the motivation is, as already said direct and apparent. The symbolism of the national flag signifying Nigeria (or any other nation) is primarily derived from the signifieds attached to the colours (signifiers). Though the flag (including the pole and the piece of cloth) has no obvious relation to the country and therefore tends to be seen as unmotivated, Nigeria's green-white-green colours cannot be said to be chosen and arranged arbitrarily¹³. In fact, it is because the motivation for choosing and arranging the colours of a flag differs from country to country that we have different flags throughout the world.

Examples from the Yorùbá àrokò system include the sending of èsúró, (yellow yam), and ewúro (bitter leaf) to a person facing an unpleasant and tedious situation in life. The èsúró in this context symbolizes the nauseating aspect of the situation. This symbolism is

derived from a type of word play signification in Yorùbá rhetoric. It is the syllable /sú/ of èsúró which is similar in form to the verb sú (to be tired/bored/exasperated) that serves as the motivating factor that confers the symbolic meaning of something that can effectuate the meaning sú on esúró¹⁴. Ewúro is a plant that initially tastes bitter but leaves a pleasant after-taste in the mouth. There is even a proverbial saying that confirms this, "Adùn ní í gbèyin ewúro", ("It is the sweet taste that comes after eating the bitter leaf"). Ewúro in this connection and in the context of the arokò under discussion is a symbol of better things to come if the present condition is endured.

The symbolism involved in the above examples of arokò signification are metaphorically motivated on the ground of certain cultural conventional similarities that are not physically apparent but are logically derived. Such symbolisms are referred to as meta-symbolization in this work. It is also not impossible to have metonymically motivated symbols, (meto-symbolization), where the signifier substituted for the signified has a contagious relationship with the

signified. An example from the arokò system is the use of sand taken from a piece of land, which one wants to be leased out to oneself, as a signifier of the piece of land. Such sand is usually sent from the person who wants the land in a covered white calabash to the owner or custodian of the land (Opádòtun 1986: 48).

1.2.1.4 Collateral Relationship Between the Three Modes of Signification.

It is implicit from the examples and discussion of the three modes of signification above that they are not exclusive of one another. We have mentioned the fact that indexical signification underlies the remaining modes because of its pointing nature. Though we have for theoretical purposes discussed the three modes separately, what usually operates is that they co-exist hierarchically and it is the context that usually determines the dominant mode.

Hawkes (1977: 129) has put the situation clearly:

the 'triad' involves not mutually exclusive kinds of signs but three modes of a relationship between sign and object or signifier which co-exist in the form of a hierarchy in which one of them will inevitably have dominance

over the two. As Jakobson observes we can have symbolic icons, iconic symbols, etc., and the nature of a sign's ultimately dominant mode will depend finally on its context

...

Hawkes gives the example of the traffic signal which according to him is, in epistemological terms, an index and at the same time a symbol. The red light of the traffic signal is a conventional symbol of danger and at the same time an index that the driver should stop the vehicle for other road users to pass the junction. The green light, on the other hand, is also a conventional symbol of the opposite meaning - i.e. no danger - and also at the same time an index to the fact that the road ahead is clear and the driver can go through the junction. It is the indexical signification in the traffic light context that takes the dominant position over the symbolic context. Let us give an example from the Yorùbá àrokò semiotic system to illustrate the co-existence of the three significating modes and how the context determines the dominating one of the three.

The carved wooden double-edged axe¹⁵, though usually

found in the Şàngó ritual context can be logically construed as an icon of a double-edged iron axe, though such an iron axe is not commonly found among the Yorùbá. The presence of the single-edged iron axe among the Yorùbá makes the double-edged one also a paradigmatic possibility, especially when one considers the paradigm of closely related objects like a cutlass, knife and sword that have both single and double-edged types. We should not, however, forget that the iconic signification of the double-edged carved wooden axe as a signifier of its iron counterpart is primarily derived from an extra-Şàngó context and only logically postulated. Within the Şàngó ritual context the wood carving of the double-edged axe is known primarily as oşé Şàngó and it can be construed as the symbol of justice for which Şàngó stands. This symbolic quality of the oşé can, however, in turn be seen as being causally derived on the ground of the belief that Şàngó uses the axe in meting out justice - by killing the guilty with it. If this explanation is acceptable, then it is the symbolic signification that is dominant while the other two significations are only secondarily

contributive to the making of the primary one¹⁶. The osé Şàngó can also be generally seen as an indexical signifier attaching the possessor to the Şàngó cult, since it is essentially a Şàngó ritual object. If, however, the osé^{is}/taken as standing for Şàngó himself, which is a possibility especially in an àrokò where the osé, together with some other objects is sent to someone as a signifier of the fact that Şàngó will have to be the arbiter in a misunderstanding between the sender and the receiver (cf Qpádòtun 1986: 26), then the predominant signification is that of symbolization - meto-symbolization¹⁷ to be specific.

The point about the context as a central determining factor in a sensible decodification of a sign proves that sign systems are quintessentially conventional and culture-bound (cf Lotman and Uspensky 1978: 233-243 and Eco 1976: 66-68).

1.3 WHY SEMIOTICS?

African literary scholars, such as Izevbaye (1975, 1977) and Irele (1977) have already indicated in their critical comments on adaptation and adoption

of critical methods for African literature that an eclectic approach will be more fruitful than any individual approach. It is indeed for its eclecticism that semiotics is preferable to other approaches in this work.

There are two basic axes in a literary text: the syntagmatic (horizontal axis of combination) and the paradigmatic (vertical axis of selection). Whereas formalism, (including New Criticism) and most other sociological approaches, take care of only one of the two axes each, semiotics takes care of both. It (semiotics) combines the "intrinsic" or "centrifugal" approach of the formalists with the "extrinsic" or "centripetal" approach of the sociological critics. This is primarily made possible by the cardinal principle of relationship between systems which underlies semiotic analysis.

From the semiotic perspective, neither the addresser (author) nor the addressee (audience) is free to make meaning. The making of meaning is essentially conditioned by the relevant conventional codes, the structures that enables and constrains

meaning" (Scholes 1982: 126). This should, however, not be seen as implying a total disregard of the authorial or responsorial perspective in semiotic analyses. Semiotics does not replace other approaches. It only unifies them "by integrating itself with them by assimilating the known results of such approaches into its own theory" (Scholes 1974: 2 and Pavis 1982: 25). Semiotic analysis is therefore not completely different from other traditional analyses. It only studies meaning more vigorously and more systematically from a different perspective by emphasizing the code. Semiotics, therefore investigates meaning from a more vigorous dimension by considering the intratextual, intertextual and extra-textual significations.

The semiotic approach to literary studies also benefits a lot from its application to other aspects of life. The approach is no doubt more appropriate than others for dramatic texts, such as those under investigation, which are derived from a complex juxtaposition of rich cultural materials and literary conventions.

CHAPTER ONE

NOTES

1. For further information on the enormous extent of the semiotic field of Eco 1976, Barthes 1957, 1967, Guiraud 1971, Culler 1976, Scholes 1982 and Silvana 1981.
2. Though Eco (1976: 49) is of the view that to say that "code organizes signs" is different from saying that it "provides the rules which generate the signs", (which he prefers), we are of the opinion that the two definitions are really not opposing. They, to us infact, imply each other.
3. The opposing views of Frye [in his Anatomy of Criticism (1976: 20), which is described by Scholes (1976: 20) "A major document in Anglo/American structuralism"] on the status of the popular (oral) literature, as "highly conventionalized" of "great value" and "no more fashionable to mark off" yet "naive", primitive" and "popular", can be taken as indicative of his reluctance to accept the objectivity of the high quality of the "popular" (oral) literature against the subjectivity of the Anglo-American received notion about such literatures and their people.

4. Similar observation is also true of audio-visual gadgets in the context of the performing arts.
5. We are not unaware of the usual practice of regarding speech as action. The present dichotomization is only for ease of analysis.
6. We shall henceforth use "context" to mean "micro-context" and "extratext" to mean "macro-context".
7. This view is even shared by some drama critics who are primarily written-text-oriented. See Styan 1960, Boulton 1960; Williams 1968 and Crow 1983.
8. This notion is, we believe, the basis of connotative signification and what Eco 1976: 19 calls "unlimited semiosis" cf Barthes 1967:90-92, Eco 1976: 54-57.
9. Eco (1976: 204-205) discusses extensively the relationship between the drawing and the drawn. He argues that the relationship we take as apparent and glaring in such a case is just only conventional. It is therefore recognised that it is the convention that makes such relation apparent.
10. See Bouisacc 1976, Scholes 1982 and Enninger 1984 for examples of analyses where the circus horse, female body and artifacts, such as "windwheels, clothing and hairstyle" are treated as texts or

part of texts respectively. Also see Barthes 1957: 18 where The physique of wrestlers is said to constitute "a basic sign which like a seed contains the fight".

11. Àrokò is a Yorùbá indigenous semiotic system where objects are used as signifiers of certain "messages" transmitted between an addresser and an addressee. A meaningful application of the semiotic theory in the Yorùbá context will no doubt benefit immensely from a sound understanding of the arokò system (See Şofqla 1983 and Qpadqtun 1986 on the subject).
12. Eco, (1976: 6-7) defines the sign as "everything that can be taken as significantly substituting for something else". He also notes that the substituted thing does not have to exist or be temporally and spatially co-present with the thing substituting it. He then concludes that semiotics, which he has earlier described as "concerned with everything that can be taken as a sign" "is in principle studying everything which can be used to lie". Jeyifo (1986) also refers to dramatic arts as "truthful lies". This implies that dramatic arts and even all literary types and other representational and presentational arts and systems, belong to the semiotic field. The Yorùbá also share this view which is expressed

in the saying "iró ní í jẹ àlọ", ("A lie is what a folktale is"). Despite the denotative truism of the saying the Yorùbá use folktales in instructing their young ones - truthful lie.

13. The whole flag is a symbol when it stands for the country. It is, however, possible to see it as a text where different significations co-exist. The green colour in the Nigerian flag is iconic of agriculture while the white colour is symbolic of the peace which the country is always striving to achieve. The arrangement is also symbolic of a peaceful country, very rich in agriculture. Hence the double occurrence of the green colour and its peculiar arrangement (cf section 1.2.4).
14. The use of the symbolic wordplay is most prominent in Yorùbá incantations. The beliefs that underlie the use of symbolic wordplay in particular and incantation in general include: homoepathic magic, contagious magic, magic of names, origin and primeval experiences (of incantatory agents) and the power of the spoken word [See Qlatunji 1984: 140-146 and 160-162 on symbolic wordplay itself; also 1985: 273-286].
15. The carved-wooden double-edged axe is a prominent hand prop indicating Şàngó in Qba Kò So, Qbátálá and Qşun.

16. On the hierarchical scale the indexical signification comes next to the symbolic one while the iconic one comes last.
17. The signification is meto-symbolic because the oşé as part of the Şàngó paraphernalia is being used to stand for Şàngó himself. It should be noted that the present instance of meto-symbolization is, unlike most of those discussed in Chapter Five, not iconic.

CHAPTER TWO

THE DRAMATIC CONTEXT OF DURO LADIPQ'S WORKS

2.0 Introductory note: Yorùbá drama

When we talk of Yorùbá drama, we mean the drama that uses the Yorùbá language and other communicative codes in expressing views on the Yorùbá world in general¹. There are four important subcategories of plays in Yorùbá drama: sacred, eégún aláre (masqued players)², "Ogunde dramatic tradition"³ and scripted plays. It is very common to broadly classify the first two as traditional and the last two as modern⁴ plays (cf Rotimi 1971: 36, Graham-White 1974: 2, Adedeji 1975: 52, J.P. Clark 1981, Ogunbiyi 1981: 9, Işola 1981: 399, Ogundeji 1981: 25). But as Nkosi (1981: 173ff.) shows and as our discussion in the next sections will further show, this classification is problematic. We therefore prefer an alternative broad classification that groups the first three types of plays as unscripted against the scripted one. The unscripted plays are primarily performances. It should, however, be pointed out that there are some scripts of plays in the Ogunde

dramatic tradition. Such scripts emanated from edited versions of transcribed texts of the plays and they are usually grouped along with other scripted plays (see Işqalá 1981: 409 where Duro Ladipo's plays are so grouped). They are, for example, studied in schools together with other scripted plays unlike the unscripted ones. It is therefore important to point out clearly that there are two types of scripted plays: the originally scripted (àpilèkq) and those that are derived from edited transcribed texts (àdálórí àdàkq). The classification can be illustrated thus:

Fig. 3 A Classification of Yorùbá Drama

"The Ogunde dramatic tradition" with its movement forms the focus of attention in this chapter since it is the immediate dramatic network within which

Duro Ladipo operates. References are, however, made to other categories of Yoruba drama where necessary. Topics discussed in this chapter include the issue of appropriate labelling, the rise and development of the tradition, the creation of plays, and places and media of performances. A brief survey on the man, Duro Ladipo, and his repertory is also attempted to help in placing the whole chapter in the perspective of the work in general.

2.1.0

LABELS

The dramatic tradition and movement pioneered by Ogunde has variously been described by scholars as "folkloric", "operatic", "popular", "travelling" or "itinerant", "modern" or "contemporary", "modern-traditional" and "professional". This situation is not a healthy one for a proper study of the tradition and movement in general. It is therefore pertinent to discuss the appropriateness of these labels with the aim of suggesting a most appropriate one. The appropriate label, in our own opinion, should distinguish the tradition and its movement from others.

2.1.1 Folk Opera

Though the descriptives "folkloric" and "operatic" are usually combined as "folk opera", they are, at times, also used separately to describe the dramatic tradition. The label "folk drama", said to have been coined by Ulli Beier⁶ (1954) (Rotimi 1971: 36), is generally regarded by most scholars as erroneous. Though Adedeji (1969, 1971) accepts the description of the tradition as an "opera", he considers its description as "folk" a misconception. Eḅun Clark (1979: x) does not agree with the use of either description. Her argument is that the classification of the theatre as operatic is out of date. The movement was operatic at the early stage of its development (1944-1950), when songs and music in general were its main means of verbal articulation. Today, characters (performers) speak out their lines in normal speech, while songs and chants are incorporated in the plays mainly for aesthetic purposes "in moments of 'parabasis', when the moral theme or lesson of the play needs to be driven home" (Rotimi 1971: 42, Ogundeji 1981: 18, 60-66).

Eḅun Clark's argument against the classification

of the dramatic tradition as "folkloric" is mainly based on its content. She argues that the theatre does not concentrate on the "folkloric" content sufficiently to warrant its being labelled as "folkloric" (1979: xi). The originally scripted plays, which also has folkloric contents would definitely have to be grouped within the tradition under examination should we insist on labelling it as folkloric.

From yet another perspective, namely, if we consider its origins, the dramatic tradition under discussion cannot be considered as folkloric. The sacred and eégún aláré dramas which are the proper folk dramas from this perspective (see Graham-White 1974: 2-3)⁷, are more indigenous than the dramatic tradition under study which dates back to just the first half of this century and under strong foreign influences.

We should, however, make it clear that we are not, in any way, disputing the fact that the dramatic tradition under focus, as opined by Owomcyela (1970: 30), is produced by Yorùbá folks about Yorùbá folks for

Yorùbá folks. "Folk" in this general sense to mean "people" is applicable to all of Yorùbá drama.

2.1.2 Popular Theatre

The description of the dramatic tradition under study as "popular theatre" (Graham-White 1971: 3-4, Ogunbiyi 1981: 333, Jeyifo 1984), like its description as "folk", engenders the meaning of a dramatic tradition oriented towards the people. Like it too, the description does not distinguish the various categories of Yorùbá drama properly. The originally scripted plays are, for example, as popular as the non-scripted plays when performed. Similarly, Yorùbá traditional festivals cannot, in any sense, be regarded as unpopular or restricted in its appeal to the populace⁸.

Originally scripted plays are also usually performed by practitioners of the dramatic tradition under study. Efúnṣetán Aniwúra and Kò Ṣe é Gbé written by Akinwumi Iṣṣola (1970, 1983) have been performed by Iṣṣola Ogunṣola (Dr I. Show Pepper) and his dramatic group. Other similar written plays performed by Iṣṣola Ogunṣola are J. F. Odunjo's Agbàlówómérisí: Baálè Jòntolo, Adebayo Faleti's Baṣòrun Gáà and

Olu Owolabi's Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà (See Bọlaji 1985). Oyin Adejọbi has also performed Olu Daramọla's Ilé Tí A Fitọ Mọ (See Ogundeji 1981). The large extent to which the performances of the originally scripted plays are popular is attested by the fact that both Efuṣetan Aniwura and Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà have been filmed⁹.

The fact that people usually travel down from far and near to watch traditional festivals such as Oṣun at Oṣogbo, Ooṣa Ogiyán at Ejigbò, Edì and Ọlọjọ at Ilé Ifẹ and Egúngún all over Yorùbá land, is also a testimony to the popularity of the festival plays. From the perspective of the above arguments, the description of the dramatic tradition under study as "popular" will not distinguish it from other categories of Yorùbá drama.

2.1.3 Travelling or Itinerant Theatre

The taking of the performance to the audience, rather than the audience going to watch it in a particular fixed place (the theatre) is a feature of all popular theatre. As previous scholars (Adedeji 1969, Eḅun Clark 1981, Jeyifo 1984, and Götrick 1984)

have rightly shown in their different studies, members ^{of the} eégún aláré and those of the dramatic movement under study which have both implicitly been shown to be popular above (2.1.2), carry their plays from place to place to their audience. We can therefore not apply the descriptive "travelling" or "itinerant" to only one of these movements as a distinctive label (See Jeyifo 1981 and Ogundeji 1981 for the use of these labels).

2.1.4 Modern or Contemporary Theatre and Modern-Traditional Theatre.

The descriptives "modern" and "contemporary" are usually combined with one of those discussed in section 2.1.3 above, as "Modern travelling theatre" (Ogundeji 1981: 15) or "Contemporary travelling theatre" (Adedeji 1978: 49). These two labels, like the previous ones, also do not distinguish this kind of theatre from the others which are by all means also contemporaneous and in that wise modern. The eégún aláré drama, from the point of view of content, is also modern despite the fact that it originated in the

pre-colonial days. It has grown with time and therefore addresses itself to contemporary issues, using appropriate modern costumes, make-up and props. As Adedeji (1969) has shown, the eégún aláré troupes usually have white man masks, which are usually designed to reflect contemporary conceptions in their repertoire. Masks reflecting the political situation surrounding Chief Obafemi Awolowo, Chief Samuel Ladoke Akintola and Sir Ahmadu Bello were also reported to have been brought out at Gbágurá in Abéokúta by the Ayelabola troupe in one of their 1966 performances. Similar observations have been made of the sacred drama (See Ogunba 1978: 21 and Dagunduro 1982: 18; also see Graham-White 1974: 2-3 and Nkosi 1981: 173, 174 for similar discussions.).

It is the recognition of the problems involved in the application of the two labels just discussed, we suspect, that has led Ogunbiyi (1981) to classify the dramatic tradition under study as "modern-traditional theatre". This label also runs into similar problems as those just discussed. The eégún aláré and even the sacred dramas can also, in the light of our discussion

in the last paragraph, be classified as modern-traditional drama. The label, like the other two, is therefore not appropriate.

2.1.5 Professional Theatre

The qualifier "professional" adopted by Jeyifo (1981) and combined with "itinerant" as "professional itinerant theatre" seems to distinguish the tradition under examination from other existing Yorùbá dramatic traditions. Owomoyela (1970: 25) seems to share this view when he says that Ogunde "gave Nigeria her first professional theatre" (See Èbun Clark 1979: 4). The eégún aláré drama which shares a lot of features with the dramatic tradition under discussion is in this light regarded as non-professional art, if only the fact that most practitioners do not live on the art is taken into consideration. The eégún aláré theatre practitioners usually practise other professions such as farming, hunting and traditional medicine. In this sense, therefore, professionalism may be said to be a distinctive feature of the practitioners of the dramatic tradition under consideration, for there are many of

them that live solely on the theatre.

A more serious look at the situation, however, could make one dismiss the autonomous claim to professionalism by the dramatic movement and tradition pioneered by Ogunde. Just as Kinni-Olusanyin (1981) has argued for the African musicians in general, there are other factors apart from the economic, (employed in making the above observation) that determine professionalism. Such factors include intensive training, high skill and institutionalization. Eégún aláré satisfies these three factors. There is a system of training and there are standards for assessing dexterity in performance. The complex art of the eégún aláre is also an integral part of, in fact a sub-unit, in the eégún cult institution generally known as òjè.

A contrary argument could even be advanced with regard to the economic criterion by which professionalism is denied the eégún aláré practitioners. It can be argued that the art is traditionally the main source of daily living for the Ológbínín lineage families (Olajobu 1975: 5)¹⁰. Members of such families engage in other professions only on a part-time basis. The

traditional medicine profession (and others) mentioned earlier would therefore be regarded as an integral aspect of the eégún aláré theatre¹¹.

In the light of the discussion above therefore, the qualifier "professional" used in labelling the dramatic movement and its tradition under examination is also non-distinctive and therefore inappropriate.

2.1.6 Nigerian Theatre?

The "Ogunde dramatic tradition" and its movement has been implicitly referred to as "Nigerian theatre" by Efun Clark (1979) in the title of her book Hubert Ogunde: The Making of Nigerian Theatre. Apart from the ambiguity caused by the omission of an article before "Nigerian" in the title the work also does not place Ogunde theatre which is the focus of the book in the general context of Nigerian theatre. This is why it seems as if "Nigerian theatre" in the subtitle refers solely to "Hubert Ogunde". As already implied in the foregoing discussion the description, "Nigerian Theatre", is a broad one that extends well beyond the scope of the genre in question. The Nigerian dramatic

scene, though not yet clearly classified¹², certainly goes beyond the dramatic tradition discussed by Eḅun Clark. The dramatic tradition, as already implied, (Section 2.0 above), is essentially a Yorùbá one, because it communicates the Yorùbá world view in general, through Yorùbá linguistic, theatrical and other communicative systems. The primary audience of this tradition is therefore also Yorùbá. We are not through this conclusion denying the fact that the Yorùbá world view is essentially a Nigerian one. What we are saying is that the Yorùbá world is not the Nigerian world. Just as there are many ethnic groups in Nigeria, so are there also many dramatic types. The Nigerian dramatic scene is perhaps as complex as the politico-linguistic scene. It would therefore be an over-generalization to identify one of the many variants as the only variety.

2.1.7 The Ogunde Dramatic Tradition and Movement

Having found all the labels discussed inappropriate for one reason or the other, it would seem necessary to propose another label that would distinguish the dramatic

tradition from another. Since it is generally accepted among both scholars and practitioners of the drama that Hubert Ogunde pioneered the tradition, it would only be proper to label the tradition and movement after him as the Ogunde dramatic (theatrical) tradition and movement. This new label no doubt distinguishes the tradition (and its movement) from others and also points at an important aspect of its historical origin. The flaw in the new label, however, is that it tends to play down the contribution of other major practitioners within the tradition. That is, it does not indicate the important development within the tradition. As our discussion of its rise and development will show, practitioners such as Duro Ladipo and Moses Olaiya have developed certain aspects of the tradition which we regard as sub-traditions under the umbrella of the Ogunde dramatic tradition.

It is generally accepted, both among dramatic practitioners and academics, that the Ogunde dramatic tradition evolved from the eégún aláré tradition. Though the evolutionary theory cannot be denied, it should be noted that the development is not a direct one. Speaking generally about drama, Mayer (1977: 268f) has noted:

drama is continually changing, but it does not have evolutionary history, and even the concept of consecutive history - a history of one form of drama budding, flowering, withering and dying, and eventually giving place to another genre following the same cycle of growth and decay is dubious.

He also warns

we must recognise that the changing, the growth of a new genre or the fading of an old, often proceeds from events outside drama, not necessarily from sentiments within the profession that it is time for something new or time to put an end to obsolete forms.

Similar views and caveats have been expressed also by Nkosi (1981: 176). We should, therefore, not overlook the fact that the rise and subsequent development of the Ogunde dramatic tradition include trends such as general Western literary and dramatic traditions, colonialism, political and cultural nationalism, christianity and independence. (See Echeruo 1962, Leonard 1967, Adedeji 1971, 1973a, Efun Clark 1979 and Jeyifo 1981, 1984). Similar trends in the rise and developments of dramatic traditions are also found to be true of other African nations and the Caribbean (Angmor 1978, Leshoai 1978 and Omoṣoṣo 1978, 1982).

In view of the chequered development of the Ogunde dramatic tradition as discussed specifically in Jeyifo (1984: 39) and as generally observed by other scholars earlier referred to, the eégún aláré dramatic tradition and in fact other sacred dramatic traditions are better regarded as the roots on to which the "new" Ogunde dramatic tradition is grafted.

2.2.1 Roots

It is within the ambience of the African christian efforts to indigenise christianity and get liberated from orthodox control that Ogunde discovered the extent of his dramatic potentials (see Eḃun Clark 1979: 5). The liberative purpose of the indigenous African churches allows Ogunde to draw on "traditional" materials for the treatment of biblical themes in his early "operas".

As he himself said in a public lecture (Jeyifo 1981: 207-222), Ogunde has been part and parcel of the pre-colonial drama (both the eégún aláré and sacred types) since he was very young. He said he was initiated into "more than sixteen" cults at a tender age. He understudied his grandfather who was an Ifá chief priest and also performed with the eégún aláré theatres called Daramọjọ and Eḃkun oko as dancer and drummer between the ages of eight and twelve (Eḃun Clark 1979 xvii). These, we believe, served as the formative period for Ogunde the dramatist.

Experiences similar to these, it should be noted, are also true of other practitioners such as Duro Ladipo,

Akin Ogungbe, Jimo Aliu, Oyin Adejebi, Yemi Elebuubon
 Şupø Koşeemani and a host of others.

Before the advent of Ogunde to the dramatic scene in 1944, it should be noted, there had been an indigenous dramatic movement called "native air opera" and "sacred cantata". The indigenous dramatic trend of the pre-Ogunde period is also known to have been directly preceded by the non-indigenous dramatic activities which were introduced into Lagos by the settler community of liberated slaves from Sierra-Leone, Brazil and Cuba.

Of notable importance in the indigenization movement is the presentation of J. A. Oloyede's King Elejigbo and Princess Abeje of Kontagora, the first Yorùbá full act play in the operatic tradition, by Egbé Ifé, a church dramatic group, in 1903 at the Bethel African Church school room. This first play was followed by another one, The Jealous Queen Oya of Oyó, also written by Oloyede and performed by Egbé Ifé in 1905. Similarly important is the Lagos glee singers' indigenization activity of 1910. This group had, before 1910, been solely involved in presenting European

operatas. They, however, advertised for "copyright of good native plays" (Adedeji 1971: 43) in 1910.

Olympus Moore's (later known as A. K. Ajişafẹ) Asikà Bì Aparò and A. B. Akinyẹle's Awon Iwàrẹfa Méfà were selected out of the five entries received. It was Akinyẹle's script that was, however, finally staged in 1912 under the directorship of D. O. Qbasa. Other names of importance in the pre-Ogunde era include A. B. David, G. I. Onimọlẹ, A. A. Layẹni, H. A. Olufoye, P. A. Dawodu and T. K. E. Phillips.

When in 1944, Ogunde was requested to stage a play, he had all the wealth of his "traditional" experiences and the various entertainments of Western origin, such as the "native air opera" and "sacred cantata", as materials to work on. His early works are, in fact, along the lines of the "native air opera". Ogunde's real achievement lies in his ability to blend successfully the two traditions (i.e. indigenous and non-indigenous dramatic traditions) more than any other person before him. The extent of Ogunde's success was asserted by C. A. Jones (in the Daily Service of 29th June, 1944) who being a musician himself quite

appreciated Ogunde's ingenuity in skilfully blending Yorùbá ancient airs with "modern" music (Èbun Clark 1979: 8). Adedeji (1973a: 394), referring to the same point notes:

As a result of Ogunde's production, the 'Grand Native Air Opera' popularised by A. B. David, T. K. E. Phillips and others came under severe criticism for its "Africanized European tunes and airs". Ogunde's use of the traditional "Ilegbe" or "Aro" and ancient airs of Yoruba land", which were aspects of the innovations he brought into the theatre was highly applauded.

Also comparing P. A. Dawodu's poetic style in his Alli Baba and the Forty Thieves with that of Ogunde in general, (Adedeji 1973b: 64) further notes that "Dawodu's dramatic poetry lacks the traditional ritual expressiveness and elegant formulae identified in the works of Ogunde". These assessments of Ogunde's works are indicators of the fact that Ogunde's input is no doubt a major improvement on, in fact, a turning point in, the dramatic trend of the era, at least at

the musico-poetic level. It must be added at the same time that it was not only at the musico-poetic level that Ogunde realised this achievement, but in the exercise as a whole.

Ogunde, for example, can also be said to have derived the Yoruba obligatory standard of paying respects at public (and even private) performance, the ijúbà, indirectly from his contacts with the eégún aláaré and other sacred examples. He surely derived it directly from the early twentieth century example of the Lagos Glee Singers and Ègbé Ifé which called it opening glee (orin isíde eré). The closing glee (orin iparí eré) which is similar to the opening glee in form and function to some extent, is also similar to the finale (called idán àparelé) in the eégún aláaré tradition. The main play like that of the eégún aláaré, is usually sandwiched between the two glees. But as Jeyifo (1984: 11ff) has noted, there are cases, nowadays, where the opening and closing glees are not used at all. Duro Ladipo's performance is usually cited as an example of the former and that of Moses Olaiya Adejumo as example of the latter. Moses Olaiya Adejumo is

also known to have, some of the time, opened his productions with cinematic screenings of both foreign documentary newsreels and film productions of his comic escapades as "Lamidi" (Jeyifo 1984: 12). Other comedy groups are also fond of using short comic monologues or dialogues that often culminate in the parody of well known religious or social songs. The Jacob, Papalolo and Aderupokọ Jesters International group is known for this variation.

The term "cabaret" dance has recently been used to describe the opening session of performances in which vigorous choreographed dancing is more prominent than other aspects of the musical show. Despite all the variations, one should note that the presentational formulae of the opening show - the play - the closing show are generally common in live performances. Even Duro Ladipo, our artist, who as already indicated above, is usually cited as an example of artists who have departed totally from the presentational pattern, sometimes uses it. This will be fully discussed later in Chapter Three. This pattern is, according to Işola Ogunşola (Jeyifo 1981: 67-68), so popular that

the audience usually demand for it. It is possibly in recognition of the popularity of the presentational pattern that the University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University, Ilé-Ife) troupe improvised an opening glee for their adaptative performance of the English version of Kola Ogunmola's The Palmwine Drinkard in 1984 under the directorship of Kola Ogunmola.

The Ogunde dramatic movement also had to adopt the eégún aláré's tradition of the theatre as a family business because of the lack of trustworthy and faithful performers. In fact, permanent actresses were hard to come by at the on-set of the professional movement. Ogunde therefore fell back on the traditional polygamous culture and married his actresses to make them stay, more or less, permanently in the troupe. Many other troupe leaders in the movement have followed this example.

The informal traditional method (used by oral artists in general) to advertise a performance is also adapted and used side by side with the modern methods of advertising through the mass media and the use of posters. The performers wearing their costumes usually have a ride in the troupe's bus (with some sitting on top of it) round the streets of the town where the

performance is to be staged, singing, drumming and announcing through a microphone, the venue and title of the play to be staged.¹³.

The repertory and itinerant characteristics of the Ogunde dramatic tradition were also borrowed and adapted from the eégún aláaré experience. It was Ogunde who created the nation-wide itinerary and also was the first to explore the West African itinerary which as Jeyifo rightly noted was created by the Ghanaian Concert Party (1984: 55).

It is only if the Yorùbá sacred performances are not accepted as drama, and if the Ogunde dramatic movement and tradition are regarded as directly evolving from the eégún aláaré tradition that much weight can be given to Efun Clark's (1979: 4) claim that Ogunde introduced into Yorùbá drama the use of "actresses as star artistes in their own right". By the sacred rules and regulations of the egúngún cult only men can act in the eégún aláaré theatre, but there are women performers in ritual and festival performances as priestesses (iyálorisà), empathisers (ẹlégùn), carriers (arugbá) and dancers (oníjò) (See Dagunduro 1982: 30-50). There were also few actresses in the

pre-Ogunde theatrical movement in Lagos and other Yorùbá towns.

It can, however, be rightly claimed that Ogunde introduced extensive spoken dialogue into Yorùbá drama. We are in making this statement not necessarily agreeing with Efun Clark (1979: 5, 121), that plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition were dialogised only at the beginning of the concert party era (1950-1954). We are rather of the opinion that dialogue in terms of conversation, was already in use at the beginning of the tradition in 1944, in the operatic plays. The major difference is that dialogue was sung in the operatic plays while it was spoken in the plays of the concert party and post-concert party era. In the pre-colonial traditional drama, miming and background music are the main means of dramatic communication, dialogue between actors in performance is minimal¹⁴; hence our argument that extensive spoken dialogue was introduced into, or more properly, was popularised in, Yorùbá drama at the inception of the Ogunde dramatic tradition. Such an extensive dramatic conversation is, certainly, an influence from the Western dramatic

tradition as it was practised in Lagos then and from other West African adaptational examples such as that of Concert Party in Ghana. Other such occidental influences include the formal organization of performance, the use of the pay box, formal staging systems, the use of Western musical instruments, choreographed dancing and the use of the proscenium stage and other media of performances.

2.2.2.0 Development of Dramatic Forms and Styles

The foregoing discussion has shown that the Ogunde dramatic tradition and movement has its roots in two different dramatic cultures - a foreign one and an indigenous pre-colonial (traditional) one - and that it is a direct offshoot of the indigenist movement of the early twentieth century in Lagos and other parts of Yoruba land. By using Eḡun Clark's (1979) frame, we will now go on to discuss the three developmental stages (operatic, concert party and contemporary phases) in relation to the style and form of plays in the tradition.

2.2.2.1 The Operatic Plays

Though Efun Clark has identified 1950 as the end of the operatic phase in the Ogunde theatre, 1950 cannot be said to really mark the end of the operatic plays in the movement as a whole. As Efun Clark herself notes, Ogunde still featured his "operas" during the Concert Party era and there are other theatre groups which staged operatic plays well after 1950. It is perhaps more appropriate to say, in the case of Ogunde theatre, that Ogunde only stopped composing new operatic plays in *1950. Duro Ladipo is an example of theatre practitioners who composed and staged operatic plays well after 1950. His famous plays Oba Mòrò and Oba Kò So, first produced in 1962 and 1963 respectively, are in the operatic style. Most, if not all, of the early dramatists such as Akin Ogungbe, Oyin Adejòbi, G. T. Onimòlẹ and Kọla Ogunmọla, composed and staged operatic plays. Though no more common nowadays, operatic plays were the first type of plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition, and since the church was the main patron of the drama at its inception, the first operatic plays were thematically biblical. Owing to the impact of cultural

and political nationalism, coupled with the divorce of the theatre from church patronage, "operas" making use of traditional folk and other contemporary social materials started featuring in the performances of plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition as far back as 1945 with the composition and performance of Ogunde's Africa and God (Adedeji 1973a: 395 and Efun Clark 1979: 9). One should, however, not forget that efforts towards the presentation of non-biblical plays pre-date the Ogunde dramatic movement and its tradition. Oloyede's plays cited above (section 2.2.1) are examples of such plays. These efforts, however, belong to the indigenist movement of the early twentieth century and not to the professional movement of the Ogunde dramatic tradition. Duro Ladipo who came into the dramatic scene about 1961 did not start the "folkloric" or mythico-historical plays as believed by Beier (1967: 250). Duro Ladipo only specialised in it and developed it to the level of a sub-genre within the tradition as a whole (See Owomoyela 1970: 28 for a similar view).

2.2.2.2 The Transitional Style of the Concert Party Era

The concert party era in the Ogunde theatre served a revolutionary and transitional purpose in the life of the movement and its tradition as a whole. The concert drama resulted from Ogunde's reaction to his 1948 experience in Ghana, (then Gold Coast), where his biblical opera King Solomon was rejected¹⁵. Ogunde therefore wrote a concert drama, Swing the Jazz, to suit the Ghanaian taste. An example of artists who followed the concert party example is Şupq Koşeemani who, according to Adegboła (1985: 9), formed a "concert party group" in 1958. Moses Qłaiya Adejumo's inclusion of comical drama sketches in his Federal Rhythm Dandies musical shows of the sixties can also be seen as an influence of the concert party style (See Adetunji 1987: 16-17). The impact of the concert party era on the dramatic tradition as a whole, however, lies in the introduction of normal speech, as opposed to singing, into dramatic dialogues. This allows for greater audience participation than in the operatic plays (Şbun Clark 1979: 151). According to Owomoyela 1970: 131) the extemporized dialogues allows performers

to address the audience directly, making jokes at them and sometimes confiding in them. The direct communicative barrier between the performers and audience, typical of proscenium performances, is therefore broken and the spectators also usually reciprocate. Such mutual interactions would perforce be limited in the performance of operatic plays where almost all conversation is sung.

The use of the English language, especially pidgin English, is another mark of this era. Pidgin English is found more useful when the theatre group tours the non-Yoruba speaking areas of the country. The use of foreign musical instruments such as saxophone and trumpets became popular during this era. It can be said that it was during the concert party era that the idea of a theatre troupe keeping a band stand was initiated. The Kola Ogunmola and Moses Olaiya troupes were known to have kept such a band stand in the past.

It was also from this era that the slapstick comedy, noted by Beier (1981: 193-195) and Ekom (1971: 42) as a feature of the Ogunde dramatic tradition, started in earnest. Ogunde, according to Efun Clark (1979: 128), moved "from being a straight actor to an actor/comedian" during the concert party period. It

is thus clear that the popular belief that the aláwàdà (comedian) genre was started by Moses Qlaiya is a misconception (Lakoju 1983). In fact, Ogunde, in a public lecture at Ifè, has highlighted that the aláwàdà genre took off from him (Jeyifo 1981: 219-221). He says that one Kaka, Ajayi Taylor, Jane Izevidua and Fólakẹ [now Mrs Adejumọ (Káríílẹ́)] broke away from his troupe to start a new group. They asked for financial support from Moses Qlaiya Adejumọ, who was then a musician and magician. It was later on that Moses Qlaiya himself joined them. Ogunde claimed that he had been performing in Ghana, for his concert party audience, what this group gave as their first television performance. The use of a big bow tie, a big wrist watch, a rope as belt, which was prominent in the early aláwàdà performances of Moses Qlaiya is said to have been borrowed from the Ogunde concert party plays. In the light of these revelations, therefore, the aláwàdà genre can be seen as an offshoot of the Ogunde theatre and therefore part and parcel of the Ogunde dramatic tradition. Just as the mythico-historical (or "folkloric") plays in which Duro Ladipọ specialised and which he further developed, the aláwàdà genre has been further

developed into its contemporary stage primarily by Moses Olaiya Adejumo (Baba Sala) and then by Ola Omotan (Ajimajasan), Ojo Ladipo (Baba Mèró) and the Jesters International trio.

2.2.2.3 The Contemporary Situation

The contemporary phase of the Ogunde dramatic tradition started in 1965 (Efun Clark: 1979: 131). It is a further development on the innovations of the concert party style. The variety and jazz musical elements were removed from the performances and Yorùbá titles were substituted for the plays formerly carrying English titles. It is in fact, during the contemporary era that the aláwàdà sub-tradition became fully developed. The latest trend in the aláwàdà tradition is that spearheaded by the Jesters International trio. The trio are known for their presentation of comical sketches as interludes during musical performances. This development is, however, in a certain respect reminiscent of the Ogunde concert party performances. The main difference is that whereas the musical background for Ogunde's plays was produced by the Ogunde troupe itself, another musical band produces

the musical background to the trio's dramatic sketches. It was, however, found out during an interview we had with one of the trio in 1985, that the Jesters International Organization was also planning to have a musical band. This was becoming necessary because of the unhealthy rivalry that usually arose from collaborative performances between the trio's group and other musical band stands.

The dramatization of stories based on Yorùbá oral poetry such as ijálá, ese Ifá and òwe by Alabi Ogundepo, Yemi Eḷebunḅon and Şupḡ Koşeemani respectively though restricted to the television, can also be regarded as a new trend in the development of plays based on stories from oral literature in the tradition. The Ogunde dramatic movement has also plunged into film-making and as of now it can boast of not less than twenty-two Yorùbá films¹⁶. The first of such films Ajàní Ogún, starring Adeyemi Afḡlayan and Duro Ladipḡ, was produced in 1976. The huge success recorded within such a short period would never have been possible but for the corporate strength and the mutual sense of sharing and growing which issued from the organization

in 1971 (See 2.4.2 below for more on films as a medium of performance).

2.3.0

CREATION OF PLAYS

Plots do not occur by accident, they are usually adapted from either one source or another. Such stories include folk stories, such as myths, legends and folktales; biblical stories, other written literatures and history, either past or present. Apart from the plot, materials are usually taken from other sources to transform the adapted story-line into a full play. Such materials include character traits, music, costume, scenery, language, masks and other images as hand and stage properties. The creation of a play out of these various sources is usually a collaborative effort in the Ogunde dramatic tradition. In the following two sub-sections collective creation and its implication for the study of plays in the tradition are discussed.

2.3.1 Collective Creation

As other scholars have noted and the dramatists themselves revealed in various interviews¹⁷ the creation

of plays is largely collectively derived. Most of the time it is the group leader that composes the scenario, but other experienced members of the troupe can sometimes write it. Collective creation, in most cases, starts from the composition of the plot. As revealed by Oyin Adejobi in an interview (I held with him on the 19th July and 22nd August 1981), the capabilities of the members of the troupe are taken into consideration while structuring out the scenario. In most cases apart from the songs which are usually memorized, the dialogues in the play are improvised by each performer. The improvisation is, however, highly influenced by the troupe leader who is also the director and lead dramaturge.

As Oyin Adejobi, Lere Paimo and Işqola Ogunşola have revealed in different interviews held with them, all members of the group usually come together many times to deliberate on the scenario and the general structure of the play. It is at the first of such meetings that parts are allotted to performers. Lere Paimo and Işqola Ogunşola in the interviews held with them, and Moses Olaiya Adejumo during a symposium in honour of the late Duro Ladipo,¹⁸ all revealed that

the mythico-historical plays are usually based on deep research. According to Lere Paimo, members are asked to investigate different aspects of Yorùbá culture related to the play at hand during their first deliberation. They then assemble again to decide which of the findings should go into the play. The lead dramaturge is, however, always the one that makes the final decision. It should, nevertheless, be noted that the extent of collective creation and improvisation varies from one group to the other and even from play to play. Our artist, Duro Ladipo is, however, known to have exploited the system considerably in his works. This is attested^{to} by Biḡdun Duro-Ladipo in an interview we had with her, which corroborates Qlajubu's (1978) analysis of the various sources of, and the contribution of individual performers to, Qba Ko So.

2.3.2 Problem of Collective Creation: The Critic's Perspective.

The issue of collective creation poses a technical problem for the literary study of plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition. The problem revolves around the issue of authorship; whether the lead

dramaturge should be called the author of the plays, or not. In cases where the play is scripted by the leader, he can properly be regarded as the author. But where broad outlines are used, the leader who produces the scenario, directs and co-ordinates the performance, can be referred to simply as the "motivator". Whatever the case may be, the plays have to be identified primarily with the lead dramaturge because he is directly and indirectly responsible for the activities of the troupe. We should, despite this, bear in mind the contributions of other members of the troupe and always endeavour to specify them.

2.4.0 PLACES AND MEDIA OF PERFORMANCE

At the early period of its development, the Ogunde dramatic movement performed only on the live stage, but the presence of the tradition can at present be felt in the following five media: radio, television, photo-play magazine, phono-disc and the cinema (See Ogundeji 1981: 1-12). In the following discussion, the live stage is first separately discussed before the remaining five media are collectively discussed. As

the discussion will show the five media share a lot of features and they are therefore opposed to the live stage.

2.4.1 The Live Stage

Plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition are performed on any kind of stage ranging from the standard proscenium stage of places such as the University theatres and the National Theatre at Iganmu, Lagos, to sub-standard stages of school halls, town halls and hotel grounds. Open spaces in front of the oba's palace and other private compounds can also be adapted as stage (See Efun Clark 1979: 149-153 for a detailed list of such places of performance). As can be gathered from our earlier discussion in section 2.2.1 above, christian mission school-rooms and church grounds served as the first places of performance for the theatre troupes in the movement, when the church was its main patron. This fact applies not only to Ogunde, but also to Ogunmola, Duro Ladipo and Oyin Adejebi. As the theatre moved away from church patronage, town halls and hotel grounds were used.

2.4.2 Other Media of Performance

Performances in the other five media, listed above (2.4.0), definitely coincide with the gradual technological awareness of the nation in general. The first radio performance was in July 1945 on Lagos Radio-Rediffusion Service (Efun Clark 1979: 371-372). Following Şegun Oluşqla's account (1981: 371-372) the first television performance was between 1959 and 1960 at the inception of the first African television station in Ibadan. The first Yorùbá photo-play magazine also started with Ogunde's Yorùbá Ronú in 1967 (See Ogundeji: 1981: 9). Though songs from the opening and closing glees of Ogunde's plays have been featuring on phonograph discs before 1964, it was perhaps not until 1964 that full-length plays started appearing on phonograph discs with Duro Ladipo's Edá and Qba Kò So. There have also been few documentary films in which practitioners of the Ogunde dramatic movements feature prominently. Such films include Culture in Transition, Esso World Theatre Production (1964), Creative Man, American Educational Television, (1966) in which Duro Ladipo features and My Brother's Children (1971) in which Kqla Ogunmqqla features (See U.I. Official Bulletin

No. 452, 13th March, 1978 and Beier 1981: 330).

Extensive involvement in the making of feature films (purely entertainment oriented films) only started in 1976 with the production of Ajàní Oḡún starring Duro Ladipo and Adeyemi Afọlayan. The number of films in the repertoire of the Ogunde dramatic tradition is as already said (in 2.2.2.3 above) at present not less than twenty-two. Taking the short period into consideration, this achievement in film-making is no doubt a huge one.

2.4.3 Comparison of the Performances on the Live Stage and the Other Five Media

The physical co-presence of both the audience and performers (their proxemic relationship) in the place of performance paves the way for a bi-directional interaction between the two groups in the live performance. As Ogundeji (1981: 1-8) has shown, the mutual reciprocal relationship between the performers and audience during live performance paved the way for the large extent of improvisation at almost every level of performance. This makes the live performance more

interesting than performances on the other media, where the performer/audience relationship is uni-directional (See 2.2.2.2 above) Efun Clark has testified to this when she says that it is only during live performance "that the audience and actors ... meet to finalise the content and form of the piece in repertory" (1980: 76).

The bi-directionality and improvisational nature of stage performances are jointly responsible for the exaggerative action of the performers. Such exaggerative actions on the television looks abnormal and "irritating". According to Oreh, (1976: 5) "It makes T.V. producers and camera men misuse close-ups and rapid montage ... in preference to many wide-angle shots". Efun Clark rightly concludes after making similar statements that we should avoid judging the plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition by their television performances because on television the practitioners' art is often mutilated. The mutilation is usually caused by the time limit imposed by the electronic media executives, whose programmes have to begin and end on strict schedule, the mono-directionality

and the involvement of a third party (an outsider, the media producer or editor) in the process of presentation¹⁹.

Ogundeji (1981: 8-12) has also attempted to show how, through the manipulation of "bold prints" and "thought balloons" the editor of the photo-play magazine can intrude on the structure of the play. As gathered from Mr. Olowomojuṣe (Bàbá Gèébú), one-time editor of the foremost photo-play magazine, Atóka and sometimes also that of Ibùkún Aláwàdà, it is also possible for the editor to alter or even reconstruct the dramatic dialogue to suit his own purpose²⁰.

Though these media of performances allow for quick change of scenery and expand the audience of the dramatic tradition greatly, there is no doubt that they also place great limitations on the performance as a play. In two different interviews with Iṣṣla Ogunṣṣla, he submitted that the live performance based on scenario is more interesting (at least from the performer's angle) than other types of performance.

It therefore seems logical, from the fore-going discussion, to suggest, for a fair study of plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition, that at least more than one text of such a play should be considered

and that one of such texts should also, at least, be a live performance. As many of the texts as possible on other media of performances, should also be considered. These suggestions present the ideal, but experience has shown that the ideal is hard to come by; in the present study therefore the suggestions are adapted according to the nature of available data.

2.5.0 DURO LADIPQ: THE MAN AND HIS REPERTORY

Despite the fact that references are made here and there to Duro Ladipq and aspects of his repertory in the above sections and subsections of this chapter, we still consider it necessary to dwell on Duro Ladipq himself and his repertory. This, we think, will help in giving a clear picture of the man and his repertory within the general context of the Ogunde dramatic tradition and movement.

2.5.1 The Man Duro Ladipq (1931-1978)

Though certain sources, such as Baratz (1964: 16-17), Owomoyela (1970: 28), Odusanya (1981: 1) and Onibqokuta (1983: 6) record 18th December, 1932 as

Duro Ladipo's date of birth, other sources such as Jaheinz-Jahn et al. (1972: 184), Herdeck (1974: 193), Welch (1972: 184), Ogunyemi (1981: 334) and the University of Ibadan (Official Bulletin No. 452 of March 1978) put it at 18th December, 1931. Since the 1931 date is, however, corroborated by Duro Ladipo (1970: xi) himself, it is just desirable to accept it as the authentic date. Ògbómòşó (Odusanya 1981 probably after Lere Paimo), Ìlobùú, (Owomoyela 1972 and Baratz 1964) and Oşogbo (Jaheinz-Jahn et al. 1972, Welch 1972, Ogunbiyi 1981 and Onibonokuta 1983) are the three towns usually cited as Duro Ladipo's place of birth. Though Duro Ladipo (1970) is silent about his place of birth, we wish to accept Oşogbo as the correct information on the issue, not only because it is supported by the majority of the sources cited, but also because it is the place of birth cited in the University of Ibadan official bulletin referred to above. Information in this bulletin is taken as official for it must have been submitted by Duro Ladipo himself who was, by the time of his death, an artist-in-residence at the Institute of African Studies

of the University.

Whatever the case may be, it is certain that Duro Ladipò was a native of Òşogbo. It was in Òşogbo that his grandfather settled after the 1878 Jalumi war (see Johnson 1921: 447ff for information on this war). His grandfather who originally came from Òfà Èrìn, was a veteran professional dùndún drummer. This man was probably captured and finally released during the said war, to a war leader called Qđerinlò, because of the age-long immunity usually enjoyed by oral artists (Qlajubu: 1978: 333). According to Duro Ladipò (1970: ix) it was Qđerinlò that brought his grandfather to Òşogbo. Members of Duro Ladipò's family are worshippers of Şàngó and Qya. But Duro Ladipò's father, Oni Ladipò, did not only get converted to Christianity, he became a catechist in the Anglican Mission under the late Reverend Mackay. He served in this capacity for many years at Òşogbo, Ìlobùú, Qđan Ayégbajú, Ìlá Qràngún and other towns in the Qşun division of the then Western Region.

Mrs. Tòwòbòla Ajiké Ladipò, Duro Ladipò's mother, was a native of Ìjèdá Ijèşà. She died in 1986, many

years after her husband who had died in 1963. Though she had a fertile womb, the first nine children she had died one after the other in the manner of the àbíkú, (born-to-die) children. Since belief in such children is anti-christian, Tọwọbọla Ajikẹ had to take Duro Ladipọ secretly to an Ifa priest who through ritual means made him stay alive. Duro Ladipọ himself is therefore, according to Yorùbá belief, the embodiment of the àbíkú who had died nine times and was re-born ten times, hence the descriptive name of appeal, Durodọla (Stay-alive-and-partake-in-the-family's-honour).

One cannot but start noting the mysterious aspects of Duro Ladipọ from this point onwards. The babaláwo who used a padlock in performing the ritual to make Duro-Ladipọ stay alive is nicknamed bàbá àgádágodo, (father of the padlock). One of Duro Ladipọ's sons, Tọla Duro-Ladipọ, informed us that no one is allowed to mention Bábá àgádágodo's name at home and that Duro Ladipọ generally disliked the man. This story is corroborated by Adebayọ Faleti, in an interview we had with him; he said Duro Ladipọ and Bábá àgádágodo "never saw eye to eye". Wale Ogunyẹmi in another interview, informed us that Duro Ladipọ heaved a sigh of relief

at Baba agadagodo's death and that Duro Ladipo died about a year after (Also see Onibokuta 1983: 6). It should therefore be noted that the effort to make Duro Ladipo live long is, within the context of Yoruba belief and as proved by his life, only partially successful, since he died on 10th March, 1978, before his mother. He is therefore, still to be regarded as an àbíkú àgbà (old àbíkú).

Duro Ladipo schooled in Otan Ayégbajú, and Ilá Oràngún and had his Government Middle Two Certificate in 1942. He was a member of the school choir and he composed his first play, Naman the Leper while still at school (Odusanya 1981: 3). As a son of a clergy man, it was made compulsory for him to memorise several portions of the Bible and other religious literature by his parents. Despite this christian orientation, the young Duro could not resist his natural interest in the indigenous set-up outside the vicarage. He therefore usually escaped from the mission house to participate in traditional sacred festivals such as Egúngún and Awòrò ọsẹ at Ilá Oràngún and Orò Ọlúa, Ọbàtálá, Şàngó and Ọtìn at Otan Ayégbajú. A story is

narrated to us by Biq̄dun Duro-Ladip̄q̄ of how young Duro once sneaked out of the vicarage with his mother's piece of head-wear, (gèlè), which was used as a part of an egúngún costume. Duro Ladip̄q̄'s mother was able to identify her gèlè on a masquerade who was later discovered to be Duro Ladip̄q̄. Duro was severely punished for it.

One can, in fact conclude that Duro Ladip̄q̄ got acquainted with both the "traditional" and "modern" dramatic forms at the early stages of his life. Though we are not sure of how close Duro Ladip̄q̄ was to his grandfather, one tends to postulate that his love for the traditional dramatic forms despite the serious opposition which he had by virtue of his father's position is due to some influence from his grandfather and the environment in which he grew up (See section 2.2.1 above).

Duro Ladip̄q̄ on completing his primary education taught for eighteen years in different elementary schools in both the old Western and Northern Regions of Nigeria (1943-1961). According to the University of Ibadan Official Bulletin just referred to, Duro Ladip̄q̄ attended in-service teacher training courses and had his Grades Three and Two Teacher's

Certificates in 1955 and 1958 respectively. He could therefore not be referred to as an untrained or pupil teacher throughout his teaching career as many other sources have done.

Duro Ladipo worked with two head teachers, A. J. Odunsi and Alex Peters, whose personalities further helped in kindling his dramatic potentials. Drama was a major extra-curricular activity in Odunsi's school and Duro Ladipo took a leading role as an actor in the performances staged then (Welch 1972). Odunsi's Sùúrù Baba Ìwà is said to have been one of the plays in which Duro Ladipo participated (Odusanya 1981: 4).

Alex Peters, though a head-teacher, was running a theatre troupe on a part-time basis. Duro Ladipo met him at Oşogbo in 1947 during one of his performances. He volunteered to follow Alex Peters to his Iléşà base where employment in a primary school, probably Holy Trinity School, Qmofẹ (Ogunbiyi 1981: 338), was secured for him and he spent his spare time with Alex Peters' theatre group. When in 1949 Alex Peters was transferred to Kaduna in the North, Duro Ladipo followed him there. They were, however, unable to stage any play until the end of 1950 when a nativity play was staged. Alex Peters

left Kaduna in 1951 but Duro Ladipo stayed behind, this time. Duro Ladipo was unable to stage a play until 1955 when he put up an adaptation of Shakespeare's As You Like It.

He had to come back to Òşogbo in 1956 when all his belongings were stolen, and he started teaching again. He was, during this time, also running a beer parlour which he called Popular Bar in an apartment in his father's house. He was also at the same time working as pay box collector and hand bill distributor at Ajax Cinema. It was on account of his involvements in dramatic and other entertaining activities that his teaching service was terminated. He was, according to him, wrongly accused of neglecting his teaching duties (See Washington Post Style of Thursday, February 20, 1975).

About this time, he met Ulli Beier, who was then a University of Ibadan Extra-Mural tutor based at Òşogbo. Beier usually came to the Popular Bar to relax after a hard day's work. All along Duro Ladipo had been involved in church music as a choir-master and chorister. He invited Beier to an Easter Cantata which he composed and staged at All Saint's Church, Òşogbo in 1960. But

his effort for introducing traditional drums into the cantata was detested by the church authority and the performance of the beautiful composition was according to Beier "ruined" because the church authority insisted on having conventional church hymns incorporated into the performance (See Jeyifo 1981: 177). Duro Ladipo and, especially, his father, were embarrassed by the reaction of the church authority. According to Beier (in Jeyifo 1981: 178), Duro Ladipo was stopped from reading the lesson in the church for this action of his.

With the advice and general help of Ulli Beier, Duro Ladipo, using students from the Teachers' Training College at Oṣogbo, staged his Christmas cantata in the same year outside the church. Ulli Beier also arranged the performance of the cantata at the newly opened Mbari Club in Ibadan and, on the television service of the then WNTV/WNBS (See section 2.4.1 and 2.4.2 above). Inspired by the Mbarí at Ibàdàn, Duro Ladipo decided to open a similar centre at Oṣogbo. With the help of Beier who managed to secure a grant of two hundred pounds for him, and of Susan Wenger, the Popular Bar and other parts of the building that hosted

it were turned into the famous M̀b́arí M̀b́áyò Club which served as a converging point for artistic-minded people for quite some time. There was an art gallery as well as a theatre space where many of Duro Ladipò's plays were first staged for the Òşogbo audience. Oba Adenle II, the then Ataoja of Òşogbo opened the centre in the morning of 17th May, 1962 while the play Oba M̀ó_rò, was staged in the evening. Duro Ladipò's effort in the creation of the first theatre building owned by a theatre practitioner where plays could be performed for the local audience, should be commended. No other practitioner has, to our knowledge, attempted such an adventure since Duro Ladipò.

The M̀b́arí M̀b́áyò cultural centre served not only as a training ground for renowned theatre practitioners but also for famous fine artists of our time such as Jimò Buraimò, Twin Seven Seven, Bisi Fabunmi, Muraina Oyelami and Aşiru Qlatunde. Renowned theatre artists that have used M̀b́arí M̀b́áyò as a practising if not training ground, include Ademola Onibonokuta, Karimu Adepoju, Lasisi Gbebajaja, Ojèniyi Amò, Lere Paimò, Abidoye Ojo and Jacob Afqlabi. Theatrical competitions

were arranged for schools and youth associations at the M̀bárí M̀báyò centre. In fact, it was during such competitions and performances that Duro Ladipò first spotted the potentials of some of his regular performers such as Ademọla Onibọnokuta, Lasisi Gbebọlaja and Adebisi Adeleke.

According to Adebayọ Faleti who was then working as a film commentator for the Western Region Ministry of Information in Ọşogbo, and who knew Duro Ladipò in 1957, Duro Ladipò did not have a standing theatre group initially. He would just gather performers when he wanted to stage a play and pay them after the performance. But Duro Ladipò started having constant financial problems when he later began to keep a professional theatre company. He had to pay members of his company monthly. This problem usually led to serious organizational disorder. Duro Ladipò was generally more interested in promoting the Yorùbá and Nigerian culture than in material gain. Many of his command performances and overseas tours yielded very little in terms of material gain but much in terms of making a name for him. He was even once duped by a

promoter of his on one of his overseas tours to South America. Apart from such problems, a considerable part of the money made is usually pumped into making in-depth researches into cultural matters and buying costumes and other theatre materials. This probably explains why Duro Ladipo could not satisfy members of his company who were always asking for better conditions of service. His inability to meet their frequent demands sometimes led to serious breakdowns in the organization of the troupe. The confessions of Muraina Oyelami (1982) and Ademola Onibonokuta (1984) are good testimonies. A lot of tricks is usually played on Duro Ladipo by his boys to get extra money from him and at times the boys deserted him during important performances. On such occasions, Duro Ladipo usually managed to put up the show. But there was the last occasion when Qba Ko So was to be staged at Ọyó and Duro Ladipo was completely deserted at the last minute. The disappointed audience went violent and many of the company's property got destroyed. It took Duro Ladipo some time to re-organize after the incident in 1972.

Duro Ladipo, according to Adebayo Faleti (in the

interview we had with him), reverted to his original organizational method of not keeping a standing theatre group. Many of his performers who wished to continue with him were invited only when there was a performance. Duro Ladipo later decided to surrender a television series Bode Wasimi which he created in 1975 for certain members of his group who constituted themselves into another theatre group. But most if not all the members of this new group usually joined Duro Ladipo whenever it was necessary. Other big theatre groups (e.g. Moses Qlaiya) now employ this device to check fissiparous tendencies in their companies. We may on the basis of the on-going discussion agree with Adebayo Faleti that Duro Ladipo was a shrewd theatre business man.

What seems to confirm this statement is the rivalry between him and two other Osoybo-based theatre practitioners, Cyin Adejebi and Kola Ogunmola. The relationship always fluctuated between comradeship and rivalry. Cyin Adejebi recalled (on 5th June, 1986), that the three of them usually consulted each other at various stages of play production. Dayo Adekunle

claimed that the biblical play, Joseph the Dreamer, was jointly composed and performed by the three artists. Though no one has corroborated this claim, there is a photograph of the Duro Ladipo's group performing in Cyin Adejọbi's Ekùró Qlọjà (Jeyifo 1984: 58).

There are, however, events that point to serious rivalry among the three groups. There was the serious controversy about the play Mọrẹmi between Duro Ladipo and Cyin Adejọbi. Duro Ladipo was accused of plagiarism and there was much publicity in the mass media about the row which culminated in a press conference by the representative of the Qọni of Ifẹ to validate Cyin Adejọbi's version as the more authentic one. There was also the rivalry between Ogunmọla and Duro Ladipo over who was to represent Nigeria at the Commonwealth Festival in 1965, when Duro Ladipo was chosen. But Ogunmọla, who also participated in the competition, thought that the competition was manoeuvred in favour of Duro Ladipo. The rivalry according to Oyelami (1982: 8) "degenerated into animosity between the two good friends". In the two cases cited above, Duro Ladipo can be said to have had an edge over his rivals because of his shrewd

business acumen.

Duro Ladipo was nevertheless generally regarded as a hard working, friendly, tolerant and honest person. He was also a loving husband and a good father. He had four wives - Mabel, Abiodun, Idowu and Funke - and many children (at least fifteen). He was fully dedicated to the theatre in particular and Yorùbá culture in general. He was, in recognition of these contributions, appointed as an Artist in residence by the Institute of African Studies, University of Ibadan, in January 1978. But he fell ill and was admitted to the University College Hospital, Ibadan in February of the same year. Out of his great commitment to the Yorùbá theatre and culture, and out of a high sense of responsibility, Duro Ladipo came out of his sick bed on 1st March, 1978 to oversee the performance, at the Institute's court-yard, of an Ijálá Ogún musical show, which he had earlier organized. That marked his last public appearance.

Duro Ladipo had a special instinct for spotting dramatic potentials and would do all that was possible to get both human and non-human materials for the production of his plays. This probably explains why

and how he joined many cults and societies and attended many ritual festivals. He would always keep a tape recorder underneath his big garment when necessary during ritual ceremonies to record useful materials for his plays. In fact, he, more than any of his contemporaries, worked with non-literate oral artists whom he usually groomed for his theatre group. Duro Ladipo can in this capacity, be seen as helping in the modernization of the traditional art institution.

Duro Ladipo is usually ranked as a good composer, theatre manager, director and tutor but not as a good actor, at least in comparison with his colleague Kola Ogunmola. Adebayo Faleti (in the discussion we had with him) is of the opinion that the roles which Duro Ladipo usually chose for himself did not allow for much movement. His general impact on the dramatic scene of Nigeria is, nevertheless enormous. He died on 11th March, 1978 and no dramatist has since then been able to so frequently take Nigerian drama to the outside world as he used to. He enjoyed playing the role of Sàngó which he chose for himself in three different plays, Qba Kò So, Qbátálá and Qsun. The death of Duro Ladipo was coincidentally marked by a heavy downpour,

thunder and lightning as if the god of thunder was welcoming him home.

2.5.2.0 Duro Ladipo's Repertory

The focus of this section is on the plays and performers. Other aspects of the repertory such as costume, hand and stage properties are mentioned only where necessary. It is from this collection of human and non-human resources that materials are selected for performances.

2.5.2.1 Plays

Plays in the repertory have already been classified into the following four categories: Biblical, Social, those adapted from other literary sources and mythico-historical plays (See section 0.2 above). The thing to note about Duro Ladipo's plays is that they contain a lot of Yorùbá cultural materials. Even his later biblical plays, (e.g. Kọ Bí Idi, Jáléyemí, Afqláyan and Olúorogbo as can be noted from their titles), are properly adapted to the Yoruba context. Kọ Bí Idi is an adaptation of the David and Goliath's story while Jáléyemí is that of Samson and Delilah, Afqláyan

deals with Joseph the dreamer while Olúorogbo depicts the nativity story. Unlike other biblical plays in the repertory of the Ogunde dramatic tradition in general, it is difficult to recognise the biblical content of the plays from their titles. It is in the adaptative sense that one can properly understand Duro Ladipo's claim that all but one, (Èdá) of his plays are based "on stories taken from Ifá" (Owomoyela 1970: 125). Since the Ifá literary corpus treats most, if not all, human problems, it was easy for Duro Ladipo to relate many of his plots, even those derived from foreign sources; such as the Bible and Shakespeare, to Ifá literature. This is how the nativity story could easily have been adapted, or domesticated as Olúorogbo. Olúorogbo is believed to be the Yorùbá surrogate of Jesus, while Mọrèmi, Olúorogbo's mother, is also usually taken as the Yorùbá equivalent of Mary. Despite Duro Ladipo's reservation noted above, Èdá in the light of the above argument cannot be separated from the others.

We should, however, not forget that Duro Ladipo in the preliminary stages of his career performed biblical plays (in addition to non-biblical ones) which

were not as properly adapted to the Yoruba context as the later plays. The 1961 Easter and Christmas cantatas are examples of such biblical plays. The characterization and actions in the christmas cantata, which was re-performed for us in solo by Dayo Adekunle,²¹ literarily follows the biblical accounts of the synoptic gospels. Most of the music is, however, composed in the indigenous church melody. On the other hand, the characters, actions and music of Olúorogbo, are in most parts mainly composed of traditional materials.

The social plays are based on day-to-day social and domestic issues. Many of the plays in this category are tele-plays. They include Gbádégesin, Alágbára Má Mèrò, Má Gbara Lé Won, Igbéraga Ní í Síwájú Iparun, Súúrù Baba Ìwà, Ológbón Ayé and Òmúlèmófo (see Welch 1972: 189 and Ogunyemi 1981: 343). The Bodè Wásimi and Òyìnbó Ajélè television series, inaugurated in 1975 and 1986 respectively can also be included in this category. The two series are both dramatizations of the Yoruba colonial experience. The idea of Òyìnbó Ajélè does not only emanate from Bodè Wásimi but also from Obá Wàjà in which the District Officer, is, as in Òyìnbó Ajélè, a major character. Despite the historical

reference of the two series, they are primarily considered as social plays because emphasis is not on important beliefs and/or particular incidents, and historical or archetypal figures. The general day-to-day happenings of the colonial period form the main focus.

Examples of plays adapted from other literary sources include Èdá, an adaptation of Hugo Von Hofmanthal's medieval play Everyman, Òtún Akogun and Omónidẹ both adapted from Shakespeare's Macbeth and As You Like it respectively. The adaptations are, like the biblical ones, best described as domestications of the originals. The adaptation in the case of Èdá is, for example, not only structural but also thematic. Whereas Hofmanthal presented the Catholic Christian doctrines of repentance and forgiveness, Duro Ladipo emphasises the Yoruba concept of ẹsan (retribution) and àsẹ̀yìnwáyé (reincarnation). Also belonging to this class is the television serial adaptation of D. O. Fagunwa's novel Ògbójú Ode Nínú Igbó Irúnmolẹ̀.

Duro Ladipo is well known all over the world rather for his mythico-historical plays than for the other categories of plays. Though Ulli Beier suggested

the mythico-historical form to him, it is to Duro Ladipo and other members of his group that the credit for successful composition and performance should be given (See Ogunyemi 1981: 338 and 470). Despite the pessimism of Nwoko (1981), about Duro Ladipo's plays and theatre group in general, it is interesting to see that Duro Ladipo's group and their plays were well received at home and abroad. It is even more interesting to note that Duro Ladipo's theatre group has survived him and many of the plays in his repertory have been staged since his demise. The many honours which Duro Ladipo received both at home and abroad are evidence of his success. It is also not true, at least in 1988, that "the Germans are today the best sponsors of Duro Ladipo's theatre" (Nwoko 1981). The theatre has toured most parts of the world with their plays and Qba Ko So has once again been performed in America (1987) this time with an American cast and a few members of the Duro Ladipo troupe.

Most of the mythico-historical plays, in fact, all those treated in this work, tend towards the tragic. This has also made Duro Ladipo the most notable tragic playwright in the Ogunde dramatic

movement. The tragic essence of his plays is traceable to the source stories in which the mythico-historical figures are themselves tragic figures. Beier in an interview with Biq̄dun Jeyifo has noted that the òrìṣàs who constitute the figures in these plays are essentially tragic figures (Jeyifo 1981: 199).

Apart from plays there are other types of dramatic works in the repertory. Prominent among them are "The Songs of Duro Ladip̄q̄" which Adebaȳq̄ Falet̄i recollected producing for the Western Nigeria Broadcasting Service in the Sixties. There was also the "Èdà Oníléqlá" narrative series on the Nigerian Broadcasting Service Radio also in the Sixties. Abidoye Ojo played the role of Àyìndé whose chanting punctuates the narratives of the journeys of Èdà (Irinajo Èdà), acted by Lere Pain̄q̄. This form of narratives is today continued in the "Èlà l̄q̄r̄q̄" programme. Şup̄q̄ Koşeemani on the radio service of the Q̄ȳq̄ State Broadcasting Service; Yorùbá proverbs are explicated in the series.

2.5.2.2 Performers

Performers in the Duro Ladip̄q̄ repertory can be grouped into two according to their general artistic

orientation. There are the "traditional" oral artists groomed by Duro Ladipo for the "modern" stage. Qjeniyi Anjo (Àkàràògùn), Abidoje Ojo (Gbónka), Lasisi Gbèbòlaja, Adebisi Faşanu, Yemi Èlèbuubòna and Adeşina Adetoyi belong to this class. The first three are originally masqued performers either of the eégún aláré or eégún èlèwè type. They are therefore highly skilled in bàtá dancing and the èşà egúngún chanting mode. Adebisi Faşanu and Yemi Èlèbuubòn²² hail from families of Ifá worshippers. They are versed in the recitation of Ifa divination poetry and Iyèrè Ifá chanting mode in particular and Yorùbá culture in general. Yemi Èlèbuubòn, for example, claims to be Duro Ladipo's major cultural adviser for quite some time. Adeşina Adetoyi is a traditional dùndún drummer and he is the chief instrumentalist of the group. They were usually given roles in which they would be able to display their artistic skills.

The other category of performers are those who have some formal education and are generally talented in the neo-traditional performing arts. Though they have some contact with the traditional oral arts through their family backgrounds they are not as

skilled in them as the performers discussed above. Ademola Onibonokuta, Lere Paimo and Biqun Duro Ladipo are the most prominent artists in this group. Both Ademola Onibonokuta and Lere Paimo have, in addition to performing, also taken major administrative roles in the organization as business and theatre managers. Biqun Duro-Ladipo was, similarly, until her husband's death in charge of costume and properties and the welfare of the actresses. The three of them assisted in play-directing and in the training of other performers. They also sometimes composed neo-traditional songs used in parts of the plays (See Olajubu 1973 and Beier in Jeyifo 1981: 182-183).

CHAPTER TWO

NOTES

1. Yorùbá drama of English expression such as the plays of Wole Soyinka and Ola Rotimi are excluded by this definition.
2. We have exercised great restraint in calling eégún aláré, secular drama because its practitioners are strictly speaking, members of the egúngún cult and are known by the common name òjè. In an eégún aláré performance, entertainment is foregrounded while ritual is backgrounded.
3. This label is adopted to solve the problem of appropriate references to the professional dramatic movement and tradition which Ogunde pioneered (See sections 2.1.0-2.1.7).
4. When used in this work, traditional drama refers to the drama that is pre-colonial while modern/neo-traditional drama refers to that which is colonial and post-colonial.
5. The situation is general in Yorùbá literature where the traditional oral forms are transcribed and are not seen as written literature. Examples of transcribed oral poetry books include Wande Abimbola's Ijinlẹ̀ Ohùn Ènu Ifá Apa Kini àti Apá Keji and Babalola's Oríki Orílẹ̀.

6. Ulli Beier in an interview we had with him when he came to Nigeria in 1986 denied this claim and explained that he only used a label that was then in vogue among the people.
7. Graham-White (1974: 2-3) exercised great restraint in even calling the unscripted drama "being performed before the colonial era and which in many cases still is being performed", "folk drama" because as he notes the term "folk"-conjures up images of a performance distilled somehow through the ages by the "folk" into a "fixed form" and folk drama is also usually regarded as "a thing of the past".
8. It is common knowledge that Yorùbá traditional festivals are usually celebrated by virtually all members of the community irrespective of their class or creed. Even foreigners from the Western world often attend some of these festivals - Oṣun at Oṣogbo for example.
9. One cannot but recall at this juncture the fact that the performance of Efúnṣetán Aníwúrà was watched at the Liberty Stadium, Ibadan by an audience of not less than fourteen thousand spectators (See Iṣṣṣla 1981: 407 and Jeyifo 1984: 115). The play has also been recorded in five other media of performance: radio, television, photo-play and phono-disc and film.

10. There is a system of lineage profession in Yoruba traditional institution - the Onírèsé are calabash sculptors, the Ìrèmògún are blacksmiths, the Qlófà are farmers and the Ìkòyí are warriors. See the oríki of most of the lineages in Babalola 1967.
11. The farming and hunting profession will allow an ológbínín to familiarise himself with plants and animals used in medicinal ingredients.
12. Attempts made at classifying Nigerian drama include those of J. P. Clark (1968), Rotimi (1971) and Ogunbiyi (1981).
13. Similar methods are used by the Concert Party theatres of neighbouring countries such as Ghana, Republic of Benin and Togo (See Ricard 1974: 165-179).
14. An example of the few places in festival drama where dialogue is used is in the question and answer session between cult officials and other members of the cult such as is found in a scene of the Adimu Oríṣa festival in Lagos. As each éyò group approaches the cult official the following dialogue ensues between the official and the leader of the éyò group.

Cultist: Agogoro Èyò
Èyò : Mo yò fún ẹ
Mo yò fúnrà mí
Èmi agogoro èyò

Cultist: Pánti wá?
Èyò : Pánti ẹ
Cultist: Qpá àsí lékà sí kó?
Èyò : Tèyin ló jù:

Cultist: You are the imposing èyò
Èyò : I rejoice with you
I rejoice with myself
I am the imposing èyò

Cultist: Why have you come?
Èyò : Because I have a duty
Cultist: What about the staff on the shoulders?
Èyò : It is the rear part which weighs much?

(See Adedeji 1973c: 17-18).

15. There was, before this time, a popular Concert Party comedy tradition, pioneered by Yalley Ishmael Johnson (Bob Johnson), Charles B. Hutton and J. B. Ansah, in Ghana. Ogunde's biblical opera was therefore out of taste. (See Angmor 1978: 56).

16. The films are:

Àjàní Ogún

Ijà Ominira

Ayé

Jaiyesinmi

Kádàrà

Aropin N Teniyàn

Owó Làgbà (Money Power)

Ijà Orogún

Taxi Driver I and II

Aníkúrá

Ayànmó

Omọ Orukàn

Ojú Oró

Iyá Ni Wúra

Líṣàbí

Efúnṣetán Aniwúra

Irèké Oníbùdó

Ààrẹ Agbayé

Qrun Móoru

Mo Ṣe Bólá Tán

Kanna Kánná

Ogun Ajàyè

Eégún Lẹ rí

Ìtākùn

17. Such interviews include those of Jeyifo (1981) and those conducted by the present writer with Oyin Adejọbi (19th July and 22nd August 1981), Iṣọla Ogunṣọla (5th September, 1982), Mrs Tayọ Ogunmọla, (15th October, 1983), Mr. Olowomojuọrẹ (5th September, 1983), and Biọdun Duro-Ladipo (26th September, 1st and 11th October, 1986).

18. This was at a symposium organized in remembrance of the late Duro-Ladipo in 1984 by the Qyọ State Council for Arts and Culture and held at the main auditorium of the Cultural Centre, Mọkọlá Hill, Ibadan.

19. As Arohunmqlaṣe (1982) has pointed out in his criticism of our (1981) analysis, it is possible to have a feed-back of the audience reactions after the performance and the dramatist can take care of such reactions in subsequent performances. This type of reaction, however, does not have the same effect of immediacy which is experienced only during the live performance. Also the following diagrams used in illustrating our (1981) explanation of the audience/performance interactions in the live stage and other media of performance have been condemned as superfluous by Arohunmqlaṣe (1982).

Direction of interaction in
other media of performance

Direction of interaction
on stage performances.

We are, however, of the opinion that the clear explanatory effect of the diagrams makes them pedagogically very relevant to the conceptualization of the discussion.

20. Arohunmqlaṣe (1982) also disagrees with our (1981) views on the use of bold prints and thought balloons. But Adeoye (1984) in his own review of both Ogundeji's and Arohunmqlaṣe's has appropriately noted that

"Arohunqlaṣe's argument in support of bold prints ... is probably a misinterpretation of Ogundeji's claim" (Emphasis mine).

21. Dayo Adekunle made a manuscript of the Christmas Cantata and that of Joseph the Dreamer available to the present writer.
22. Yemi Eḷebuubon had a brief primary education early in his youth before he was withdrawn to be trained as an Ifá priest. He also went to a private school after his Ifá pupilage in 1967. He therefore cannot be regarded as a non-literate. By 1967 when he served as Professor Qlatunji's research assistant at Oṣogbo he could write Yoruba a lot. Today he is fluent in English. He actually belongs to a mid category according to our classification of the performers. He is grouped in the first category just for ease of discourse.

PART TWO

ANALYSIS

CHAPTER THREE

MUSICO-POETIC CODE

3.0 INTRODUCTORY NOTES

Under this heading, we do not intend to describe music as a semiotic system in itself. That is a task that should be left for the semiotic-inclined musicologist. Our own orientation is more towards the poetic than the musical. It is because the two semiotic fields of music and poetry are, within their Yoruba conception and, especially in the dramatic context of our data, inseparable that we shall discuss music from the literary man's point of view in this work.

The Yorùbá musico-poetic tradition is categorised into two after Akin Euba (1970), traditional and neo-traditional. The pre-colonial forms are regarded as traditional while the new ones introduced during and after the colonial days, but which are based on traditional patterns, are regarded as neo-traditional. Traditional patterns may either be adopted or adapted in the creation of neo-traditional musico-poetic style. In our analysis, a traditional pattern is considered as adopted, when the relevant extra-textual context of performance is presented along with its appropriate

musico-poetic mode of performance and text. Slight changes may, however, be necessary in such adoption for dramatic effects. A traditional pattern is, on the other hand, considered as properly adapted when the musico-poetic context is transplanted from its extra-textual reality into a different dramatic context, or when new lines are built on common traditional melody.

In their treatment of poetry, the structuralists (especially Jakobson) pay attention to the "poetic function" which is regarded as the orientation towards, or emphasis on, the linguistic signifier for the purpose of foregrounding aesthetic combinations (See Jakobson 1960: 356). The poem is usually divided into stanzas and usually shown is "how symmetrical distribution of grammatical items organizes the stanzas into various groupings" (Culler 1975: 59). The interest is often in the alliterations, assonances, rhymes, rhythms and parallelism of various types (See Jakobson and Levi-Strauss 1973: 372-389). This implies a neglect of the other communicative functions, especially the referential, within which the poetic one is situated and without which it cannot properly operate. Whereas for Jakobson the

referential function is only not dominant and often ambiguous in poetic discourse (Jakobson 1960: 356), it is completely replaced by the "semiotic function" for Riffattere (Riffattere 1977: 7). But for Yuri Lotman and Scholes (1982) the referential function is as important as other communicative functions in a poetic discourse.

Though it is clear that the situation is far from settled among literary structuralists, it is important to note that the notion of referential fallacy belongs more to a formalist-structuralist poetics than to a semiotic one. It is the semiotically oriented poetic analysis, the type expounded by Scholes (1982: 37-56), which takes care of the poem's referential and other related contexts along with the poetic one, that we find comfortably adequate for the analysis of poetry in drama. We cannot, in the analysis of dramatic poetry, but take the syntagmatic, paradigmatic, and pragmatic relations into consideration (Scholes 1982: 49).

The point to note about poetry in drama is that it is strictly contextualized. There is, unlike with

ordinary poetry, (poetry as found in poetry books), always a given context to the poem in drama. In ordinary poetry, the poem will have to generate its own context from its intra- and extra-textual relationships. The "I" and "You" of the poem is, for example, often masked. This is, however, not to imply that one will not appeal to extra-dramatic contexts in the analysis of dramatic poetry; rather it implies that all the meanings and interpretations given to a dramatic poem will primarily be conditioned by the dramatic context. This observation, it should be noted, is as true of poetry as of other aspects of the musico-poetic code such as instrumentation, rhythm, melody and dance, some of which will be explored in this chapter.

3.1.0 TRADITIONAL MUSICO-POETIC STRUCTURES

The three primary modes of Yorùbá poetic rendition, singing, chanting and speaking (Oluḱoju 1978) can be conceptualized in a sort of musical gradation scale with singing and speaking at the two extreme ends, while chanting is in the middle. A content oriented cline will, however, have the spoken mode in the middle

while the other two are at the opposite ends. This second gradation is possible because all the poetic types in the speech mode class can also be rendered in either of the other two modes. In fact, they are usually incorporated into the texts of different songs and chants. Oriki (a major speech mode type) in particular has been noted to be the primary text of most, if not all the chants (see Babalola 1966: 19-38, Vidal 1980: 8-9, Qlatunji 1984: 67). The performative fluid nature of the chants is, undoubtedly responsible for the medial position of the speech mode in the content oriented cline. We will in the light of this fact not discuss our analysis of the speech mode separately. We will instead, discuss it as an integral part of the analysis of poetry in the other two modes according to how Duro Ladipo has structured them in his plays under study.

3.1.1.0 Songs

The traditional songs prominent in Duro Ladipo's mythico-historical plays under study include festival songs, children's songs and war songs.

3.1.1.1 Festival Songs

Festival songs are more prominent in Morèmi and Ọsun than in other plays. This is a reflection of the extra-textual situation where songs are more prominent than chants in the Edi (or Morèmi) and Ọsun festivals while the reverse is the case in the Ọbàtálá and Ẹàngó festivals from which songs would have been adopted and/or adapted into Ọba Kò So and Ọbàtálá.

The Edi festival songs codified in Duro Ladipo's Morèmi include "Iná bàbá jó rire" (p. 44), "Ẹnu ogbigbò gbèkan" (p. 44), "Wórò wórò Pantéètè" (p. 52) and "Ọyá ká Ẹeré Morèmi" (p. 53). The four festival songs constitute the two sub-texts lurking in two other songs. The first two songs are really woven into the following single composition for dramatic purpose.

Iná bàbá jó rire
 Ariṣikà, iná bàbá jó rire;
 Níjọ Igbò Ẹkéké!
 Ẹnu Igbò mà kan o
 A rẹhin ọtá, a rẹhin odì 5
 Morèmi Ajàṣorò, akin obinrin
 Iná bàbá jó rire o,
 Ariṣikà iná bàbá jó rire. (1971: 44)

Our father's fire burns well

We are no evil doers. our father's fire
burns well,

The day the Ìgbòs were deceitful

The Ìgbòs' mouths went sour

We saw the end of our enemies, we saw
the end of our opponents

5

Mọ̀rèmi Àjàṣorò, the brave woman

Our father's fire burns well

We are no evil doers, our father's
fire burns well.

The song is rendered in unison by the Ifẹ̀ warriors immediately after their victory over the Igbò. The song is therefore primarily a song of victory in the dramatic context. In the extra-textual context the two songs are each rendered in the responsorial pattern:

Lílẹ̀: Iná bàbá jó rire o

Ègbè: Àrèsikà

Lílẹ̀: Iná bàbá jó rire o

Ègbè: Àrèsikà

Lead: Our father's fire burns well

Chorus: We are no evil doers

Lead: Our father's fire burns well.

Chorus: We are no evil doers

and

Lílé: Níjọ̀ Ìgbò sèké

Egbè: Ènu Ìgbò gbèkan

Lílé: Níjọ̀ Ìgbò sèké

Egbè: Ènu Ìgbò gbèkan

Lead: The day the Ìgbòs were deceitful

Chorus: The Ìgbò's mouths went sour

Lead: The day the Ìgbòs were deceitful

Chorus: The Ìgbòs' mouths went sour

It is therefore realised that it is not only in merging the two songs into one that Duro Ladipo can be said to have adapted the songs but also in reducing the responsorial pattern to one of unison. Two new lines (5 and 6) are also added to make the new composition more directly relevant to both the immediate and remote dramatic contexts of the victory. Line 5 generally celebrates the victory while line 6 can be seen as crediting the victory to Mọ̀rèmi who actually paves the way for it. This should lead us to a detailed comparative analysis of the textual and extra-textual

contexts of the songs.

The songs in their festival, extra-textual contexts are usually rendered at the inásánán phase of the festival after fire brands have been lighted and displayed before the Ọ̀nì sitting in state, and the people in general. The fire brands can be seen as iconic signifier of the mythico-historical firebrands (signified) used in roasting the Ìgbò raffia-masqued warriors. The fact that the two songs are found in the same extra-textual context has probably motivated Duro Ladipọ to merge them together to celebrate the victory. Both the dramatic, textual and festival, extra-textual contexts are commemorating the said victory. This makes the songs thematically relevant to their contexts. Because victory has been achieved through the use of the fire brands, the fire brands can be said to have truly burnt well. And the Ifẹ̀ people can also be finally said to be the justified ones, since they have the final victory. They are in that wise not the "evil doers". The Ìgbò people who wrongly use a sacred disguise in waging war against the Ifẹ̀ are the "evil doers". They are therefore rightly considered

wayward. This partly explains why they are completely routed.

As distinct from the foregoing, the extra-textual responsorial pattern of the other two songs, "Wòrò wòrò Pantètè" and "È jé ká şeré Mọrèmi", are adapted into their textual contexts. They are rendered immediately one after the other.

Wòròwòrò-----Pàntètè
 Wòròwòrò-----Pàntètè
 Á rọ mí, á rọ ọ-----Pàntètè
 Á rọ ẹkẹ ilé-----Pàntètè
 Ìgbín akika-----Pàntètè
 Ọmọ olúwo-----Pàntètè

Èèèè ò! Èèèè o!!

Ó yá ká şiré Mọrèmi o ... Èèèèè Kolómbè
 Asẹ̀.ìn şánko awùsá o ... Èèèèè Kolómbè
 Akọgun nìkàn l'aròró ò... Èèèèè Kolómbè
 Ípére şánko şánko ... Èèèèè Kolómbè
 Akọgun kẹràn-an dè mí o ... Èèèèè Kolómbè
 A kì í şánko láíkọ ebè ... Èèèèè Kolómbè

(1970: 52-53)

Wọrọwọrọ.....Pàntẹtẹ

Wọrọwọrọ.....Pàntẹtẹ

Things will be easy for me and you.....Pàntẹtẹ

It'll be easy for the house post.....Pàntẹtẹ

Snail armadilloPàntẹtẹ

Olúwo's child.....Pàntẹtẹ

Eèééè ò! Eèéé o!!

Now let's play Mọrèmi's game.....Eèééé Kolómbẹ

When it was time to cultivate the awùsá farm land
.....Eèééé Kolómbẹ

Only Akọgun was miserly.....Eèééé Kolómbẹ

The snail cleared the bush for a long time
.....Eèééé Kolómbẹ

Akọgun you should leave some meat for me
.....Eèééé Kolómbẹ

One doesn't clear the bush without making heaps
.....Eèééé Kolómbẹ

The two songs are separated by the exclamation as shown in the excerpt above. They are usually used at the initial stage of the Edì festival known as ọfọnràn to generate the happy festive mood needed for the festival. At this stage of the festival, fire is made

in front of each house and at road junctions early in the morning to ward off evil spirits as the people prepare for the festival. This phase of the festival may also be seen as commemorating the arrival of Mọ̀rẹ̀mi from Ìgbò land. The fire can therefore be seen as iconic of such a fire made on Mọ̀rẹ̀mi's arrival from Ìgbò land. It was from the fire that the fire brands were lighted when the Ìgbò warriors came. In the dramatic context, the songs are rendered after Olúorogbo has been sacrificed. The Ifẹ̀ people want to start mourning but Mọ̀rẹ̀mi advises them that rather than mourn, they should be happy; she then implores them to erect a shrine in remembrance of Olúorogbo. One can therefore see that unlike the first two songs treated above, the extra-textual and textual contexts are not identical. The relationship between the two uses of the songs (signifiers) is therefore restricted to generating felicitous atmosphere (signified). Though there is no structural change in the songs, their dramatic codification is still seen as an adaptation of the festival song.

Looking at the thematic content of the two songs, one realises that "Wọ̀rọ̀wọ̀rọ̀ Pantẹ̀tẹ̀" has a more direct relevance to the dramatic context in a way which

"È jẹ ká ẹrẹ Mọrẹmi" does not. The prayerful theme of "Wọrọwọrọ Pantẹtẹ" in the festival context is a general prayer for peace within the community. In the dramatic context, since the song comes after Olúorogbo's sacrificial demise, the prayerful content has to be seen in the light of the sacrificial context. Olúorogbo's death is the supposed harbinger of the peace which the whole of Ifẹ starts enjoying after his death.

The adaptative styles and general structuralization of the festival songs in Ọsun are not dynamically different from those already discussed above. One of such songs in Ọsun, "Gbọkọgbọkọ", is, however, worthy of our comments because of the basic analytical problem it poses. It is rendered in unison by Ọbà twice in the play.

Gbọkọgbọkọ

Kó má gbọkọ mọ mi lẹwọ

Gbọkọgbọkọ

Kọ má gbọkọ mọ mi lẹwọ

May husband-snatchers

Not snatch my husband from me

May husband-snatchers

Not snatch my husband from me.

Other variations of the song where omo and aya substituted for okọ are also usually rendered in the extra-textual festival context (see Olowuni 1979: 79). The song is usually rendered responsorially in the extra-text with the chorus fully repeating the leaders line. The tendency is to conclude that Duro Ladipo has adopted and/or adapted the song from the Oṣun festival. Looking more closely at the dramatic context, one, however, realizes the need to be cautious in coming to that conclusion.

The song is textually used in the context of ^{rivalry} among co-wives where it is directed at the more experienced and elderly but new wife, Oṣun. After rendering the song on the second occasion, Oya, another senior co-wife of Obà, joins her in singing another house-wives' rivalry song which is also clearly directed at Oṣun.

Pekélépekèlè

Pekélépe

Arúgbó jẹgbèsè

Ta ní ó san?

Pekélépekèlè

Pekélépe

An old woman has incurred a debt

Who'll pay it?

The derision in this second song is directed at the fact that Ọṣun, the new wife, is older than the two senior wives. The situation is in fact ironical within the Yorùbá cultural context in which the second wife is usually younger than her senior co-wife. This second song coupled with the general dramatic textual co-wives' rivalry context is indexical of the fact that the first song is also to be primarily seen as an

co-wives' rivalry song. The prayerful wish, which is foregrounded in the extra-textual festival context is secondary in the textual context. This prayerful wish should, in fact, be properly seen as a means to an end in the secondary role.

The problem arises when it is realised that the song is also found in the extra-textual co-wives' rivalry context. The performance in unison of the song in the text agrees with what operates in the extra-textual co-wives' rivalry context. There is therefore

the tendency to see the song as having been adopted from the extra-textual co-wives' rivalry context. But at the same time the Ọṣun macro-context of the play cannot make us disregard the possibility of an adaptation from the festival song. The indeterminacy of the compositional structure of the song reminds us of the oral and popular nature of the source materials where the same poetic text can be set on various musical modes. The thematic relevance in such a poetic text to its textual context is the most important thing.

3.1.1.2 Children's Songs

The adoption and adaptation of traditional children's songs similar to those of the festival songs analysed above are found in Béyí Ọ Se, Obá Wàjà, Morèmi and Obàtálá. Such songs include folktale songs, games and deterrence songs.

The folktale songs "Erò Ọjà Olówó" (You traders at Olówó's market), is codified in the market scenes in both Béyí ọ Se and Obá Wàjà. The song can be considered as a case of adoption in that it is taken from a market context in the folktale into a market context in the

plays. But Duro Ladipo has restructured the song for dramatic effect. It is in this sense, therefore, also a case of adaptation. Only the initial lead part and the chorus refrain are adopted from the folktale. Other lines are woven into the remaining lead parts. The text of the new composition in Bevi ò Se is as follows,

Lílé: Èrò ojà Olówó

Egbè: Jàlòlòjalóló

Lílé: È bá dákun

È gbà wá sílẹ̀

Egbè: Jàlòlòjalóló

Lead: You traders at Olówó market

Chorus: Jàlòlòjalóló

Lead: Would you please

Deliver us

Chorus: Jàlòlòjalóló

while that of Obá Wàjà (Beier 1964: 58) is also as follows,

Rich people trading in the market

Jàlòlò jalóló

People trading in the market

You hope to get rich quickly

Jalòlò jalóló

Let us see your kichikpa cloth

That is good for a farmer's gown

Give us a reasonable price:

A house is not built in one day.

Jalòlò jalóló.

The different contextual situations of the two dramatic market scenes is clearly indicated in the songs. The former is a slave market - that is why the singing slaves are imploring the traders in the market to save them. The latter is a cloth market or at least the section of a market where traditional textile materials are sold and the song is rendered by two customers (crossing the stage) who want to buy some cloths. The wide difference between the lead parts of the two songs quoted above on the one hand and that of the folktale song below is an index of the imaginative adaptative competence of Duro Ladipo.

- Lilé: Èrò ọjà olówó
- Egbè: Jàlòlòja. óló
- Lilé: Njẹkàn bá mi rọmọ mi?
- Egbè: Jàlòlòjalóló
- Lilé: Kí lorúkọ ọmọ rẹ mà mi jẹ?
- Egbè: Jàlòlòjalóló
- Lilé: Ọkàn Wẹrẹwẹrẹ-là-á-sẹgi
 Ọkàn Wọrọwọrọ-là-á-bọfọ
 Ọrọ Ọmọniyùn kékeré
 Ọrọ Ọmọniyùn ó dùn mí yéye
- Egbè: Jàlòlòjalóló
- Lead: Traders at Olówo market
- Chorus: Jàlòlòjalóló
- Lead: Have you seen my children?
- Chorus: Jàlòlòjalóló
- Lead: What are the names of your children?
- Chorus: Jàlòlòjalóló
- Lead: One is Wẹrẹwẹrẹ-là-á-sẹgi
 Another is Wọrọwọrọ-là-á-bọfọ
 It is the case of little Ọmọniyùn
 It is Ọmọniyùn's case
 That pains me most
- Chorus: Jàlòlòjalóló¹

The adaptative codification of the remaining children songs is slightly different from that of the folktale song just treated. The games song "Eṣin banba kútúpà" in Obàtálá and the deterrence songs "Eṣi orò kú lé lórí" and "Ojú olè rè é" in Obá Wàjà and Obàtálá respectively can be considered as merely adopted because they are reproduced in their dramatic contexts without any structural change. The general renditional patterns are also retained. "Ojú olè rè é" is rendered in the responsorial pattern while the other two songs are rendered in unison. It is therefore in the transplantation of the songs from their extra-textual contexts to their textual contexts that their adaptation lies.

The song

Eṣin banba kútúpà

Kútúpà, kútúpà

Eṣin banba

The big galloping horse

Galloping, galloping

The big horse

is usually rendered when children sight a horse or when

imitating horse-riding. The song is used in a similar dramatic context as background to the enactment of horse-riding by Ọbàtálá. The second song,

Èní orò kú lé lórí
 Kò ẹ́ ẹ́ bá ẹ́rẹ́ mọ́
 Okèlè bànhà
 Omi ọbẹ́ ẹ́ororo

Anyone who comes last in the performance of
 the ritual competition
 Will no more be played with
 Heavy morsel
 Watery soup

is usually used to deride the child who lags behind in hide-and-seeK games such as bojúbojú or ekùn méran. The song is used by the citizens of Ọyọ́ to ridicule Olórí Èlẹ́şin Ọba for failing to perform his ritual duty of committing suicide after the ọba's demise. Likewise the third song,

Lílẹ́: Ọjú olẹ̀ rẹ̀ ẹ́
 Ègbẹ̀: Olẹ̀
 Lílẹ́: Ọjú olẹ̀ rẹ̀ ẹ́
 Ègbẹ̀: Olẹ̀

Lead: Here's the thief's face
 Chorus: The thief
 Lead: Here's the thief's face
 Chorus: The thief

which is normally used to ridicule the pilferer among children, is used as the background song in the scene where Ọbàtálá is caught riding the lost horse of king Şàngó.

It can be seen from the on-going that the dramatic contexts of these songs are very similar to their extra-textual contexts. The only difference is in that adults are involved in the rendition and other activities in the dramatic context while children are the sole actors in the extra-text.

Whereas the thematic relationships of the three songs just treated, to their respective dramatic contexts are strong, that of the folktale song to its textual context is weak. The thematic content of the folktale songs is not determined by the previous actions in the plotal development. The primary signification in both cases, however, lies in the musical creation of the necessary respective atmospheres. The thematic content

and other aspects are no doubt contributive either directly or indirectly to this primary signification. One should exercise great restraint in concluding that the children's songs reduce the seriousness of the dramatic situations in particular and the plays in general. They should instead be seen as reinforcing the pleasure derivable from the performances in general. In fact, they generally help in reducing acute tension in the tragic plotal developments of the plays.

3.1.1.3 War Songs

War songs are prominent in Morèmi, Ajagun-ńlá and Béyí ò se. The war songs are those used in mobilising warriors and in frightening the enemy, and those used in celebrating martial victory. The songs are in the dramatic contexts usually preceded by the following exclamatory call and response:

Lílé: Gídígbògídígbò!

Egbè: Héè!

An example of war songs found in Beyí ò Se is:

Lilé: Èni yòó wù kó dúró dọba
 Egbè: Awówó á wo o
 Lilé: Èni yòó wù kó dúró dọba.
 Egbè: Awówó á wo o

Lead: Any one who stands in the King's way
 Chorus: Will be crushed
 Lead: Any one who stands in the King's way
 Chorus: Will be crushed.

The lead part, and this is also true of the exclamatory call and response just cited, is rendered by a war leader while the response is by the other warriors. The song as a whole is an example of war songs used to frighten the opposing sides and it is used by the two sides involved in their individual martial campaigns. From a structural aesthetic perspective such use of the same war song by two opposing sides though at different points on the plotal line does not look neat enough. It does not allow for a clear delineation of the two sides involved in the military campaign for example. The primary signficatory purpose of creating a battle-charged atmosphere seems to have eclipsed other artistic intricacies in these particular codifications.

In Ajagun-ńlá, the most war-oriented of the

eight plays, there are not less than six war songs some of which are repeated more than once. Most of them fall into the category of those used in frightening the enemy. There are, however, some used in celebrating martial victory of which the following is an example:

A ẹẹ, ẹẹ a jù wọn lọ ná o
 A ẹẹ, ẹẹ a jù wọn lọ ná
 Igba ìròrẹ̀ ò tókan àparò
 A ẹẹ, ẹẹ a jù wọn lọ ná

We strove hard and have superseded them
 We strove hard and have superseded them
 One thousand tiny birds are no match for
 a partridge
 We strove hard and have superseded them.

It is not clear which battle has just been fought and won at the opening section of the play, when this song is first used. Whereas the first person pronoun in the song clearly refers to the four war lords who render the song and/or to the people under their leadership, we do not know to whom the third person pronoun refers. But the content of the song and general celebrative context of the opening scene are clear indices of the identified significatory purpose of the song.

The example of the war song in Morèmi is unique in that it is presented in a mixture of Yorùbá and non-Yorùbá language. The following alternative of "Gídígbògídígbò", used in Morèmi to call the Igbò warriors to attention and to arouse their spirit in general, is borrowed from the Igbo language of Eastern Nigeria.

Lead: Igbo ku énú (kwenu)

Chorus: Héèè

The war song rendered by the Ìgbò to instil fear into the people of Ifẹ̀ is also a mixture of Yorùbá (in the first two lines) and Igbo (in the remaining lines).

Ọba ju ọba lọ

Ọba ju ọba lọ

Obi ẹ se ni mo jo

Obi ẹ se ni mo jo

One king is superior to the other

One king is superior to the other

It is Obi that we respect

It is Obi that we respect

The Ìgbò warriors are through this song saying that their king, and therefore the whole of Ìgbò people, are more

powerful than the Ifẹ king and his people. Rendered properly in Igbo the last two lines of the song will look thus "obi se no jle" (Adedeji 1972: 138). Duro Ladipo has aesthetically employed an Igbo musico-poetic art in this case to delineate clearly the Ịgbò warriors from the Ifẹ warriors unlike in the case of "Eni yòb wù kó dúró dọba" discussed above. In fact, Duro Ladipo is known to have invited the Otu Osomeze group of dancers from Agbor (Ika Igbo) to act the Ịgbò in the premier performance of the play in 1966 (Adedeji 1972: 139 and Ogunbiyi 1981: 351). By the use of the Agbor musico-poetic form it is probably being suggested that the Ịgbò of the Mọrẹmi myth is the same as the Igbo of the Eastern part of Nigeria. Awolalu (1979: 26) has, however, identified the Ịgbò of the Mọrẹmi myth with the Ụgbò people of the Ịlàjẹ town in Ọkitipupa part of Ọndó State. This identification is said to be supported by a very strong oral tradition among the Ụgbò people that they were aborigines of Ilé-Ifẹ. Awolalu (1979: 26) reports:

There are places in Ilé Ifẹ today which cannot be seen by traditional Ụgbò people; and it is also believed that if

any Ifè people should set eyes on Ùgbò town they will die. Whenever Ifè people need to pass by Ùgbò, they cover their heads.

In the light of this finding, Duro Ladipo's codification of the Ìgbò in Mọ̀rèmi myth as the Igbo of Eastern states may be seen only as an aesthetic signification. This conclusion, it should be noted, agrees with Adedeji's view (1972: 138-139) that Duro Ladipo is "more interested in the dramatic effect" than in the mythico-historical significations.

3.1.2 Chants

The chanting modes found in the plays under study include esà, ìjálá, ràrà, ìyèrè Ifá and àsámò. Esà is the most prominent of them all and it forms the main focus of the discussion in this section, though references are made to others where necessary. As already mentioned (see 3.1.0 above), oríkì forms the main content materials of the chants.

The dramatic situations in which esà eégún is commonly contextualized are generally not the same as those of the normal extra-textual egúngún context. It

is usually adapted for dramatic use in palace contexts for praise singing. The court poets, Iwàrẹfà in Oba Kò So, Olórí ẹmesẹ in Morẹmi and Ológbo in Oba Mórò, for example, chant the praises of kings Ẓàngó, Aláyémọrẹ and Abípa respectively in the esà mode. So also are the praises of the war lords in Ajagun-ńlá, Oba Kò So and that of Olórí Ẹlẹṣin Ọba in Obá Wájà. The Baṣọrun in Bevíf ọ Se similarly employs the mode in eulogising both the dead Aláàfin and the newly installed Aláàfin Aólẹ. It is of importance to note that the ràrà chanting mode is the most appropriate extra-textual mode used in these contexts among the Yorùbá. It is in fact only in Baálẹ Apòmù's palace context in Bevíf ọ Se that ràrà is iconised.

There are two types of styles in which the chants are usually codified. The praises of all monarchs and those of some very important chiefs such as Oníkòyí in Ajagun-ńlá are usually chanted by another person, the court poet or a chief as the case may be. But other characters, such as Gbonka and Timì in Oba Kò So, and Olúgbón and Arẹsà in Ajagun-ńlá, usually chant their praises themselves. Though not common among the Yorùbá the chanting of one's praises oneself is dramatically

economical and very striking. It can also be seen as a character delineation signifier between the two groups whose praises are chanted in the plays. The preponderant use of the èṣà egúngún chanting mode is certainly conditioned by the fact that many of Duro Ladipò's collaborators are well versed in the art.

With regard to the relationship between the contents of the chants and the contexts, Armstrong (1978: 372) has noted that the Iwàrèfà's chants after Ṣàngó's two war-lords and the Òyómèsìs have walked out on him respectively are "ironically out of place" and "inappropriate". Here are the texts of the two chants.

Ewéléré, ọkọọ mi o!
 Ààrá-ṣowó-ìjà-lálá!
 Ààrá-ò-íjà-wólé!
 Gbe-ngbe-lekú-r'íjà
 Ó yò ṣẹṣẹṣẹ!

(1970: 13)

Ewéléré, my husband!
 Thunder, who displays his fighting hands!
 Thunder, who knocks down a house in anger
 The prodigy sees a fight in progress
 And rejoices exceedingly!

(1970: 79)

Şàngó l'ẹni t'o bá ẹ ni lóore náà làá
dúpẹ́ fún

Ó bá baálé jìyan-à-n-gángán tán,

Ó p'ọmọ rẹ síloro!

Sángiri-làgiri

Ọlàgiri kàkà figba ẹdùn bọ ọ!

(1970: 14)

Şàngó says that a person who does good
to someone is the one whom we thank.

When he finishes eating pounded yam

with the head of the family

He kills his son on the porch!

Who cracks walls, spilts walls!

Who spilts the wall open and thrusts

two hundred thunderstones into it.

(1970: 81)

One would have thought that these powerful poetic lines
would instigate Şàngó into violent reactions to the
insultive gestures from his subordinates, but he instead
keeps his calm and succumbs easily to the threats of the
two groups. The description of Aláàfin Aólẹ in

Béyí ọ Se as

Ọmọ ọhúnhúnhun

Tí í róbìnrin ẹ láşọ

Ọwọwọ tí í wọ tálíkà lẹwù

Offspring of the great weaver
 That clothes his women
 The lover of clothes that clothes the poor

can similarly be seen as ironical in the context of Aólẹ's characterization. He, for example, through sheer inconsiderate and self-conceited arrogance, leads the whole of Ọyó into civil upheaval. One therefore tends to conclude that he is not worthy of the lines of the praise poetry.

The ironical ambivalence can, however, be explained within the extra-textual context. In Şangó's case, one can postulate that he has probably acquired the strong praise lines earlier than the time being depicted in the play. Similarly, Aólẹ may have inherited the praise lines. The content of the praises therefore need not be derived from the actions in the play. Similar situations are, in fact, possible in the extra-text. The oral poet usually picks from a repertoire of poetic lines; the action of the object of praise at that point in time need not correlate with the content of praise. To us, the ironical signification makes the codifications more aesthetic than an alternative one where there is a straightforward content/context relationship. It is

therefore arguable to say that the codifications are "inappropriate".

3.2.0 NEO-TRADITIONAL MUSICO-POETIC STRUCTURES

The neo-traditional musico-poetic forms are mostly songs usually composed on church and pop melodies. Such songs, though usually distinct in content and melody from the traditional ones, are often based on traditional patterns. These songs, however, also include "pieces in which strong European influences remain" (Euba 1977: 14). Topics discussed under this section include the opening and closing glees and other neo-traditional songs classified into dialogised and non-dialogised songs.

3.2.1.0 Extra-plotal Beginning and Ending

As discussed earlier in Chapter Two, plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition are usually sandwiched between the opening and closing glees (or in variations of these as the case may be) during live performances. These two glees are usually not intrinsically part of the plot. Their relationship is essentially extra-plotal. They can, in fact, be respectively taken as prologue and epilogue to the plot almost in the traditional Greek

sense.

It has been observed in earlier writings that Duro Ladipo has merely removed the opening and closing glees from the structure of the presentation of his plays on the live stage and replaced them with the curtain raising and the lining up of performers taking their bow after performance (Eḡun Clark 1979: 140, Jeyifo 1984: 12). Our own finding, however, shows that the situation is not as clear cut as that. There is evidence to show that Duro Ladipo sometimes employs the same format as in the live performances of his plays. Instances of the use of the opening glee can be found in the recorded performance of Oḡa Mòrò and Oḡun in the archives of the Institute of African Studies, University of Ibadan. Odusanya (1981: 77) also notes that a particular song culled from Mòrèmi is generally used as closing glee in the live performance of Duro Ladipo's plays. Our personal experience of the performances and our interview with Biḡdun Duro-Ladipo corroborate Odusanya's observation. The recording of Aiagun-ńlá and Béyif ò Se in the University of Ibadan's Institute of African Studies indicates the use of the closing glee.

After Duro Ladipo's demise, Biḡḡun Duro-Ladipo who has taken over the leadership of the theatre troupe, composed an opening glee song, as a sort of homage-paying and general remembrance of her late husband, which she uses in most of her stage performances. She is also known to have continued the use of the song culled from Morèmi as closing glee. In the light of these facts it is not correct that Duro Ladipo did not use the opening and closing glees in the structuralization of his performances, as previous scholars want us to believe.

3.2.1.1 The Opening Glee

The text of the extra-plotal song composed for Oba Mòrò is as follows: We are quoting it in full because no text of it has appeared in print before.

Ajọkọ: E kú ikàlẹ ara wa o
 A kí yín o
 E kú àgbówá o
 E kú ikàlẹ ará wa o
 À kí yín o
 E kú àgbówá o
 A gbéré wa dé
 Olóyin mọmọ ni
 A gbéré wa dé
 Olóyin mọmọ ni

5

10

Ìròyìn kò táfojúbà

Ọ̀bẹ̀ ogee

Tó ǹ dùn yìn-ìn

Ọ̀lá orílẹ̀ẹ̀ wa ni ká máa wá o

Ọ̀lá orílẹ̀ẹ̀ wa ni ká máa wá

15

Ọ̀lá orílẹ̀ẹ̀ wa ni ká máa wá o

Ọ̀lá orílẹ̀ẹ̀ wa ni ká máa wa

Bí a bá lówó

Tí a sì ní láárí o

Ọ̀lá orílẹ̀ wa ni ká máa wá

20

À ní wí o

Akókò kò mà dúró dẹnìkan mọ

Ọ̀lá orílẹ̀ wa ni ká máa wá

È jẹ ká wẹ̀yìn wò, ká rántí

Ìgbà ìṣẹ̀dálẹ̀ àwọn Yorùbá

25

Ní Ọ̀yọ̀ Ìgbòho

Ìgbòhoo

Ibà Ìgbòho o

Ọ̀ba Mọ̀rọ̀ o ní Ọ̀yọ̀ Ìgbòho

Adáko:

Bí ọ̀gbọ̀n bá sọ̀nù

30

Ọ̀gbọ̀n la fi ní wa

Ọ̀rọ̀ rújú

Ìdàrú bẹ̀rẹ̀ oo

Léyìn ikú ọ̀ba Ajíbóyèdé

Ọ̀ba Abípa kò gbọ̀dọ̀ má gbẹ̀yìn ọ̀ba

Ọ̀yọ̀, Aláàfin

35

Kí ni ká ti pẹ̀yí sí o

A ó padà relé

A ó padà

- Bó dọtẹ sí Ọyọ Igbòho
 Ajọkọ: Àwọn Ọyọ ní látí pada sílẹẹ wọn àtijọ 40
 Níbi tí àfin baba nílá wọn tí wà
 Íjòyẹ ilú kọ
 Gbajúmọ ilú dojúrú
 Aláàfin pẹlú kò gbádùn
- Adáko: Má ẹ gbàgbé iléé 45
 Má ẹ gbàgbé ilé o
 Bí o bá jẹun yó tán o
 Má ẹ gbàgbé iléé
 Bí o bá powó nílá sóko
 Má ẹ gbàgbé ilé 50
 Má ẹ gbàgbé iléé
 Má ẹ gbàgbé ilé o
 Bí o bá kọlé nílá sóko
 Má ẹ gbàgbé ilé
 Ẹ jẹ ká relé 55
 Ilé là n lọ
 Agbẹ kan ọ rokoroko
 Kó gbàgbé ilé
 Ẹ jẹ ká relé
 Ilé là n lọ o 60
 Agbẹ kan ọ rokoroko
 Kó gbàgbé ilé.

Chorus: Hope you are well seated, our kindred
 We greet you
 Thanks for coming
 Hope you are well seated, our kindred
 We greet you 5
 Thanks for coming
 We are here with our play
 It's an interesting one
 We are here with our play
 It's an interesting one 10
 The report about it is not the same as seeing it
 It is the delicious soup
 That tastes very good
 The glory of our land is what we should seek
 The glory of our land is what we should seek
 The glory of our land is what we should seek
 When we are rich
 And wealthy
 The glory of our land is what we should seek 20
 We are saying it
 Time waits for no one
 The glory of our land is what we should seek
 Let's look back and remember
 The origin of the Yorùbá 25
 At Ọyọ́ Igbòho
 Igbòho
 Homage to you, Igbòho
 King Ghost-catcher of Ọyọ́ Igbòho

- Solo: When wisdom is lacking 30
 Wisdom is used in sorting things out
 There was disorder
 Trouble started
 After king Ajibóyè's death
 King Abípa must succeed the king of Ọyó
 Alááfin 35
 To what shall we compare this?
 We shall go back home
 We shall go back,
 Even in the face of any conspiracy to Ọyó
 Ígbòho 40
- Chorus: The Ọyó people must go back to their homestead
 From where their forefathers came
 The chiefs disagreed
 The eminent people in the town refused
 And the Alááfin was not happy
- Solo: Do not forget your home 45
 Do not forget your home
- Chorus: When you are satisfied
 Do not forget your home
 After amassing wealth outside your home
 Do not forget your home 50
 Do not forget your home
 Oh, do not forget your home
 After building a big house outside your home
 Do not forget your home
 Let's go home
 It's home we are heading for
 No farmer is so preoccupied with land cultivation

That he forgets to go home

Let's go home

It's home we're heading for

No farmer is so preoccupied with land cultivation

That he forgets to go home.

60

The first six lines of this song perform a phatic function in establishing the initial contact with the audience through greeting. This is in line with the Yorùbá culture in which such greetings are considered as indices of good manners. On the literary level this part of the song is comparable to the traditional ìbà (homage paying) in Yorùbá oral rhetoric. ìbà is, however, conceptually more ritualistic than the greeting we have in this example. Whereas Duro Ladipo is primarily concerned with arresting his audience's attention and interest in this case, the oral artist will, in a similar situation, also be concerned with enlisting the favours of both supernatural and natural powers (see Işola: 1976). In lines 7-13 the audience is assured that the play to be performed is an interesting one. The play is meta-symbolised both as honey and a delicious soup. Thus the spectator's interest is further being enlisted by raising their expectation about what the play is going to

lock like. Lines 14-23 of the song can be regarded as a general declaration of the thematic content of the play - the search for national glory. The fact that the Ọyọ history is to be used in explicating the theme is the subject of lines 24-29, where the particular era of Ọba Mọrọ's reign, in the setting of Ọyọ Igbòho is also given (see Johnson 1921: 164-167). Lines 30-45 give the general background to the play and briefly summarize the ensuing action. Abípa after succeeding his father Ajíbóyède as king of Ọyọ, insists on shifting his seat of government from Ọyọ Igbòho, their current settlement, to Ọyọ Ajàká from where their forefathers have come, despite stiff opposition from his chiefs. Duro Ladipo's stand in the conflict that ensues is signified in the remaining part of the song. The likely resolution of the conflict is therefore also indirectly indicated at this initial point. This part of the song is actually an advice to the audience on dedication to one's fatherland. It is a Yorùbá axiom which tells of the farmer who will always retire to the comfort of his home after a hard day's work. All these are enough signifiers of the fact that the conflict will be resolved in favour of the king.

The song has followed the general opening glee style of the Ogunde dramatic tradition as described by Adedeji (1979: 47-52) and Eḅun Clark (1979: 102-103). The song has a prologic relation to the play since it "establishes the setting of the play and indicates the course of the ensuing action" (Arnott 1959: 68-69). It is a successful prologue in that it does not give details of the plot in advance. It can be said that Duro Ladipo has from the onset started working on his spectators by successfully putting them in suspense as to the details of the plot.

The opening song of Ọsun is detached from the plot of the play in a way which that of Oba Mórò is not. Here is the text of the song which, unlike that of Oba Mórò, is totally sung in unison:

Ọṣogbo, ìlú aró
 Ọròkí lÀtáójà
 Àrè ò pẹtà o
 Àrè pẹtà, wọn gbà á o
 Ọṣun Ọṣogbo pẹlẹ́ o
 Tíméyìn mà rọra o
 Láàrọ màrà pẹlẹ́ o
 Ogidan ò máa rọra o
 Ọṣun Ọṣogbo ọlọmọyọyọ
 Ọlẹlẹrú àgbó

5

10

Agbàrá àgbo

LỌsun fi ñ wẹmọ rẹ

Kí dọkítà ó tó dé

Ọsogbo, the town of indigo dye

Atáọja is Oròkí

The stranger did not kill the civet-cat

The stranger killed the civet-cat and

they seized it (from him)

Greetings, Ọsun of Ọsogbo

5

Greetings, Timeyin

Greetings, Láàrọ

Ogidan, greetings

Ọsun Ọsogbo owner of several children

The spring of fluid medicinal concoction 10

The torrent of fluid medicinal concoction

Is what Ọsun uses in bathing her children

Before the arrival of (European-type) medical doctors.

Unlike the common tradition which Duro Ladipo has followed in the former example, the present song is very short, covering only thirteen lines in transcription as opposed to the sixty two lines of the former example. There is also no direct homage paying or general greetings in this example. The contact between the performers and their spectators, provided by the proxemic situation, is rightly taken for granted. Neither the theme of the play

nor the background information to the story-line is directly given as is done in Oba Mórò and as is generally practised. The song instead directly connects Òṣogbo to the Òṣun river goddess. A connection that has little plotal basis². Its basis is strongly extra-textual. The opening song of Osun does not qualify as a prologue in the Greek sense of the term and it is only on an indirect level of understanding that it can be taken as an ibà in the Yorùbá sense of the word. The only level on which the song is directly comparable to either the Greek prologue or the Yorùbá ibà is in its structural (initial) position in the play. It can, however, be taken as an indirect homage paying to the Òṣun river goddess and to Òṣogbo, the town where the goddess is today popularly worshipped. Whatever the case may be, the song in its primary significating capacity still serves the general function (the signified) of enlisting the audience's interest or whetting its appetite though more on a performative than on a literary level.

Since the song is the "national anthem" of Òṣogbo³, it is possible that Duro Ladipò wants the people of Òṣogbo to identify ^{themselves} with the play. One can, in fact, safely conclude that it is Duro Ladipò's nostalgic

sense that motivates his use of the song. The fact that the song is also generally used for opening the performances of other plays as *Biḡdun Duro Ladipḡ* revealed to us corroborates our conclusion. The song in this sense can also be seen as an indexical signifier of the local base of the theatre troupe.

Another common alternative variant of the opening glee also used by the group according to *Biḡdun Duro-Ladipḡ* is the employment of a fast rattling rhythm played on membranous instruments as the signifier of the beginning of the play. The audience is taken straight into the plot of the play after the instrumentation. It is a unique invention of *Duro Ladipḡ* which economically performs the same function of attracting the spectators' initial attention on a purely performative level.

3.2.1.2 The Closing Glee

The closing glee of *Aḡagun-ńlá* is the focus of our analysis in this section⁴. Three different songs are structured into it.

Aḡokḡ: Ẹ gbimḡ pḡ
 Ẹ jẹ́ ká gégi oró
 Ẹ gbimḡ pḡ

E jẹ ká gégi iyà
 E gbimò pò 5
 E jẹ ká gégi ọtẹ
 Igi oró
 Igi iyà
 O ti bú mi ná
 N ò ba seré 10
 O ti nà mi ná
 N ò ba rìn
 E gbimò pò
 E jẹ ká gégi ọtẹ
 Igi oró 15
 Igi iyà

Chorus: Join hands

Let's cut down the tree of wickedness
 Join hands
 Let's cut down the tree of punishment
 Join hands 5
 Let's cut down the tree of disunity
 The tree of wickedness
 The tree of punishment
 He has abused me
 I won't play with him 10
 He has beaten me
 I won't walk with him
 Join hands
 Let's cut down the tree of disunity
 The tree of wickedness 15
 The tree of punishment

2. **Lílé:** A ò mẹnì tí ó ẹ̀e o
 Ta ni yó ẹ̀e?
 Wí kí n gbọ́ 5
 Ta ni yó ẹ̀e?
 Mo bèrè wò
 Ta ni yó ẹ̀e?
 Sọ fún mi ná 10
 Bí a si wí
 O pé irọ́ ni mo pa

Egbè: A ò mẹnì tí ó ẹ̀e o
 A ò mẹnì tí ó ẹ̀e o
 A ò mẹnì tí ó ẹ̀e o 15
 A ò mẹnì tí ó ẹ̀e o
 Kọ̀rọ́ lo fojú sí
 Gbańgba lo fojú sí
 Kọ̀rọ́ lo fojú sí
 Gbańgba lo fojú sí 20
 Kátubọ̀tán wa kó dára
 Işẹ́ ọ̀wọ́ wa là ó jẹ
 Tó bá dī
 Lópin ayé
 Kọ̀rọ́ lo fojú sí oo 25

Solo: We don't know to whom it can happen
 We don't know to whom it can happen
 We don't know to whom it can happen

We don't know to whom it can happen
 To whom will it happen? 5
 Tell me
 To whom will it happen?
 I'm just asking you
 To whom will it happen?
 Just tell me 10
 And if we say it
 You'll take it as untrue

Chorus: We don't know to whom it can happen
 We don't know to whom it can happen
 We don't know to whom it can happen 15
 We don't know to whom it can happen
 Whether you hide your face in a corner
 Or you show up your face in the open
 Whether you hide your face in a corner
 Or you show up your face in the open 20
 May our end be pleasant
 It is from the fruits of our labour that
 we'll eat
 At the end
 Of our lives
 Whether or not you hide your face in a corner 25

3. Erè ká relé mi o
 Erè ká relé mi o
 Èèé ajé ọjà Ifẹ
 Erè ká relé mi ò

May profit follow me home
 May profit follow me home
 Oh wealth from Ifẹ market
 May profit follow me home

The first song is the actual concluding song which draws out the moral of the plot in the manner of the general closing glee tradition⁵. The meta-symbol of the tree of punishment that should be cut down [adopted from the saying "ẹ má gbíngí oró, nítorí ẹyìn ọlẹ" ("do not sow the seed of wickedness because of tomorrow")], which is in fact iconised during performance, is used in the song as a signifier of the enmity that develops between the household of both Olúgbón and Arẹsà on the one hand and that of Oníkòyí on the other. The members of Olúgbón and Arẹsà's household decide to avenge the untimely death of their fathers and leaders on Oníkòyí, a colleague of their fathers suspected of foul play. The song is actually led by Ajagun-ńlá, the generalissimo who tries without much success to resolve the situation amicably. One can therefore say that the song is being addressed to the warring parties in the play. But since the three war-lords (and even Ajagun-ńlá) are legendric progenitors

of some Yorùbá lineages, one can also safely say that Duro Ladipo is both directly and indirectly addressing the song to his audience. Such a semiotic shift in the object of address, the addressee, is possible because the Yorùbá form the primary audience of the play. They can therefore be meto-symbolically substituted for the primary addressee.

The connection or relation of the second song to the plotal trend is not as clear as that of the first one. It is, perhaps, primarily addressed to the audience, hence the rhetorical questions in the lead part. If the deictic pronoun 'ó' ('it') of the quadri-repeated lines at the beginning of both the lead and chorus' parts is seen as referring to various human problems in general, the second song can be indirectly related to the first song and therefore the plotal trend of the play. One can say that Duro Ladipo is probably also advising his audience to help others because we do not know who it is that will need such a help⁶, for such a help matters in the next universe.

This third song is culled from Mọ̀rèmi as already mentioned above (in 3.1.2.0). It is also used as closing

song for other plays. In the context of Morèmi from where it is adopted, the prayerful and other significations of the song are restricted. It is used in creating the market scene atmosphere where traders pray for abundant blessing, so that they will make enough profit at the end of the day. The concept of the Yorùbá people as expressed in the following axiom

Ayé lojà

Ọrun nilé

The world is a market place

Heaven is the home

makes the song relevant as a concluding prayer to the performance of any play. The signification of profit in this context takes a meta-symbolic dimension. It is to be seen as a signifier of offsprings and a peaceful life in the after-world. Childlessness among the Yorùbá is considered an unfortunate thing (see analysis of Morèmi's character in Chapter Five). Thus we can see that the third song relates directly to the second one on a philosophical level.

Our analysis of both opening and closing glees above

proves that Duro Ladipo is aware of, and at least sometimes uses, the performing format of the Ogunde dramatic tradition. One tends to conclude that it is the general influence on Duro Ladipo of occidental performing convention where the period for dramatic performances is strictly limited that makes him tend to do away with the two glees in some of his performances. As the examples analysed above have probably implicitly shown, when the two glees are used they are most of the time brief and probably not as interesting as those of Ogunde, Kola Ogunmola and Oyin Adejobi. Duro Ladipo could probably not afford to stop using the two glees completely because they have become almost a standard by which the popular audience judge successful performances (Jeyifo 1981: 67-68). When he, however, performs for a literate audience, as on a university stage, or overseas, he does not often use the two glees.

3.2.2 Dialogised Neo-traditional Songs⁷

The use of dialogised neo-traditional songs is more pronounced in Oba Mórò, Oba Kò So and Obátálá than in the other five plays. Thus the three plays can be said to belong more to the operatic tradition than the others.

Two types of dialogised neo-traditional songs are codified in these plays. In the first type the thread of thought in conversation is continuous while in the second there is a musical intrusion into the dialogue that tends to make it non-continuous. Examples of continuous song dialogue is more prominent in Oba Kò So than in the other two plays.

Timi àti

Gbònkáà: Ogun yá wa o, a fẹ̀ lọ jagun
 Ogun yá wa o, a fẹ̀ lọ jagun
 Fàṣẹ̀ si, àní ko fàṣẹ̀ si
 Fàṣẹ̀ si, àní ko fàṣẹ̀ si
 Ogun yá wa o a fẹ̀ lọ jagun

Ṣàngó:

Kál
 È dákun o!
 È má lọ jagun!

Timi àti

Gbònkáà Bí a kò bá lè jagun, Ọ̀yọ́ á tú o!

Bí a kò bá lè jagun, Ọ̀yọ́ á tú o!

...

A ó dìtẹ̀ mọ́ ọ, Aláàfin Ṣàngó!

Ogun, yá wa o, a fẹ̀ lọ jagun!

(1970: 12)

Timì and

Gbònkáà:

We are ready for war, we want to go to battle
 We are ready for war, we want to go to battle
 Authorise it, we ask you to authorise it!
 Authorise it, we ask you to authorise it!
 We are ready for war, we want to go to battle!

Sàngó:

Never!
 Oh please
 Do not go to war!

Timì and

Gbònkáà:

If we cannot fight, Òyó will be depopulated!
 If we cannot fight, Òyó will be depopulated!
 ...
 We shall rebel against you, Aláàfin Sàngó!
 We are ready for war, we want to go to battle!

(1970: 78)

Generally speaking, it should be noted, the musico-poetic dialogues in Oba Kò So change with the differences in situation. One can, however, say that the musico-poetic lines are not long in general because of the charged atmosphere. There is usually no room for very long renditions in this type of situation as illustrated in the last example above.

Examples of non-continuous or, more properly, broken dialogues are many in Oba Mórò and Obàtálá. The following

example from Ọbàtálá will suffice in illustrating the pattern.

Ọbàtálá:

Torí pé Olódùmarè Ọba ló fún mi láṣẹ

Ó ní kí n bù ọ

Ó ní kí n bù ọ

Ká máa gbinsu

Ká máa gbìngbàdo

Ká máa gbìngèdè

Kébi ó mọ pẹ̀nikọ̀ọ̀kan lórílẹ̀ èdè ayé

Egbè: Ilẹ̀ oo

Ilẹ̀ oo

Ilẹ̀ oo

Ilẹ̀: Tí o bá bù mí oo

Kí ni kí n ẹ?

Egbè: Ilẹ̀ oo

Ilẹ̀ oo

Ilẹ̀ oo

Ọbàtálá: Tí mo bá bù ọ

O ò lè ẹ ǹkankan

Ọbàtálá: Because, it is Olódùmarè, the king, that
has authorised me

He says I should take a part of you

He says I should take part of you

That we should be planting yams

That we should be planting maize

That we should be planting bananas
So that none would be hungry all over
the world.

Chorus: Oh Ilẹ̀ (Ground/Soil)
(from back stage): Oh Ilẹ̀
Oh Ilẹ̀

Ilẹ̀: .If you take a part of me
What should I do?
Oh Ilẹ̀
Oh Ilẹ̀
Oh Ilẹ̀

Obàtálá: If I take a part of you
You cannot do anything

Though the primary signification of the choric intrusion into the conversation between Obàtálá and Ilẹ̀ tends to be musical, a secondary structural signification is possible. The chorus part no doubt foregrounds the pitiable position of Ilẹ̀. This is why Ilẹ̀ rather than Obàtálá is made the focus of the chorus. The lines assigned to Obàtálá are chanted in the èsà egúngún mode while those of Ilẹ̀ and the chorus are sung in the neo-traditional musico-poetic style. The sympathy of the chorus with Ilẹ̀ is therefore also musically related in that they are both in the neo-traditional mode. The common plight of the two is therefore

musically contrasted to that of Ọbàtálá.

Though Euba (1970: 101) has noted that the underlying principle that determines the choice of "musical idiom" is the nature of the text (sub-text), we want to note that the capability of the performer rendering the part is the primary factor that even decides the choice of the text. Abidoje Ojo, who is a professional masquerader, well versed in èsà chanting, acted the part of Ọbàtálá while Ilẹ̀ is acted by Lere Paimọ who does not chant in any traditional mode but can compose and sing in the neo-traditional style. The different areas of performance talents of these two artists must have contributed immensely in determining the nature of the blending illustrated above.

3.2.3 Non-dialogised Neo-traditional Songs

The use of non-dialogised neo-traditional songs is not as common as that of the dialogised ones. Non-dialogised neo-traditional songs are generally used, like the traditional musico-poetic renditions and the dialogised neo-traditional songs treated in 3.2.2, in creating atmosphere and in the heightening of situation.

We should at this juncture point out the difference in the two functions (signifieds) which are, in fact, related. When such a song is used in creating an atmosphere it is seen as an integral part of the atmosphere. But when it is used in hieghtening or foregrounding an atmosphere, the atmosphere is already created before the song comes in at the climax of the situation to reflect on it.

Though we have done an analysis of the "Èrè ká relé mi" ("Profit follow me home") song in its closing glee context (in 3.2.1.2) where it is said that the song is culled from Morèmi's plot, it is pertinent to consider the full plotal signification of the song at this point. The song, rendered in unison, is used along with other traditional songs to create a festive atmosphere as the newly installed iyálóde-ojà (market women leader), Morèmi is welcomed to the market during what we term an extension of the iwíyè (installation) ceremony. The theme of the song namely, that the market should be profit bearing, is an anticipatory index of Morèmi's general patriotic disposition in her new capacity as the leader of the Ifè market women. The song is, however, primarily used as an advertising poem (ipolówó

ojà) and it is in this signification that it is most relevant to the market scene. The advertising signification is, however, more pronounced in the solo part than in the chorus.

Eyí tá a wí fọgbọ lọgbọ n gbọ
 Eyí tá a wí fọgbà lọgbà n gbà
 Obìnrin tó dára ni ẹwà ọkọ rẹ
 Ẹ wá bá mi ra aṣọ o gbogbo ojà
 Kéré bà gbogbo wa relé o

(1971: 5)

It is that which the ogbó is told that ogbó hears
 It is that which the ogbà is told that ogbà accepts
 A good woman is the beauty of her husband
 Come and buy cloths from me, people of the market
 May profit follow all of us home.

The advertisement starts with assertive statements and ends with the wish that people should patronise her (as is characteristic of Yorùbá incantations). It is in the final line in which she extends the prayer to every seller in the market that further confirms our earlier observation about Mọrẹmi's selflessness.

In Ajagun-ńlá, the song "Awarawa ní mọbà" ("Between us there is due respect") is initially used to create the

solemn ritual atmosphere needed for the oath-taking by Ajagun-ńlá, Olúgbón Oníkòyí and Arẹ̀sà.

Ajagun-ńlá: Olúgbón ó dọwọ rẹ
Arẹ̀sà ó dọwọ rẹ
Oníkòyí ó dọwọ rẹ

Gbogbo wọ̀n: Awarawa ní mọ̀bà
Awarawa ní mọ̀bà o
È jẹ́ ká sètò ara wa.

Ajagun-ńlá: Olúgbón it's left to you
Arẹ̀sà it's left to you
Oníkòyí it's left to you

All of them: Between us there is due respect
Between us there is due respect
Let's get organized

The spatial and kinetic arrangement of the scene shows the four war-lords gathering together and holding a short rodlike sacred object with their left hands. In subsequent codification of the song along the plot line, the accompanying ritual action is absent. The song is therefore seen as an indexical reminder of the ritual bond between the four of them.

An example of the use of neo-traditional song that heightens a situation is found in Oba Ko So when Şàngó

bursts into lamentation after killing his people out of anger.

Şangó: Gbà mí, oríì mi o!
 Oríì mi gbà mí o e!
 Orí a bá wáyé ló n şeni bó ti wù ú
 Orí mi gbà mí o e!
 Àà! mo ti pa ayáà mi
 Mo ti pa ìjòyè mi
 Bí bàtá bá n ró àrójù
 Yíya ní í kẹyìn rẹ
 Ọtẹ ìlú Ọyọ mà wá pọjù
 Igbẹyìn ayé fẹẹ dé bá mi o, èmi Şangó
 (1970: 54)

Şangó: Save me, Oh my head!
 O my head, save me!
 The head which one follows into the world,
 treats one as it likes.
 O my head save me!
 Ah! I have killed my wives!
 I have killed my chiefs!
 If the bata drum is made to sound too high
 It is sure to tear in the end
 The plots in Ọyọ are becoming too much.
 My end is getting near, I, Şangó
 (1970: 124)

This song is used to reflect on, and draw the audience's attention to, the distressing effect of the disastrous

event on Şàngó and also to indicate that the resolution point, the end of Şango, is nigh. The depression of Oya after Şàngó's death is also presented in a similar song (1970: 58). In the plays the neo-traditional songs are used more to create atmosphere than to heighten situations.

3.3.0 OTHER MUSICO-POETIC STRUCTURES

The musico-poetic structures to be treated here include some features of spoken dialogue, exclamatory call and response, and instrumentation and dance. The first two belong to the verbal or more properly literary aspect of the play while the last one belong to the theatrical aspect.

3.3.1 Some Features of Spoken Dialogue

Anybody accustomed to dialoguing in western theatre cannot but consider as "rowdy" the spoken dialogues of most performances of plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition in general. This "rowdiness" arises from the attempt of more than two performers to speak their different lines simultaneously. The improvisational style of dialoguing in the tradition allows for overlapping of speeches and incomplete statements during conversation. This is the

reason for the "rowdiness". An example of such a rowdy scene can be taken from the royal feast scenes in *Oṣun* where about four members of the *Ọyómèsi*, who are the guests, are trying all at the same time to commend the cooking of the hostesses, who have prepared the dishes. The hostesses' acknowledgement of the compliments overlaps with the commendation from the guests. At the background of this hustle and bustle is the royal poet, chanting the praises of the guests. The rowdiness in this dramatic situation, however, looks appropriate. It seems as if the situation of this kind of overlap generally allows for it. It may therefore go unnoticed in live performance and especially with the popular audience. But on the radio, television phono-disc and even when listening to the recorded performances, the "rowdiness" usually becomes more pronounced and perhaps less acceptable.

Incomplete statements may arise from the overlapping of speeches as seen in the following attempt to transcribe an overlapping conversation from the televised version of Mọ̀rèmi.

Ìjòyè kejì: Ara un tá a wí nù un, ẹnì bímọ
 ọ̀ràn ní í pọ̀n ọ̀n

- Ijòyè kẹta: Eni bímọ ọràn ni ó pọn ọn o
- Ijòyè kejì: Eléyíí wá kọjá gbogbo un tá a wí tẹlẹ
- Ijòyè kẹlíní: Kò wá dọrọ kábiyèsí nìkan, ó wá kàn wá gan-an.
- Ijòyè kerin: Kò lè mọ rí bẹẹ ...
- Ijòyè karùnun: Kò lè mọ rí bẹẹ ... bó o lá á ti ẹ se é?
- Ijòyè kẹrin: Kò lè mọ rí bẹẹ, ìjà gbogbo wa ni Mọrẹmi n gbèe.

Second Chief: That is part of what we were saying. It is the person who gives birth to a problem child that will carry it on her back.

Third Chief: It is the person who gives birth to a problem child that will carry it on her back.

Second Chief: The situation is more serious than we thought it would be.

First Chief: It's no more Kábiyèsí's problem alone we're all deeply involved.

Fourth Chief: It can't but be like that ...

Fifth Chief: It can't but be like that ... how do we do it?

Fourth Chief: It can't but be like that, it's on our behalf that Mọrẹmi is fighting.

The pauses and overlapping in the dialogue are indicated by the repetition of lines and broken lines. The fourth chief cannot complete his lines because of the sarcastic interruption by the fifth chief; but the fourth chief completes it later as our transcription shows. It should, however, be noted that this transcription does not capture the rowdiness of the dialogue in full. There are other instances where the utterances are left uncompleted. In Béyíí Ọ Se, for example, when prince Aólẹ̀ is arraigned before Baálẹ̀ Apòmù for slave trading he proudly addresses the Baálẹ̀.

Baálẹ̀ Apòmù
 Kílọ̀ fún àwọn jíatijàti wọnyí
 Pé ...
 Ọ ọ̀ mọ̀ mí ní?

Baálẹ̀ Apòmù
 Warn these foolish ones
 That ...
 Don't you know me?

This type of speech is common in the plays. They are to be seen as indices of non-illusionistic presentation⁸. Illusionistic presentations are generally tidier.

3.3.2 Exclamatory Call and Response

In addition to the use of exclamatory call and response that precedes war songs discussed in 3.1.1.3 above, Duro Ladipo is fond of using the exclamatory call and response pattern in ushering most if not all, of his major characters onto the stage. Şangó in Oba Kò So exclamatorily calls on Timì and Gbònkáà with "Timì oooooo!" (1970: 4, 11, 15, 35 and 44) and "Gbònkáà oooooo!" (1970: 5:12, 24 and 32). The usual response to such calls even in the extra-text is "òòòòò!" ("Yees!"). Such calls and responses are found in Ajagun-ńlá where Ajagun-ńlá calls on the babaláwo (diviner). This type of call and response which is a common extra-textual experience is musicalized in Duro Ladipo's plays where it is usually accompanied by a rattling instrumentation.

There is also a ritual version of the exclamatory call and response in the plays. In such examples the call of the addressee's name is usually preceded by invocational poetry. The response is also sometimes delayed till the third or seventh call as the case may be⁹. In Ajagun-ńlá for example, Oníkòyí, who has disappeared under a fig tree is called thrice before he answers at the third call.

Ajagun-ńlá ...

Oníkòyí òòòòòò

Ó mò dẹ̀ẹ̀kejì

Bí mò bá pè ọ lẹ̀ẹ̀kẹ̀ta

Tọ̀ọ̀ jẹ̀ mí

O dewúré jẹ̀léjẹ̀lé

O dàgùntàn jẹ̀mọ̀jẹ̀mọ̀

Aní o daláùmù lẹ̀gbẹ̀ẹ̀ ọ̀gírì

Oníkòyí òòòòòò

Ohun Oníkòyí: Óóòòòò

Ajagun-ńlá: Oníkòyí òòòòòò

It's now the second time

If I call you the third time

And you don't answer me

You then become a goat eating in
the house

You then become a sheep that eats
palm leaves

You then become a lizard that eats
by the wall of the house

Oníkòyí òòòòòò

Oníkòyí's voice: Óóòòòò.

There is usually no accompanying instrumentation in the invocatory part and the call, but the response is usually accompanied by the fast rattling rhythm. Other examples of such ritualized invocatory call and response pattern

can be found in Oba Kò So where Gbònkáà invokes and calls Tímì at Èdẹ (1970: 27) and in the witches' scene where Gbònkáà invokes and calls on the witches (1970: 38-43). The invocation and call of Èsìnminrìn by Mọrẹmì also falls within this category (1971: 18 and 48). It should be mentioned that the ritual invocatory call and response is adopted and adapted from the extra-textual resurrecting ritual practice used in the ushering of the ancestor back to the world in the masquerade cult¹⁰.

3.3.3 Instrumentation and Dance

Prominent among the musical instruments and dance codified in the performance of the mythico-historical plays are dùndún and bàtá. Agogo (gongs) and sẹkẹrẹ (gourd rattles) are usually added to the dùndún ensemble. Other instruments used include gbèdu, (an upright drum), tòròmágbè (gourd flute) and èkùtù (bamboo flute). Instrumentation and dance are inseparable parts of the Yorùbá musico-poetic art (See Olatunji 1975b: 120). They therefore share in the realization of different textual significations of the verbal musico-poetic art such as the creation of necessary dramatic atmosphere and characterization.

We have already discussed the rattling instrumentation that usually accompanies the exclamatory call and response (in 3.3.2 above). In the context of ushering onto the stage of war lords and other powerful characters such as Şàngó, Gbònkáà and Tìmì in Oba Kò So and the four war lords in Ajagun-ńlá, the rattling sound usually graduates into the type used for the eégún jàndùkú, (the hooligan masquerade) or the climax of any empathizing process in any ritual festival among the Yorùbá. The accompanying movements in such situations agree with the various contexts. In the case of Ajagun-ńlá he is held by his war lords, in the manner which empathisers are usually held extra-textually, to prevent him from breaking loose. Şàngó after being ushered onto the stage starts moving restlessly about the stage as he waves his osé and ìrùkèrè and says "ẹ ẹun" ("Thank you") to the eulogy being chanted for him like an extra-textual elégún would do. Gbònkáà and Tìmì on the other hand dance vigorously to bátá instrumentation after being ushered in respectively. The civil lords such as the Ọyómèsì in Oba Kò So, Oba Mọrò and Ọsun, and Báalẹ Apòmù and the chiefs in Beyíí ọ ẹ and Mọrèmi respectively dance gracefully to the wórò, slow rhythm of the dùndún and sèkèrè ensemble.

Thus there is a consistent binary opposition in the musical iconization of both the war lords and the civil lords. The empathizing iconization of Ṣàngó and Ajagun-ńlá also helps in pointing to their òrìṣà personalities and distinguishes them from the two groups of lords to which they are at the same time closely related.

Except in certain few cases, the palace musical contexts are usually iconised with the dùndún instrumentation and dance. Such instrumentation is found in Obàtálá, Beyí ò Se, Obá Wàjà, and Oba Mórò. Even in the Ṣàngó contexts of Oba Ko So and Oṣun where the bàtá instrumentation is predominant, dùndún instrumentation and dance still feature. Another partial exception is the Ọ̀ni palace context of Mọ̀rẹ̀mi and Beyí ò Se where the ìgbìn instrumentation is foregrounded. In the two exceptions the appropriate extra-textual instrumentation has been iconised in the texts. The bàtá drum and dance are extra-textually attached to the Ṣàngó cult just as the ìgbìn one is attached to certain Ifẹ̀ traditions as reflected in the Olúfẹ̀ lineage poetry line, "Ọ̀mọ̀ alugbìn-jó-fóòṣa" ('Offspring of One-who plays-ìgbìn-for-the-divinity-to-dance.) (See

Babalola 1967: 19-20 and Duro Ladipo 1971: 2).

The talking power of some Yorùbá musical instruments is also effectively tapped in Duro Ladipo's plays under analysis. The text of the song is sometimes simulated on the iyá ilù, (master drum), of the dùndún set simultaneously with singing. In Oba Kò So, the iyá ilù and tòròmágbè are made to repeat the incantations intoned by Tìmì and Gbònkáà on their different approaches to Èdè. This dramatic use of the musico-poetic style helps in the emphatic iconization of the ritual efficacy of both incantations and the characters of the chanters. Because such a style is more commonly known of the dùndún and sèkèrè music¹¹ than of the tòròmágbè and because of the general plotal trend in the play, where Gbònkáà is presented as more powerful than Tìmì, one tends to regard the tòròmágbè adaptation as generally more ritualistically effective. The use of the talking power of ekùtù in Ajagun-ńlá is more semiotically interesting than the ones just discussed. The ekùtù is attached to the character of Ajagun-ńlá as the iconization of the supernatural power that usually forewarns him about impending danger. Ajagun-ńlá is, for example, forewarned on the flute not to drink the poisoned water

presented to him and his colleagues by his wife on their return from the battle field.

Ajagun-ńlá

O ò gbọdọ mu ún

O ò gbọdọ mu ún o

O ò gbọdọ mu omi un

Ajagun-ńlá

You mustn't drink it

You mustn't drink it

You mustn't drink that water.

The fact that the èkùtù is played from the invisible backstage throughout the play gives some credibility to this semiotic interpretation.

Two types of group dancing can be identified in the plays. There is the unison simultaneous dancing of the same movements by two or more performers as in the case of the four royal wives in the opening scene of Oba Kò So and that of the war dance by the four Ọyómèsi chiefs in protest against Şàngó's initial refusal to caution his overbearing war lords in the televised performance. There is also the non-unison dance movement where each performer iconises the instrumentational rhythm in

different dancing steps. Examples of this are found in the scene in Oba Kò So of the installation of Timì at Ede the market scene in Morèmi where the market women celebrate Morèmi's iwúyè (installation) and in most palace contexts in the other plays. The non-unison group dancing seems more appropriate than a unison one in the festive context of the above examples. Though such singing in unison, in the extra-textual palace context is alien to the Yorùbá it is considered a good dramatic adaptation in the other two examples from Oba Kò So.

Whereas there can be singing and instrumentation in non-felicitous situations, it is unusual to have dancing in such a context. Thus we may take dance as a primary general indexical signifier of a peaceful and a happy situation in the texts¹². Most of the dances in the palace contexts already referred to fall within this analysis. It is, for example, because the dancing and general merry-making of the chiefs fall out of this significating context that Morèmi rebukes them harshly.

...

È n jó, è n yò, è n jẹ, è n mu
Ogun ti kó kete Ifẹ

...

Ọgèdè mbàjé ẹ ní ńpón:

Aiye ńt'ojú nyin bàjé, ẹ ni ńdara,
(1971: 12)

You are dancing, you are eating and drinking
Wars have taken all Ifè into captivity

...

The banana is getting rotten, you say
it's ripening

The world is in ruins in your time but
you say it's getting better.

In Bèyíí ò Se, Baálẹ̀ Apòmù will always dance dexteriously to the dùndún and sèkèrè music when there is no trouble. The dancing and meriment, however, stop when trouble starts. Tìmì's dance at the end of the first act in Oba Kò So is semiotically interesting. The vigorous bàtá dance primarily serves as an indexical signifier of Tìmì's joyful state of mind when he is given a second chance of proving his military prowess after being defeated in a first encounter with Gbònkáà. The dancing is, however, so vigorous that the palace inmates present become afraid and evacuate the floor for him. The Yorùbá believe that over-excitement kills. One can therefore conclude that Tìmì's over-excitement is an anticipatory

index of his failure during the ensuing second encounter.

3.4.0

CONCLUDING NOTES

We have considered the codification of the Yorùbá musico-poetic structures in Duro Ladipo's plays under study. We have dwelt on the correlation between content, form and context of many of the musico-poetic structures. The few cases where there seems to be little or no correlation, it has been argued, should not be seen as faulty codifications. The oral and/or popular nature of the source materials that form the sub-texts of the texts under analysis can be said to have allowed for the seemingly incongruous features (see 3.1.2 and 3.3.1).

Duro Ladipo has no doubt exploited the musico-poetic code in facilitating a cognitive understanding of situations and characters. This is apart from the fact that the musico-poetic patterns are in themselves interesting and therefore contribute to the general success of the plays.

CHAPTER THREE

NOTES

1. The phono-semantic chorus lines generally do not have componential meaning of their own. Their signification therefore tends to be primarily musical. But a secondary signification may not be impossible at times. The example that readily comes to mind is the adaptative use of the folktale refrain "Alugbinrin" in Morèmi during Dìbíá's final lamentation. If the refrain is seen as a phono-semantic nominal derived from a+lù+gbinrin > alugbinrin (one who beats the drum/gong to give the sonorous sound), then it can be seen as referring to Dìbíá, who renders the lead part and has always advised the Igbò king so that things are lively and smooth for him like the sonorous gbinrin sound until the moment the king disregards his advice. The fact that the refrain is echoed from the back stage during performance gives the analysis some credibility. Had it been Dìbíá singing to commend himself as a good adviser one would probably have seen such a reference as empty self-exaltation in the light of the general context of the play.
2. The play is, for example, set in Òyó town and not Òṣogbo.
3. This information was given by Bìṣdún Duro-Ladipo and Adeṣina Adetoyi during the interviews I held with each of them.

4. The following is the text of the traditional éégún aláré closing song adopted for Beyif ò Se but which is not considered here.

Awá n lọ
 Ó dígba ó se
 Ká má fikú yara wa
 Ká má fàrùn yara wa

We are going
 It's good-bye for now
 May we never part in death
 May we never part in sickness

5. Alo àpagbè is a common example of traditional literary performance that has a similar concluding structure.

6. The following are two proverbs that are relevant in this context.

i) Bí a bá sọkò lọjà ará ilé ẹnì ní í bá
 (When one throws a stone in the market
 it usually hits ones kinsman)

ii) Ẹni tí ó bá gbèèbù ikà; orí ọmọ rẹ̀ ni yóó hù lé.
 He who plants seedlings of wickedness; it will
 grow on his children.

7. Though song dialogues can be seen within the musical structural perspective of lead and response, it should be noted that not all such instances are conversational.

Only cases where there is conversational thread are treated here.

8. It should, however, be noted at this juncture that such free comments and interpolation are not uncommon in Yorùbá indigenous traditional performances. Since the dramatic performances under consideration are not restricted by written texts that should be followed word for word, there is the tendency that the residual orality of the people's literature finds its way into the dramatic performances.
9. A more dramatic version of the call and response is adapted for Ajagun-ńlá. Ajagun-ńlá is ushered in by the first type of exclamatory call and response discussed above. On entering, the following exclamatory call and response ensues between Ajagun-ńlá and his three lieutenants.

Ajagun-ńlá: Olúgbọ̀n ọ̀!

Olúgbọ̀n/Arẹ̀sà/Oníkòyí: Ajagun-ńlá ọ̀!

Ajagun-ńlá: Arẹ̀sà ọ̀!

Olúgbọ̀n/Arẹ̀sà/Oníkòyí: Ajagun-ńlá ọ̀!

Ajagun-ńlá: Oníkòyí ọ̀!

Olúgbọ̀n/Arẹ̀sà/Oníkòyí Ajagun-ńlá ọ̀!

The normal response as already discussed is "òóòò". It is not common for the person being called to respond by calling his caller back. This is why

the innovation is seen as a dynamic dramatic one that foregrounds the toughness and warlikeness of the four characters.

10. The resurrecting ritual can be seen as a dramatic piece where a masked impersonator of the ancestor emerges from an inner chamber or part of the egúngún sacred grove (called ìgbó ìgbàlẹ̀) after being called seven times. He answers with "òóòò" on a modulated guttural voice peculiar to masquerades. The ground is beaten with a whip on each call and there are lots of incantatory invocation and praise poetry (see Johnson 1921: 29-31).
11. Ayányẹmí Atokowágbowónlẹ̀ and his dùndún and sẹkerẹ̀ band have popularised this style (see Fatokun 1984).
12. There is, however, an example of meto-symbolic dancing that signifies the Ọyómẹsì's protest against Ẹ̀ngó's initial refusal to caution his overbearing war lords in the televised version of Oba Kò So. In the dance (which can be termed a war dance) a forward movement is done by each pair of the four chiefs involved, facing each other to make a round about turn and start all over again. The crossing of their chieftaincy swords to produce a clanging sound, as they dance past each other serves as the climax motif of each dance sequence. The ruffling of the flowing agbádá and all other aspects of the dance combine together in the memorable codification of

the scene. That Şàngó drives them out of the palace angrily by spitting fire at them confirms the meto-
symbolic analysis of the dance as a signifier of
the Ọyómèsi's protest.

CHAPTER FOUR

PLOTAL CODE

4.0 INTRODUCTORY NOTES

In this chapter, we hope to consider the linear structure and signification of the setting (as a major sub-plotal codification) and the events (as the main plotal codification). Though treated separately, the two codifications are inseparable in performance. The separation here is only for analytical ease.

When we talk of plot, the linear or syntagmatic structure of the narrative text is usually what we have in mind. We should, however, remember that the componental units of the syntagmatic structure are selected on certain aesthetic principles from the paradigmatic axis (see Jakobson 1960: 358). A comprehensive signification of each of the units combined on the syntagmatic axis cannot therefore be achieved without relating them to their possible alternatives on the paradigmatic axis from which they are selected. The sequential structure of episodes, events, or actions is usually the most emphasised in the discussion of plots in general (see Forster 1927: 87; Abrams 1981: 137; Boulton 1960: 20ff; Dawson 1970: 79; Crow 1983: 38

etc.). We are therefore, no doubt in the area of Barthes' (1970: 19) proairetic and hermeneutic codes¹ in the discussion of plot. "Thought", "theme" or "general meaning" and "impression" or "the emotion of the audience" are also sometimes considered along the linear progression of the plot with events in aesthetic narration (see Styan 1960: 64ff, 121ff; Crane 1967: 141-145; and Friedman 1967: 145-166). The structuralists (from their formalistic to the semiotic phase) also recognise the linear structure of the spatio-temporal aspect of the narrative text as part of the plotal structures, that is, the (scenery) setting and time of both the dramatic world and extra-dramatic world in which the audience/text relationship is contracted.

From the structuralist perspective, the plot is an organic whole made up of the elements listed above and others which cannot be practically severed from the whole. The breaking of the whole into parts is usually done theoretically for analytical and pedagogic convenience (Scholes 1982: 85). Thus it is realised that one cannot discuss a part of the whole, even in the analytical and pedagogical processes, in isolation without making references to other parts of that whole.

Abrams (1981: 137), who defines plot as the structures of the actions in dramatic or narrative work, goes on to say that,

Plot and character are interdependent critical concepts - as Henry James has said, "What is character but the determination of incident? What is incident but illustration of character?"

Plot, character, and the verbal aspects of the narrative work are undoubtedly fused together.

Structuralists (Propp, Souriau, Dundes, Greimas, Todorov, Levi-Strauss and Ogunpolu) are usually interested in determining the general linear model of events common to many, if not all, narratives. This exercise borders on determining the "grammar", or in Saussure's terminology "langue", of plots of which a particular plot will be an instance, its "performance" or "parole" in Chomskian and Saussurean terms respectively². Such an exercise usually yields a symbolic linear notation system, considered as a similitude of the linear sequence of the plotal events. Such generated linear notations are according to Scholes (1982: 88), governed

by "no explicit system" and "have spurious exactitude"³. The notation is not in itself explanatory and still needs to be expatiated upon through the use of key notes and further discussion; if the paradigmatic dimension is to be considered along with it. The notation, it is therefore realised, is just a means to an end. This, at least, is the experience of the methodology (Propp and Dundes' brand of it) as applied to certain Yorùbá folktales by Ogúnpoḷù (1978 and 1979). In the present work, since the paradigmatic dimension is not going to be relegated to the background because of our semiotic orientation, the methodology is avoided, especially in our treatment of events. The breaking down of the dramatic narrative text into its componental units is, however, complex, problematic and therefore controversial⁴. For convenience, therefore, we prefer to talk, as already indicated (0.1), of the significant events within the much more elastic Aristotelian linear frame, Beginning-Middle-End. It is only in our consideration of the sequence of settings, where the componental numbers of settings are considerably fewer than in the linear structure of events, that the methodology is adapted.

Of relevance to our analysis is the crucial theoretical distinction usually made between plot and story which the Russian formalist, Tomashevskij (1965: 66-78) clearly explains in his work titled "Thematics" (also see Forster 1927: 44, 87; Elam 1980: 119-120 and Crow 1983: 38, 45-51 etc.). The story, called "fabula" by Russian formalists, is said to be the chronological sequence of events which differs from the sequential structure of the plot called "sujzet". The events in the dramatic plot are lineated to achieve certain general aesthetic and dramatic effects. The plotal arrangement needs not be consequential or chronological, and it can include events that are not crucial to the plotal development in as much as such events are serving certain aesthetic or dramatic ends. Such events are usually eliminated from the chronological sequence of the story. We should therefore note that whereas causality is the primary factor in the lineation of the story sequentiality is the primary factor in plotal lineation.⁵ Forster's theoretical view that the story is a lower "organism" on which the higher "organism" of plot, is based is also relevant to our study. Related to Forster's position is Elam's (1980: 119) view that

the story has to be extracted from the plot by the audience before a full realization of the plotal essence can be grasped. But from the artist's (plotal creator's) perspective, we wish to add, it is a matter of total re-organization of the story-line for intended effects in order to yield the plotal-line. Some of the devices usually employed in plotal construction, but which are not necessary in the story of, say the historical narrative text, include suspense, dramatic irony, surprise, flash back, omissions and off-stage events (see Elam 1980: 119).

In the case of Duro Ladipo, the mythico-historical narratives, some taken from historical texts and others from oral accounts, are regarded as the story, the "lower organism" on which the plot of the plays, the "higher organism", is based. This stand should theoretically help us in determining Duro Ladipo's plotal adaptative competence. But the elusive and multiple nature of the oral materials that form most of his plotal sources frustrates a detailed investigation at this level. We shall, however, explore this aspect of plotal signification within the possible limits the situation allows for.

Related to the distinction between story and plot is Seagre's (1981: 100-101) relevant observation that the dramatic plot is often "plurilineal" while that of the non-dramatic plot is often "mono-lineal". This situation is, as Seagre has noted, conditioned by the time limit (two to three hours) to which the exposition of dramatic plots to its audience in performance is conventionally restricted. This makes the dramatist emphasize only the important events so that other events are at least relegated to the background if not eliminated. This partly accounts for the use of offstage actions reported by other characters, and interlacing of events.

In conclusion we shall examine, in our analysis of the plotal code, the sequence of episodes, its spatial aspect and plotal adaptation; attempts will also be made to consider the impressions created in the audience. Our analysis of the sequences of events (development of the main actions) from the beginning (exordium), through the climax to the end (dénouement) will be based on our examination of the sequential and/or consequential unfolding of the problems, conflicts, intrigues and general tension in the plays.

4.1.0

SETTING

Two types of setting are identified for our purpose. The macro-setting is the large dramatic community that forms the background of the plotal events while the micro-setting is the specific place in the macro-setting, where the events are immediately situated.

4.1.1 Macro-setting

Apart from Moremi, which is predominantly set against an Ilé-Ifè macro-setting, all other plays are set in an Òyó macro-setting. By Òyó is meant Yorùbá cities, towns and villages that are often referred to as Òyó Yorùbá communities in the extra-text. Examples of Òyó cities codified in Oba Mórò include Òyó Igbòho and Òyó Ajàkà. Though particular Òyó cities in which the remaining plays are set are not specified, one can infer information about them from both intra-textual indices and extra-textual mythico-historical evidence. The story codified in Obá Wàjà is, for example, of recent history (1944)⁶. The contemporary Òyó, which is variously known as Òyó Atìbà and Àgòdòyó, is therefore the particular Òyó city iconised in the play. Taking our cue from Johnson's account (1921: 149ff.), if the

Ọyọ city which Sàngó claimed to have founded in Oba Ko So (Ladipo 1970: 4) is Ọyọ Ajáká [also known as Ọyọ Koro or Katunga (Johnson 1921: 149)], then the Ọyọ from which he migrated called Òkè Igbètì after Hethersett (1941: 50), is probably Ọyọ Òkò, the Ọyọ founded by Ọrànńyàn himself. If, as shall be further argued (in Chapter Five) the events in Oba Kò So are seen as sequential to those in Obátálá and Ọsun, where Sàngó also features, then one can conclude that Obátálá and Ọsun are set in Ọyọ Òkò. Other Ọyọ towns and villages codified in the plays are Ede, in Oba Kò So and Apòmù in Béyí ò Se. Though the Ọyọ setting of Ajagun-ńlá is not specified, the fact that the war leaders, Olúgbón, Arẹsà and Oníkòyi, who are prominent in the play are progenitors of Ọyọ Yorùbá towns, coupled with the fact that the warriors claim to be fighting a war for the Alááfin Ọyọ, indicates the Ọyọ macro-setting of the play.

Two reasons can be advanced for the predominant use of the Ọyọ macro-setting. One can say that Duro Ladipo, being of Ọyọ Yorùbá origin himself, is just making use of materials from his immediate surroundings. But the fact that Ọyọ myths, history, legends and culture

in general are more researched into than those of other Yorùbá communities might also have facilitated his dominant use of Ọyọ Yorùbá setting in his plays.

4.1.2.0 Micro-setting

The three micro-settings that are found in all the eight plays under study are àfin (palace) ojà (market-place) and igbórò⁷ (sacred grove). The remaining micro-settings are grouped and discussed together. The extra-textual Yorùbá concept of the micro-settings is examined in relation to their linear significations. The linear structure of the setting in each play will now be schematized for ease of reference.

It is, however, necessary to make our terms clear to facilitate easy reading of the schemes. The direction of the arrows indicates the direction of movement from setting to setting. There are two ways of counting the occurrences of the settings. Whereas all occurrences of the settings are counted in a comprehensive counting, only one occurrence of the same setting is taken into account in an economical counting. The total number of settings in each play is also indicated with the economical one written in brackets.

QBA MÓRÒ

i) Àfin_{1a} → Òkè Àjàkà_{2a} → Àfin_{1b} → Òkè Àjàkà_{2b} → Àfin_{1c} 5 (2)

QBA KÒ SO

ii) Àfin_{1a} → Èdè_{2a} → Àfin_{1b} → Èdè_{2b} → Àfin_{1c} → Igbó àjé_{3a} → Ojà Akèsán_{4a} → Ònà Tápa_{5a} 8 (5)

MOREMI

iii) Àfin → Ojà Ifè_{2a} → Àfin → Odo Èsinmnrin_{3a} → Ojà Ifè_{2b} → Àfin Oba Ìgbò_{4a}
 Aláyémọ̀rẹ_{1a} Aláyémọ̀rẹ_{1b} (Èsinmnrin stream)

Àfin ← Odo Èsinmnrin_{3b} ← Ojà Ifè_{2a} ← Àfin Aláyémọ̀rẹ_{1c} (4) 10
 Aláyémọ̀rẹ_{1d}

QBÁ WÀJÀ

iv) Àfin_{1a} → Ojà_{2a} → Ilé D. O._{3a} Ojà_{2b} → Túbú_{4a} → Ilé Olórí Èlẹ̀ṣin → Ilé ọ́tí ní Gánà_{6a} → Ilé Olórí Èlẹ̀ṣin
 (D.O's (prison) Ọba_{5a} (A beer palor Ọba_{5b} 8(6)
 house) in Ghana)
 (Olórí Èlẹ̀ṣin Ọba's house)

QBÀTÁLÁ

v) Ọrun_{1a} → Ibi tí ọ̀gún àtí Ọbàtálá → Àfin Ọbàtálá_{3a} → Ọnà Ọyọ́_{4a} → Àfin Ẹ̀ngó_{5a} 5 (5)
 tí mu ẹ̀mu_{2a} (The way to Ọyọ́)
 (The place where ọ̀gún and Ọbàtálá drank palm-wine)

ỌSUN

vi) Àfin Ẹ̀ngó_{1a} → Yàrá Ọsun_{2a} → Àfin Ẹ̀ngó_{1b} 3 (2)
 (Ọsun's room)

BEYÌf Ò ŞE

AJAGUN-ÑLÁ

Fig. 4: The Sequential Structures of Micro-setting in the Plays.

Micro-setting	Comprehensive Countings %	Economical Countings %
Àfin	48.28	39.39
Igbórò	13.79	18.1
Ọjà	13.79	15.15
Àwọn yòókù (Others)	24.13	27.27

Fig. 5: A Summary of the Countings of the Occurrences⁸

4.1.2.1 Àfin (The Palace)

The àfin carries the highest percentage in both countings of all the settings as the above table shows. It should be mentioned at this juncture, that the celestial setting at the beginning of Obátálá and the camp of Ajagun-ńlá are both considered as palaces. The general palace-like presentation of these two settings, as well as the extra-textual knowledge of the Yorùbá concept of Olódùmarè as a Supreme King and judge, coupled with the fact that Ajagun-ńlá was an oba among the Igbóminà Yorùbá tribe of Ilá Ọràngún and Òkè Ilá,⁹ primarily motivates our classification of the two settings as palaces. Secondarily the classification is also motivated

by our intention to check an unnecessary overswelling of the miscellaneous category.

In Yorùbá culture, as in most cultures of the world, the palace is the nucleus. In most cases any incident of joy or sadness that happens in the palace usually affects the whole society, and any such incident that happens in any part of the society is also usually directly or indirectly related to the main inmate of the palace, the oba. Hence the general situation in the society is usually described as "ìgbà oba" (the era of the oba), a phrase used in Oba Kò So (Ladipo 1970: 13). The palace and therefore the oba can in effect be seen as a meto-symbolization of the whole society.

The palace as codified in Duro Ladipo's plays is iconic of the Yorùbá àfin. If there is no national disaster, the àfin is often bustling with activities (see Babayemi 1986: 12). A standard traditional palace has its own set of verbal and instrumental artists, who sing the praises of each visitor that comes into the palace. By doing this the oba, who is probably in an inner chamber, knows each and every visitor to his palace. Almost all important social and sacred festivities in the community are extended to the palace.

The celebrants of such festivals, as a matter of both sacred and social convention, come to the palace in pomp and pageantry to pay the cultural homage (ibà) to the oba. The appearance of the oba in public is usually colourful. This extra-textual background paves the way for the type of dramatic iconization which Duro Ladipo builds of the palace setting in his plays, for the palaces are usually colourfully presented.

The opening scenes of the eight plays under analysis are all situated in palace or palace-like settings and the concluding scenes of four of them are also situated in the palace (see the schemes in Fig. 3 above). Many of the actions that do not happen in the palace are often reported there. Such reports may be of off-stage situations, such as the report of the famine by the women of Ọyọ to Ọya and Şàngó respectively in Obatálá. The report of the situation in the battle-field in Ajagun-ńlá is dramatically more effective than such presentations in the other plays. Alejò, through a supernatural means, sees the battle front on the surface of a calabash of water and relays the different feats being performed by both Ajagun-ńlá and Oníkòyí in order to raise the anxiety of Ọmọlọla, who is both Oníkoyí's

daughter and Ajagun-álá's wife. The audience's anxiety is similarly raised because they, like Ọmọlọla, cannot see the scene.

Some reports are many times not of off-stage actions. They are actions which the audience has earlier witnessed. Examples include the report of Timi's coronation by Olófofó in Oba Kò So (Duro Ladipo 1970: 23-24); the report of the disorder at Ọjà Ifẹ by Mọrẹmi in Mọrẹmi (Duro Ladipo 1971: 42); and the report of how Ọsun tricks Ọbà into cutting and cooking her ears in Ọsun. The reports of such actions in the palace before the oba can be seen as an index of the centrality of the palace to the whole society and, therefore, of its meto-symbolic signification. What the situation generally signifies is that the plays are directly concerned with the sovereignty of the iconised community in particular and the Yorúbá society in general.

4.1.2.2 Igbórò (The Sacred Grove)

Judging from its frequency of occurrence especially at the level of economical counting, (see table 1 above), the sacred grove can be rated next to the palace in

order of importance.

The generic name for forest among the Yorùbá is igbó. The name of the divinity to which a particular grove is dedicated usually follows it in adjectival relationship to distinguish it from others. So that the Ifá sacred grove is Igbó Ifá and that of Orò is Igbó Orò (see Awolalu 1979: 114). It should, however, be observed that igbórò is used here as a generic term for all sacred groves, rather than for the Orò grove alone. This denotation is derived from the meaning of orò as ritual rather than as a divinity.

Most sacred groves are in traditional Yorùbá society situated in the outskirts of the community. Because of its isolated location, the sacred grove is usually silent. Huge trees such as ìrókò (African teak) and àràbà (white silk cotton tree) are found in such forests. The grove is usually shaded from sun rays by the many branches and foliage of trees, making the place dark and cool (see Awolalu: 1979: 114ff.). This physical structure of the grove coupled with the legends, myths and beliefs that the grove houses the divinities and other spirits, creates an awesome atmosphere for the sacred location.

In fact, the sacred grove is in most cases out of bounds to non-initiates who are usually kept off it with palm fronds hung at its entrance.

This awesome outlook is usually iconised in Duro Ladipo's performances through lighting and musical effects. Examples of sacred grove iconization in the plays being analysed include Òkè Ajàká in Oba Mórò, Odò Èsinmìnrin in Morèmi, Òṣun's grove in Obàtálá, Ònà Tápà and Igbó Ajé in Oba Kò So, and the forest where Oníkòyí disappeared in Ajagun-ńlá. Whereas the sacredness of the first three examples is clear enough, that of the last ^{two} three needs further clarification. We have considered the forests where Şàngó and Oníkòyí breathe their last as sacred forests because, among the Yorùbá, Şàngó is considered to be a god and Oníkòyí a semi-god. Moreover, the iconizing techniques used in presenting the two forests are comparable to those used in presenting other sacred groves. Our consideration of Igbó Ajé as a sacred grove is based primarily on this presentational iconizing criterion and secondarily on the fact that the witches are regarded as supernatural beings among the Yorùbá.

It should have been clear by now that, apart from the performative iconization through the use of lighting and musical effects, the criteria of the dramatic iconization of the sacred grove include the occurrence of supernatural events there. The voices of both Oníkòyí and Şàngó are for example, echoed from the other world. The Oşun river goddess in collaboration with the trickster god, Eşù, rips off the supernatural dazzling eyes, (eyinjú ide) and the eérìndínlógún divinatorial powers from Oòbátálá at the Oşun grove in Oòbátála. The witches and Èşinmìnrìn river goddess also give both Gbònkáà and Mòrèmi the supernatural supports that make them succeed in their respective dangerous ventures at the sacred groves in Oba Kò So and Mòrèmi respectively. The central action in Obá Mòrò can be seen as a semiotic game based on the Yorùbá belief that the sacred grove houses supernatural beings. The eni òrìşà (deformed characters dedicated to the òrìşà Oòbátálá) are sent by the Oşòmèşì to the Ajàkà hill to impersonate the spirits. Another iconizing signifier of the sacredness of the forests is the fact that sacrifices are offered in three of the six identified sacred forests. A propitiatory

sacrifice is prepared and carried to the Ajáká hill in Oba Mórò. The sacrifice offered by Gbònkáà to the witches in Oba Kò So is also a propitiative one but the sacrificial offering of Olúorogbo to Èsinmìnrin river goddess in Morèmi is a votive sacrifice. There is no other setting in which such sacrifices are offered in the eight plays under analysis.

When a sacred grove setting occurs in the middle of the plot, the actions that take place there are usually vital and of great implication for subsequent developments. It is in the Igbó Àjẹ setting in Oba Kò So that Şàngó's tragic end is implicitly decided when Gbònkáà receives the support of the witches. It is also in the first Odò Èsinmìnrin setting that Morèmi's success and the untimely death of Olúorogbo are supernaturally concluded in Morèmi. The Òkè Ajáká settings in Oba Mórò are alternately woven on a two to three ratio with the palace setting. And it is in the closing sacred grove settings of Oba Kò So and Ajagun-ńlá's plot that the supernatural aspects of Şàngó and Oníkòyí are finalised. All these point to the importance of the sacred grove settings in the plays - a concern with the

religious aspect of the Yorùbá.

4.1.2.3 Ojà (The Market-Place)

The market-place occurs in Oba Kò So, Obá Wàjà, Beyif Ò Se and Morèmi. It can be taken as a meto-symbolization of the community's socio-economic stability. Among the Yorùbá, it is traditionally situated near the palace or the house of an important chief to allow for direct control and quick contact by the oba, chief or their agents. Apart from the commercial transactions which are the primary function of any market, the Yorùbá market also usually serves religious and other social functions. The central position of the market makes it accessible to all and sundry for these socio-religious and economic functions. Since it is near the palace, most of the annual festivals and other celebrations which are taken to the palace are also extended to the market (see 4.1.2.1 above).

A little account of the administrative structure of the Yorùbá market is necessary at this point to elucidate the iconization of the market-place in Morèmi in particular and the other three plays in general.

The market is in most cases divided into stalls. Each stall consists of a guild of traders who sell common or similar goods. There is usually a leader for each guild and the iyálóde ojà is more often than^{net} the overall leader. She is an important female chief usually appointed by the oba and she is directly responsible for the daily smooth running of the market (see Fadipe 1970: 159-163; Eades 1980: 81-91). It is with this type of chieftaincy title that Morèmi is honoured in the opening scene of Morèmi.

The market settings in the plays under analysis are iconic of the extra-textual market situations described above. It is, for example, the fact that social and religious celebrations are extended to the market among the Yorùbá that we are able to comprehend the festive iconization of ojà Ifẹ̀ market in Morèmi and of the Ọyọ́ market (Akeşán) in Obá Wàjà. In both cases the commercial activities of the markets are relegated to the background.

The spatial proximity of the market to the palace can also be said to have motivated the sequential patterning of the settings so that the market setting is either immediately preceded or succeeded by a palace setting.

the same proxemic condition and general social factors must have motivated the choice of ọjà Akẹsán as the scene of the re-match between Gbònkáà and Tímì in Oba Kò Se and where Aólẹ̀ is shot to death in Béyí ọ̀ Se. The choice of the market as the location for the manifestation of conflicts in both Morẹ̀mi and Beyí ọ̀ Se derives from the fact that the problems in the plays are linked with the socio-economic stability of the dramatic worlds. As already noted above, socio-economic stability is the signifier of the smooth running of the physical and organizational structures of the market. When these structures are disrupted as in Morẹ̀mi, or threatened as in Beyí ọ̀ Se, then the society as a whole is economically and socially unstable.

4.1.2.4 Other micro-settings

A feature of the mythico-historical plays, which is carried over from the story-lines of the source materials (the oral myths, legends and histories), is the vagueness of some of the settings (and characters). Such vagueness is, however, more common among other micro-settings.

There are, for example, about two different

micro-settings fused in the Èdẹ setting of Oba Kò Sọ. It is both an outskirts of the town by the bodẹ (gate) and also an open place close enough to the palace where Timì can easily be coronated; he can also easily hear Gbònkáà's call. As our earlier discussion (in 4.1.2.2 and 4.1.2.3) has shown, this setting could have either been taken for a sacred grove, or a market place. The reason for this vagueness in the presentation of the setting can, however, be attributed to dramatic spatial economy. What is more important to Duro Ladipo, and his source (Hethersette 1941: 51) where the micro-setting is mentioned, is that the location is Èdẹ and not any other Yorùbá town.

The location of the setting in Ajagun-ńlá generally, needs explanation. As earlier said (in 4.1.2.1), Olúgbòn, Arẹsà and Oníkòyí are also obas in their respective original communities but the four war lords are, in the dramatic context of the play, on Aláàfin's military service. They are in military camps. Since Ajagun-ńlá is the generalissimo, he is presented in a monarchical code while the remaining war lords are presented as his lieutenants or chiefs. This is why Olúkòyí's camp, which

also features twice in the sequence of setting, is not discussed as a palace.

The location of the second micro-setting in Obátálá can only be mythically identified. It is probably Ifè-òdáyé, where Obátálá is believed to have poured the earth he brought from heaven and from where the earth spread all over the world. The location of the remaining micro-settings, especially those in Obá Wájá, does not pose any problem. It will be remembered that Obá Wájá's plot is said to be derived from recent history of Oyo city (see 1.4.1).

We think the above discussion of the settings will further help in a clear understanding of the plays in general and of the structure of the actions and events in particular.

4.2

THE PLOTAL EXORDIUM

The plots of the eight plays under analysis have a common feature. They all have the same type of exordium. All the plays open with a sort of festivity or celebration which is generally allowed for by the palace or palace-like setting discussed above. The general arrangement of

the opening scene, with an empty throne on which the oba is expected to sit, and the fact that the oba is the subject of the opening verbal performance, make the opening scene as a whole indexical of the imminent appearance of the royal figure. The eventual appearance of the oba is usually the climax to the celebration and it is always marked by the greeting shout of káábíyèsí, to acknowledge his presence. The oba may at this point join the celebration by moving to the music and responding to the eulogy of the chant and/or song and the greeting exclamation of káábíyèsí. This pattern is true of Oba Kò So and Osun where Şàngó is the royal figure and also of Morèmi where Oṣoni Aláyémọrẹ is the monarch. In the first two plays Şàngó bursts in on the celebration with his thunderous shout of "éééé" to which the people respond káábíyèsí in the extra-textual manner of the Şàngó adherents' response to thundering. It should, however, be noted that this response is also iconic of the general palace contexts. Şàngó in the two plays acknowledges the praise singing of the court artists by interjecting "È şeun" ("Thank you") into the performance on a regular basis in the manner of the extra-textual Şàngó empathization performance.

Definitely in a celebrative mood, he also sings a song in solo thanking "Ọlọrun" (God) who has prospered his migration from Ọkè Igbètì to Ọde Ọyọ where he now settles and reigns (Ladipo 1970: 4).

Likewise in Morèmi, Aláyémọrẹ is ushered onto the scene amidst chants of the praise poetry of the Olúfẹ lineage rendered by the Olórí ẹmẹsẹ in praise of both the royal figure in particular and the whole Ifẹ nation in general. As he enters the people shout "Bàbá yíí ọ" (the equivalent of "Kábiyèsí" in the Ifẹ tradition). The Ọọni acknowledges this greeting with the prayerful saying "Ẹ á gbó" ("You will live to a ripe age"). The chiefs also pay the Ifẹ traditional homage by prostrating themselves before the Ọọni and saying,

Woori wóórí woori
 Eku á jíṣẹ
 Ẹja á jíṣẹ
 Ọpó á tìrì mọlẹ
 Ẹṣin ọba á joko
 Ará iwá á wá
 Èrò ẹhìn á wá
 Ẹní tì sìn á sìn
 Tin in tin in Ajàlọrun
 Woori wóórí woori

(Ladipo 1971: 2-3)

Behold him, behold him, behold him
 The mouse (more properly, rat) will deliver the
 goods

The fish will deliver the goods

The house-posts will keep their foundation firm.

The king's horse will graze well.

Those who have passed away will return

Those who are yet to arrive will arrive

The one who has not served will serve.

Ajálórún the Radiant one

Behold him, behold him, behold him

(Adedeji 1972: 7)

In Adedeji (1972: 7) Aláyemọrẹ leads a song immediately after this obligatory greeting. Thus one can see him as participating actively in the festivity of the opening scene. In the televised codification of the opening scene, the situation is not only festive, it is also an annual festival occasion where the Ọ̀nì says the annual festival prayer,

Ọ̀ḍọ̀ḍún ní à á rórógbo

Ọ̀ḍọ̀ḍún ní à á ráwùsá

Ọ̀ḍọ̀ḍún ní à á má a ríra wa o

È níí bàjẹ nígbà tiwa o.

The bitter kola appears yearly
 The awísá fruit appears yearly
 We shall see one another yearly
 There won't be upheavals in our time

to which the people respond "Àşẹ" ("So be it") after each line. The Oḍni also announces the result of the annual divination to his subjects in the televised performance.

Baalẹ Apòmù being a very lively person is, more than the other monarchs, actively involved in the merry-making of the festivity that opens Béyíí ò Şe. He dances gracefully to tunes played for him and stops the oral artists with the shout of "ó tóó" ("Hold on"), to make one or two self-praising comments and initiate new tunes to be played for him.

The type of festivity identified in Ajagun-ńlá is peculiar to it. Being based on war and war-like people, the play opens with the celebration of martial victory. This subject of celebration is clearly indicated in the opening song - "A şe, şe a jù wọn lọ ná" (see 3.1.1.3 above for the text of this song). The two types of exclamatory call and response identified in the opening section of Ajagun-ńlá which have been discussed (in

Chapter 3) above are also used in the creation of the martial celebration. As the discussion in Chapter Three shows Ajagun-ńlá like the royal figures in Oba Kò So, Ọsun, Morèmi and Beylì ò Se also participates actively in the celebration. He is like them too the centre of the festivity.

The introductory scenes in Oba Mórò and Obátálá, however, deviate slightly from the general pattern described above only because the monarchs do not participate directly in the festivity by joining the singing or by dancing. We, however, still consider the monarchs in the two cases as indirect participants in the festivity because each monarch constitutes the nucleus of the celebration. The festivity stops as soon as the Aláàfin enters and the council goes on straight into serious business after the normal greetings in Oba Mórò. The concept of Olódùmarè as an invisible monarch already referred to, conditions the way he is presented on stage so that only His voice is heard in Obátálá. The angels are presented praising Olódùmarè in a neo-traditional musical melody¹⁰ (see Oníbonòkúta 1983: 24 for the text of the song). Like in Oba Kò So and Ọsun, the praise

singing, which can be seen as a sort of celebration of the personality of Olódùmarè, is stopped abruptly on the thunderous shout of "éééé" by Olódùmarè. But unlike in Oba Kò So and Osun, there is no exclamation of "káábíyèsí" in response. Like in Oba Mórò the celebration is summarily terminated. Though it is possible to speculate that it is the invisible nature of Olódùmarè that does not allow for His participation in the festivity, it is more plausible to consider, as in the case of Oba Vórò, the seriousness of the succeeding line of action as the factor that determines the termination of the festivity in the opening scene of Obàtálá.

The introductory scene of Obá Wàjà is unique in its conformity with the general pattern. Though situated in a palace setting and a festive atmosphere can be construed for it (in the televised version at least), no monarch is presented. As indicated in the title of the play the royal figure, Alááfin, has just died when the play opens. The Ọyómèsi and other nobles in Ọyọ gather in the palace to deliberate on his funeral ceremony. The praise singer sings the praise of the deceased Alááfin, as well as that of the chiefs as they enter. There is drumming and dancing,

for the death of the Aláàfin is not a thing of sadness. The celebration in this exordium, which precedes the deliberation, can be seen as a token of the main funeral ceremony. It is however clear that though not present physically, the monarch still forms the centre of the festivity. It should be noted that the token of the funeral celebration is sliced off from the Ulli Beier (1964) edited version of the play where the main celebration is only overheard or probably seen through the window of the D.O.'s bedroom (1964: 55-57).

It is against the festivity of this exordial situation that the conflict of the play is usually introduced. But the situation in Morèmi and Obàtálá differs slightly on this point. The actions that follow the initial festivity in the two plays rise to their climax and are soon terminated. It will not be wrong to consider the sequence of actions as complete sub-plots in themselves. It is after the termination of this sub-plot that a fresh festive atmosphere is created from which the main plotal action takes its roots. In Morèmi (Duro Ladipo 1971) the sub-plot tells of how Morèmi is unanimously selected and installed by the royal council as the new Iyálóde ojà Ifè.

It is this honour which impels Moremi to be directly committed to the Ifẹ̀ sovereignty and the upshot is the heroic steps that form the life-wire of the plotal trend. A fresh festive atmosphere within which the major conflict is introduced is inaugurated in the market scene where Moremi's chieftaincy title is celebrated. We would have analysed the sequence of the initial opening scene, the sub-plot and the fresh festive atmosphere as constituting the exordium of Moremi, but for its unusual length.

The sub-plot in Obatalá focuses on Obatalá's primordial error in creating deformed beings. This error is caused by his joining Ogún in drinking palmwine excessively. Olódumarè calls him to order by warning him.

Bó o ò bá yeraà re wò,
 Èni mímọ̀ ni mo se ọọ,
 N ó padà léyìn reẹ.

If you do not examine yourself,
 I created you a holy person,
 I will forsake you.

Obatalá then becomes repentant and vows not to take palmwine again. It is after this resolution that the

festive atmosphere is inaugurated in which Ọbàtálá celebrates the yam festival. The subsequent plotal trend develops directly from the new festive situation. The relationship of the sub-plot to the subsequent actions in the play is, unlike that of Mọ̀rẹ̀mi, tenuous and only indirect. It is important to note that the general exordial pattern and the sub-plot are sliced off the Ọbọ̀túndé Ijímèrè version of Ọbàtálá (titled The Imprisonment of Ọbàtálá) and Beier's edited version of Mọ̀rẹ̀mi (1967). The primary structural signification of the sub-plot in Ọbàtálá is that it serves as the logical basis for the subsequent passive suffering of Ọbàtálá for his primordial error.

Whereas the agreement of the new festive atmosphere in Ọbàtálá with the general exordial pattern is apparent if, as shown (in 4.1.2.1) above, Ọbàtálá is seen as presented in a monarchical code, that of Mọ̀rẹ̀mi needs some clarification. Though Mọ̀rẹ̀mi does not have a palace setting or monarch as its centre of attraction, the fact that it has a very strong royal connection can be used in making a case for its belonging to the general exordial structure. Mọ̀rẹ̀mi who is the centre of attraction can

be seen as a royal figure in that she is a royal wife¹¹ and the primary representative of the Oṣoni in the market. Moreover, the market, o.jà Ifè, is a royal market situated near the palace. It is therefore clear from the on-going discussion that the fact that Obátálá and Morèmi have ^{each} two exordia/does not necessarily set their introductory structure apart from the general pattern discussed above. It is also very clear that each play has adapted ~~the~~ pattern according to the structural nature of its plotal progression.

The possible initial impression signified by the festive atmosphere of the exordial scenes is that of peace and normalcy in the dramatic community as a whole. This reading is based on the meto-symbolic signification of both the palace and the monarch as the representation of the community and its people. This signification is clearly codified in Oba Kò So where the people declare in a song that the community is peaceful.

Igbà oḅa wa dára fún wa
 O dára fún wa
 Igbà oḅa wa sunwọn fún wa
 Íjà kò sí ọtẹ kò sí
 Íjà kò sí ọtẹ kò sí
 Igboro mà dùn gbọngbọn fún wa
 (1970: 4)

The reign of our king is good for us
It is good for us.

The reign of our king is good for us
There is no fight, there is no plot
There is no fight, there is no plot
The town is very pleasant for us

(1970: 70-71)

The inclusion of the royal figure (and *Olódumarè* in the case of Obàtálá) as the centre of attraction in the festivity is capable of having a socio-psychological impression which allows for the initial dramatic arrest of the audience's interest. The oba is traditionally a political and sacred figure seen in public only occasionally at annual festivals. To see such a figure on stage in full regalia can be interesting in itself. The extra-textual context of the occasion when the oba is publicly seen can be regenerated in the audience's subconscious. This socio-psychological signification is also possible in the case of *Olódumarè* in Obàtálá. To hear the voice of *Olódumarè*, the invisible almighty contacted only indirectly through the divinities and their priests, can also be arresting in itself.

On a general note, it can be concluded that

Duro Ladipo has woven into the general exordium of his mythico-historical plays the effect of the extra-plotal opening glee (which as said in 3.2.1.1 is used infrequently). The plotal exordium as our discussion above must have clearly shown is also preponderantly musical.

4.3.0 PLOTAL PROGRESSION: DEVELOPMENT OF CONFLICT

In this section we will go on to examine the progression of the conflicts in the plot by considering the patterns of conflict introduction and further development of the conflicts.

4.3.1.0 Introduction of Conflict

Two patterns of introducing conflict are postulated for the plot of the plays under analysis. The main conflict of the plot is directly initiated during the festivity of the introductory scene in the first pattern, while it is indirectly initiated in the second pattern. All the key figures or groups involved in the articulation of the conflict are presented at this point in the first pattern while only some of them are so presented in the

second pattern. Oba Mórò, Oba Kò So, Morèmi and Osun manifest the first pattern while the second pattern is manifested in Obá Wàjà, Obàtálá, Béyí ò Se and Ajagun-álá.

4.3.1.1 Direct Introduction of Conflict:

Oba Mórò, Oba Kò So, Morèmi and Osun

In all the plays in which this pattern is manifest, it is the introduction of the conflict that stops the festivity of the opening scene. Apart from Osun, there are indices either in the opening scenes or in the way the conflicts are introduced that the conflicts are not fresh ones or that they have been underway before the plotal exordium.

In Oba Mórò the index is embedded in the traditional homage-paying song of the Ọyómèsì to the Aláàfin.

Kábíyèsí ọba wa àtàtà
 Aláàfin Ọyọ, ìbà o
 Ká to fi ọ jọba la ti mò
 Pólórfire lo jẹ o
 Idòbálẹ wa rè é o
 A yíká o
 Rántí o, rántí o
 Má se gbàgbé péé
 Iran baba baba rẹ ní í jaláàfin Ọyọ o

Awa ni ìjòyè Ọyọ,
 Awa tún ni gbajúmọ
 Tí í mú ìlú tòrò
 Ìlú Ọyọ dọwọ rẹ o
 Aláàfin Ọyọ ìbà o
Má se sá wa tí nínú ètò ìlú o.

Kábiyèsí, our very good king
 Aláàfin of Ọyọ, we pay homage
 Before you were enthroned, we knew
 That you are a lucky person
 Here we prostrate ourselves
 Rolling to the left and right
 Remember, oh! remember
 Do not forget that
 It is your great grandfathers that usually
 ascend the throne of the aláàfin of Ọyọ
 We are the chiefs of Ọyọ
 And we are also the nobles
 The city of Ọyọ is in your care
 Homage to you, oh Aláàfin of Ọyọ
Do not ignore us in the organization of the city.
 (Emphasis is mine).

The warning of the Ọyómèsì, which gradually builds up and
 culminates in the last line, anticipates the Aláàfin's
 disregard later for their views in his decision to shift

the base of his government to Ọyọ Ajàká and indicates that the conflict has been underway. The fact that the instruction to move the seat of government is said to have been passed down to the new Aláàfin by his father, his immediate predecessor further corroborates our view that the conflict has been brewing underground, even before the installation of the new Aláàfin. The conflict is, however, properly introduced when immediately after the homage-paying and the warning, the Aláàfin declares his intention to carry out his father's wish. The Ọyómèsì's promise to deliberate on the matter, rather than support it outright, is enough indication of their opposition.

In Oba Kò So, the main conflict is introduced at the point where the Ọyómèsì enter during the festivity in the opening scene to register, their protest against Gbònkáà and Tìmì's frequent military expeditions (see Ladipo 1970: 9). The contradiction between the Ọyómèsì's claim and the earlier declaration that Şàngó's reign has been peaceful ("Tgbà ọba wa dára fún wa") is indexical of an underground outstanding conflict. The people of whom the chiefs are representatives must have all along been dissatisfied with the frequent wars but cannot face Şàngó with it until

in the three plays is therefore a camouflage. One cannot, in the face of the connotative signification of the said sharp contradiction, say that there has been peace in the community as a whole. Duro Ladipo deliberately wants to take his audience by surprise when an unexpected conflict is made to surface¹².

In Osun, which can be seen as a sub-class of this category, the contradiction that ensues from the introduction of the conflict is not as sharp as in the other three plays. In fact, the conflict in Osun is, unlike in the other three plays, a fresh one that emerges from the situation of the opening festivity. Oya and Obà are the senior wives of Şàngó who usually prepare the weekly royal feast alternately. Oşun, however, arrives on the scene during the first weekly royal feast prepared by Oya (Şàngó's most senior wife) and Şàngó, who is deeply infatuated with ^{her} her does not only propose marriage to her but later also orders that she should prepare his next royal feast. Şàngó's action contradicts what obtains in Yorùbá polygamy for he does not seem to respect the seniority among co-wives according to the chronology of his marriage to them. By asking Oşun, rather than Obà, to prepare

the next feast, Şàngó has already set the stage for foregrounding the potential house-wives' rivalry in a polygamous situation.

As already stated (in 4.3.1.0) above, all the key characters (or groups) involved in the conflict are usually clearly presented at the point of conflict introduction. So, we know from this early point in Oba Kò So that the main conflict is between Şàngó, the Ọyómèsi and the two warlords while in Oba Mórò, it is primarily between the Alááfin and the Ọyómèsi. In Ọsun, it is realised that the conflict is more likely to be between Ọsun and Ọbà than between Ọsun and Ọya since it is Ọbà that is directly assaulted by Şàngó's decision. The conflict in Morèmi, it is also clear from this early point in plotal progression, is to be an Ìgbò versus Ifẹ affair. The oba of the two communities are therefore going to be major actors in the conflict. But the way in which Morèmi is foregrounded, especially in the televised version, at the exordium of the plot is also indexical of the fact that she is going to play a major role on the Ifẹ side of the conflict. It is the clear and direct presentation of these major characters in the introduction

of conflict that makes the indexication of subsequent actions in the plot straightforward.

4.3.1.2 Indirect Introduction of Conflict:
Obàtálá, Bèyìf ò Se, Ajagun-ńlá and Obá Wàjà.

The main conflict of the plot is introduced in the form of an oracular prophecy in Obàtálá, Bèyìf ò Se and Ajagun-ńlá. As in Oḷá Rótìmi's The Gods Are Not to Blame (Oxford University Press , 1971) an impending calamity is usually indicated in the divinatory transaction. One can also say that the conflict is usually introduced in a subtle manner when the protagonist (as well as his men, as the case may be) has to decide whether or not the divinatory instruction should be taken. A contrary stand to that of the oracle is usually taken. The protagonist is therefore comparable to the defiant Ifá suppliant, of whom the following is usually said in the Ifá divinatory poetry:

Ó pawo lékèé
 Ó pÈşù lólè
 Ó wòrun yàn-yàn-yàn
 Bí ẹnì tí ò ní kú mọ
 Ó wá kọtí ọgbọin sẹbọ.

He accuses the diviner of being a liar
 He accuses Eṣù of being a rogue
 He looks up to heaven with contempt
 As if he will never die
 And he turns a deaf ear to sacrifice.

On the basis of this extra-textual consideration, the audience at this early point in the plot can start to guess the turn of events since such defiance to divinatory instructions usually leads to regret (see Abimbola 1966, 1969). A likely tension is therefore created in the audience at this juncture between the present known situation and the anticipated repercussion. It is this tension which sustains the audience's interest to find out the unknown final situation. Let us first of all illustrate this from Obàtálá, Béyí ò Se and Ajagun-ńlá.

In all the three plays, as in those discussed in the last sub-section above, the conflict is introduced during the festivity at the beginning of the plot. A diviner is either invited as in Ajagun-ńlá and Obàtálá, or he comes on his own out of a sense of duty as the royal Ifá priest to divine for the protagonist as in Beyí ò Se. In Ajagun-ńlá the oracular injunction is disobeyed, namely,

the four warlords refuse to perform a propitiatory sacrifice to avoid a clash with Èṣù. The diviner's instruction that Ọbátálá should not go on a journey to Ọyó/^{to}settle an account with Èṣù is disregarded in Ọbátálá. Similarly, Baálẹ̀ Apòmù refuses to offer a preventive sacrifice. In all the three cases, therefore, we can see that the protagonists have set themselves not only against the Ifá god of divination but also, in the case of the first two plays at least, against that most dreaded trickster divinity Èṣù. The extra-textual knowledge of Èṣù and the implication of refusal to placate him can make the critical spectator guess the likely plotal development. But whatever the case may be, a spectator cannot at this point be sure of the way and manner in which Èṣù will precipitate the confusion that is to emanate from the conflict. In Ajagun-ńlá where the war-lords think that they are as supernaturally powerful as Èṣù and therefore see no reason why they should propitiate him, the diviner feels ridiculously insulted and activates the powers of Èṣù against the warlords with an incantation.

Wọn ló dọ̀ràn waríkò
 Èmi nǎǎ ló dọ̀ràn waríkò
 Olúgbọ̀n waríkò
 Ín sẹ̀wọ̀ Arẹ̀sà
 Arẹ̀sà waríkò
 Ín sẹ̀wọ̀ Olúkòyí
 Olúkòyí waríkò
 In sẹ̀wọ̀ Ajagun-ńlá
 Èni tó bá jẹ̀rú
 Ènu wọ̀n a rú
 Ògírímòtasi
 Ènu wọ̀n a rú
 Èni tó bá jata
 Ènu wọ̀n a ta
 Ògírímòtasi
 Ènu wọ̀n a ta

They said it is a matter of "drawing in one's
 head" (withdrawing one's support)
 And I said it is a matter of "drawing in one's
 head

Olúgbọ̀n "draws in his head"
 He antagonizes you Arẹ̀sà
 Arẹ̀sà "draws in his head"
 He antagonizes you Olúkòyí
 Olúkòyí draws in his head"
 And antagonizes you Ajagun-ńlá
 He that eats locust beans
 Will foam in the mouth

Ogírímòtasi

Will foam in the mouth

He that eats pepper

His mouth will get hot

Ogírímòtasi

His mouth will get hot.

One can suspect an internal conflict among the warlords in the subsequent developments along the plotal line. But in the case of Obàtálá and Béyíí ò Se there is nothing that indicates a comparable trend of plotal development. One cannot even but wonder how the conflict suggested at this point in Ajagun-ńlá will materialize in the face of the bond of comradeship among the four warlords.

We also recognise at this early point in the plotal line in the cases of both Ajagun-ńlá and Obàtálá that the conflict is actually between the protagonists and Èṣù. But since Èṣù is capable of manifesting his handiwork through other beings apart from his physical self, we cannot be sure of the particular character in whom Èṣù will manifest himself. Similarly we are not certain about the likely antagonist at this point in Béyíí ò Se. This is why we conclude that, unlike in the cases of plays

where direct introduction of conflict is manifest, the ensuing line of plotal development is not as clearly indicated in the plays that exhibit indirect conflict introduction. The initial conflict or crisis between the protagonist and the diviner is only employed as an indirect springboard to the main conflict. It is, for example, only in Beyí ò Se where the diviner plays the role of a confidant to the protagonist that he features in the remaining part of the plot.

The patterning or structuring of the conflict introduction in Obá Wájà constitutes a sub-class of its own in this class just as Osun does in the categories of plays treated in 4.3.1.1. The conflict, like in the remaining three plays is introduced against the background of the festive opening situation and it is also introduced like others on a crisis point. But the decision that must be taken is not whether an oracular instruction should be taken or not. The crisis is instead a verbal argument between a white couple [the D.O. (District Officer) and his wife] on whether it is within the D.O.'s colonial jurisdiction to interfere, in the royal burial ritual during which Chief Olórí Èlẹ̀şin Ọba¹³ is expected

to commit suicide to buy a safe passage for the dead Alááfin. The argument starts in their bedroom after the wife has learnt from her husband that the "noise" of the music that has been disturbing their peace is in preparation for the suicide.

D.O.'s wife: What?

Do you mean to say that in the twentieth century we still have human sacrifice in this town - and under the British rule?

D.O.: This is not human sacrifice. Nobody will kill the man. He will die by simple act of will.

D.O.'s wife: And you tolerate that under your own jurisdiction? Are you not here to bring civilization to this people?

D.O. I am here to maintain law and order, not to interfere in people's lives.

D.O.'s wife: You are here to prevent this type of savagery. I am disgusted with you. You are letting down the side. I promise you that if you will not stop this ugly business then I will take the next boat home.

D.O.

Now don't get excited. I will see what I can do tomorrow - I'll do it for your sake. But I assure you that these things are better left alone.

(Beier 1964: 56-57)

From this dialogue, one is left in no doubt as to the next line of action. The solution being presented for the initial crisis prepares the ground for the main conflict of the plot between the colonial culture meto-symbolised by the D.O., and an aspect of Yorùbá culture in *Ọyọ*. Like in the three plays already discussed here, the argument between the couple is used indirectly to indicate the main conflict. We can only just guess from this point in the plotal line that the person who is to commit the suicide will be the particular target of the D.O.'s attack. There is no full information in the dialogue about this.

In the four plays considered here one can notice that the introduction of the conflict against the background of the festivity of the opening part is not as sharp or violent as in the plays that belong to the first category. The type of surprise signification achieved in the plays

of the first category is therefore also absent. In fact, there are no indices that the hypothetical peaceful signification of the initial festivity is false in any of the four plays.

It is pertinent to note, as a sort of general conclusion on the categorization that emerges out of the discussion in 4.3.1. (i.e. including 4.3.1.1 and 4.3.1.2) that Osun (in the group of plays that manifest the direct pattern of conflict introduction), and Obá Wàjà (in the group which manifests the indirect pattern), tend to deviate from the general structures of the categories under which they are respectively discussed. But they are so classified firstly because they share some features with other plays in their respective categories and secondly to avoid proliferation of categories. This explains why they are each described as a sub-class in their respective categories.

4.3.2.0 Development of Conflict

To sustain the audience's interest, the conflict introduced has to be further developed or complicated. Two general patterns of conflict development can be noted

in the plots of the plays under study. The conflict may be complicated either through the scheming of intrigues or through direct confrontations.

4.3.2.1.0 Development of Conflict Through Intrigues.

There are two types of conflict development under this pattern. The conflict can be developed either through unilateral intrigue or bilateral intrigue. Plays in which unilateral intrigue is manifest include Obátálá and Ajagun-ńlá, while Oba Kò So, Oba Mórò, Morèmi and Osun are those in which bilateral intrigue is manifested.

4.3.2.1.1 Unilateral Intrigue

The intrigues on which the plotal complication of Obátálá and Ajagun-ńlá are based are schemed by Èṣù. The objects of Èṣù's intrigues are powerless against him; they cannot react against Èṣù's machination, hence the intrigue is unidirectional. It should, however, be remembered, as our discussion in 4.3.1.2 has shown, that the intrigued ones initiate the scheming of the intrigues by first setting themselves against Èṣù.

The first three of the intrigues in Obátálá can be

traced directly to Èṣù who appears physically either as an active or passive participant in the materialization of the intrigues. The realization of the fourth intrigue which culminates directly in the tragedy in the play can be traced to the machination of Èṣù though he is not physically present.

In the first case Èṣù in disguise pours red palm oil on Obàtálá who is trying to help him to lift a pot of oil onto his head. Obàtálá's immaculate white garment is therefore soiled. The soiling of Obàtálá's garment can be seen as a meta-symbolic indication of the vitiation of Obàtálá's holy uprightness through his primordial error¹⁴. To remove the blemish and regain his original state, Obàtálá has to suffer without retaliation in the hands of Èṣù. It is probably because of this signification that the Oṣun goddess, conniving with Èṣù, refuses to allow Obàtálá to wash the stain on his garment into river Oṣun. Oṣun also refuses to allow Obàtálá to cross the river until he has offered his sixteen divinatory cowries (eṣ̀r̀ind̀íǹlóg̀ún), and the supernatural brass dazzling eyes (eyinjú idẹ)¹⁵. Thirdly, Èṣù through his bi-coloured robe also causes an argument

between Ọbàtálá and his farmer friend who has earlier agreed to show Ọbàtálá the way to Ọyọ in the savannah. On the three occasions, Ọbàtálá manages to control himself, receiving all the assaults passively. Eşù compounds the situation by making jest of him on each occasion. Fourthly, the weary Ọbàtálá is also later taken for a thief when he attempts to ride Şàngó's horse. He is arrested and imprisoned without trial.

The structuring of the intrigues in Ajagun-ńlá is quite different. The nature of the intrigues looks more complex than in Ọbàtálá. Eşù disguises as Alejò (Visitor) and takes advantage of Ọmọlọlá's (Ajagun-ńlá's wife) childlessness. He deceives Ọmọlọlá and gets her to agree to cut her husband's beard for some preparation that would enable her to bear a child. Alejò later on tells Ajagun-ńlá of Ọmọlọlá's intention to murder him in his sleep at midnight. The same Alejò goes round to inform Olúkòyí, Ọmọlọlá's father and Ajagun-ńlá's lieutenant, that Ajagun-ńlá plans to kill his only daughter for some ritual at midnight. In addition, Alejò warns the bodyguards in Ajagun-ńlá's house of the danger in interfering in a duel between Ajagun-ńlá and

Oníkòyí. Ajagun-ńlá readily believes Alejò when at midnight he catches his wife holding a knife in his bedroom. The confused Ọmọlọlá goes down on her knees and tries to explain the situation. Olúkòyí enters at this moment and he too, readily believes Alejò's story when he finds Ajagun-ńlá holding a knife and Ọmọlọla on her knees. A physical combat ensues between the two warlords. But for the timely intervention of the diviner whom Ọmọlọla has summoned after trying in vain to stop the fight, the situation would have led to a fatal disaster. Èṣù's malignity is, however, revealed when all the sides concerned realise that it is Alejò who has schemed the conflict. This revelation leads to the resolution of the conflict between the two warlords and even strengthens their friendship.

Though the second intrigue can be seen as emanating from the first, the connection between them is very thin. The conflict that arises from this second intrigue is primarily between Olúgbọ̀n and Arẹ̀sà's children on the one hand and Olúkòyí on the other hand. Disappearing after the intrigue has been unfolded, Alejò re-surfaces after Olúgbọ̀n and Arẹ̀sà's death to incite the mourning children

of the deceased warlords against Olúkòyí. The death of the two warlords is actually traceable to Àlejò's initial intrigue. The water which Ọmọlọlá offers the four warlords on their return from their first battle, and which only Olúgbón and Arẹsà take, has earlier been contaminated by Alejo with a power capable of neutralising the military strength and supernatural powers of the warlords. This is why Olúgbón and Arẹsà are defeated easily and killed in the second battle. Àlejò is however able to convince the bereaved children because Olúkòyí stays back at home instead of going to the battle-field with the dead warlords. It is, however, Ajagun-ńlá who advises Olúkòyí against going to the battle field because of the premonition he has about the outcome.

There is no doubt that the plots of the two plays are loosely developed. The looseness in Ọbàtálá is comparable to that encountered in folktales, (aló àpagbè), where certain patterns are iterated for emphatic purpose and to create room for singing and dancing¹. On the connotative (signified) level of the materialization of the four intrigues in Ọbàtálá, the point of emphasis is the extent of Ọbàtálá's suffering¹⁷. One can say that the actions in each event on the denotative (signifier)

level are unconnected, that is, they do not develop out of one another. They are sequentially but not consequentially arranged. The re-arrangement of the first three intrigues will have little or no effect on the denotative structure of the plot. The fact that some, if not all, the intrigues are taken from different sources can probably serve as a pointer to the looseness. The third intrigue is, for example, from a popular anecdote about Èşù which another dramatist Ògúnmolá, has also adapted for his play Èşù Òdàrà. The first intrigue is also probably adapted from the popular saying "má da epo sí aşo àlà mi" ("do not pour red palm oil on my white garment"). The four intrigues can be seen as paradigmatically structured and one can talk of slow or even non-movement in plotal progression in the structuralization of the intrigues. The following is a diagrammatic conceptualization of our analysis:

Fig. 6: The structure of the looseness in Òbàtálá's plot.

The slow or non-movement of action in plotal progression is also indicated in the setting of the four intrigues against a single background òṅà Òyó (see 4.1.2.0 above).

The looseness in Ajagun-ńlá is not as disjointed as that of Obàtálá. There are two plotal progressions in Ajagun-ńlá, with the second one taking its source not from the conclusion but from the middle of the first. The second one, based on the conflict between the children of Olúgbòn and Arẹ̀sà and Oníkòyí, can therefore be seen as subordinate to the first, which is based on the conflict between Ajagun-ńlá and Oníkòyí. It is at the point of Olúgbòn and Arẹ̀sà's death in the plot that we have the foregrounded link between the two plotal trends which are based respectively on the two intrigues and major conflict. The incident of the contaminated water, however, forms the backgrounded basis of the link.

Fig. 7: The structure of the looseness in Ajagun-ńlá's plot.

One cannot but notice the overlapping structure of the plot. Such overlap is, however, not a peculiar feature of the plays. As noted by Seagre (1981), it is a general feature of dramatic plots.

4.3.2.1.2 Bilateral Intrigue

Oba Kò So, Oba Mórò Morèmi and Osun are the plays which are said to manifest the development of plot based on bilateral intrigue. In this pattern of plotal development, unlike those just discussed above, there is intrigue scheming and counter scheming or reaction. Hence the descriptive bilateral. Unlike in the unilateral pattern the plotal developments of plays that exhibit bilateral intrigue are predominantly consequentially structured.

Whereas in Oba Mórò and Morèmi, it is the antagonist that initiates the intrigues, one can say that the intrigues develop naturally out of the opening events in Oba Kò So and Osun (see 4.2). The Ọyómèsì, who are the antagonists in Oba Mórò, plan and send deformed characters to Okè Ajáká to impersonate the spirits in order to frighten the messengers of Aláàfin away from arranging for the

movement of the seat of government from Igbòho to Ajàká. The military use of the sacred ancestor masquerade by the Igbò warriors, who constitute the antagonist group in Moremi, is also an intrigue aimed at frightening the Ifè people into believing that they are being attacked by spirits.

In, Oba Kò So, however, Şàngó has no better alternative than to scheme against his obstinate warlords in order to satisfy his people. This is why he agrees to send one of the warlords to Èdè where he is expected to get killed by the Ijèşà army (Ladipo 1970: 15-16). In Ọsun, it is after Şàngó has re-arranged the roster for the cooking of the royal feast that Ọbà and Ọya show signs of the game of intrigue. This is indicated by the house-wife rivalry songs (see 3.1.1.1 above) which they sing.

The protagonist, who is naturally aware of the intrigue (as in Ọsun), or to whom the secret of the intrigue is leaked (as in Oba Mórò), plans a counter intrigue that crushes the initial one. The counter intrigue in Ọsun materializes before Ọbà and Ọsun have time to scheme out theirs. This happens when Ọbà,

following the advice of their husband, goes to seek Ọsun's advice on how to cook a delicious meal for the royal feast. Ọsun tricks Ọbà into cutting and cooking her ears¹⁸. In Oba Mórò the counter intrigue is hatched when, on the advice of Ológbo, the Alááfin sends Olúḡḡ, his chief hunter, to capture the spirit impersonators. He then makes them serve the Ọyómèsì, the initial intriguers during a royal feast.

The situation in Morèmi is similar to that in Ọsun and Oba Mórò in that it is in reaction to the incessant raid on Ifẹ by the Ìgbò that Morèmi goes as a spy to Ìgbò land where she manages to extract from Ọba Ìgbò himself information about the masqued warriors. Morèmi also intimidates Díbíá, the Ìgbò royal diviner, into revealing the secret of the masqued warriors.

The consequentiality of the plot development is no doubt clearly implied in the scheming and counter scheming of intrigues. A total of three intrigues is, for example, schemed by Ọ̀àngo in Oba Kò So with a new one emerging from the failure of the old one. The two warlords are set against each other in a duel when Tìmì, instead of getting killed at Èḡḡ is installed as the king. A re-match

of the duel has to be planned when the two warlords survive the first one. It is at this point that Gbònkáà realizes the treacherous intention behind the scheme. Gbònkà's final reaction cannot be regarded as an intrigue. It is more of an open and direct confrontation. Gbònkáà, after killing Tìmì in the second fight, challenges Şàngó by first of all proving that he is beyond Şàngó's reach and secondly by ordering him out of Òyó.

It is worth noting that it is the result of the greater impact of the counter intrigue, (or just reaction in the case of Oba Kò So) that leads to inevitable resolution in the four plays.

4.3.2.2 Development of Conflict Through Direct Confrontation.

The pattern of conflict development in Beyif ò Se and Oba Wàjà is based on direct confrontation and/or open antagonism between the protagonist and an imperialist superior power. The protagonists in the plays cannot defend their stands effectively against the imperialist and it is this incapability that leads to their tragedy. In Obá Wàjà the D.O. is the representative of the colonial

imperialist power while Aólẹ stands for the imperialist power of the Aláàfin in the pre-colonial era of Yorùbá history.

In Ọbá Wàjà, the D.O., by imprisoning Olórí Èlẹsin Ọba breaches the age-long Ọyọ tradition of ritual suicide on the death of the Aláàfin. This leads to a dilemma for Olori Èlẹsin Ọba who is heavily chided with a series of derisive songs by the Ọyọ populace. He, however, retires to the comfort of his house after being released by the D.O. on the promise that he will no longer perform the ritual. The dialogue which he has with the Aláàfin's ghost serves as the bleak index to a catastrophic dénouement.

Aláàfin:

Know then; that I shall not enter
the gate of heaven unattended, I
have chosen my new attendant. And
you will pay for your betrayal.
The white man's law will not
protect you from my wrath.

(Beier 1964: 64-65)

The development of the conflict in Béyif ò Se does not take off promptly after conflict introduction as in

the other plays. The oracular introduction of the conflict in this play, it should be noted, is neither clear to the audience nor to Baálẹ̀ Apòmù, the protagonist. It therefore allows for an initial suspense. On the other hand, it is in the events that immediately follow that we have a clear background information on the main conflict of the play¹⁹. Baálẹ̀ Apòmù receives a message, through the Ọ̀nì of Ifẹ̀, from Alááfin Abiọ̀dun, instructing him to check the selling of Ọ̀yọ̀ indigenes into slavery in his domain.

The development of the conflict in Ọ̀bá Wàjà shows clearly that the conflict is primarily based on cultural differences but that of Béyí ọ̀ Se as will presently be discussed is based on revenge. Prince Aólẹ̀, Alááfin Abiọ̀dun's son is caught selling his servant, Akanbí, into slavery at ọ̀jà Apòmù and he is arraigned before Baálẹ̀ Apòmù. The baálẹ̀, in his enthusiasm to carry out Alááfin Abiọ̀dun's injunction, orders that Aólẹ̀ be given twenty-four strokes of the cane. He would have ordered a stiffer punishment were Aólẹ̀ not an Ọ̀yọ̀ prince²⁰. The seed of the conflict in the main part of the plot is thus sown, for fourteen years after, when Aólẹ̀ comes to the

throne, he asks for Baálẹ̀ Apòmù's head in revenge or, in the alternative, that Apòmù be razed to dust. The dilemma of Baalẹ̀ Apòmù is worsened by the fact that his immediate superior, the Oṣoni of Ifẹ̀, through whom Aláàfin Abíòdún's message is originally sent has refused to give him any type of support. The Baálẹ̀, however, decides to save Apòmù by committing suicide.

The death of Baálẹ̀ Apòmù no doubt resolves the primary conflict, but another loosely connected conflict develops after Baálẹ̀ Apòmù's death and this conflict serves as an epilogic conclusion to the events of the plot as a whole.

4.4 THE DÉNOUEMENT: RESOLUTION OF CONFLICT.

As our discussion in the last section must have shown, the general plotal trend of the eight mythico-historical plays is towards tragedy. In fact, Duro Ladipo has, on account of this, been regarded as the foremost tragic dramatist in the Ogunde dramatic tradition (see Beier 1964: 75 and Jeyifo 1984: 101). A close look at the

dénouement of the plays under analysis reveals a dominant pattern of plotal conclusion. The tragic trend built up in the development or complication of the conflict is most of the time transcended. Obá Wájá is the only example, out of the eight plays, in which the tragic trend in the plot is not transcended at the resolution point²⁴. Our focus here is, however, mainly on the tragedy transcending resolution of the other seven plays.

In this dénouement pattern, in spite of the fatality of the preceding event, there is a general psychological sense of satisfaction, from the deificational and/or other pleasing event of the resolution. Şàngó in Oba Kò So, Olúorogbo and Mọ̀rẹ̀mi in Mọ̀rẹ̀mi, Ọ̀bàtálá in Ọ̀bàtálá and Ọ̀şun and Ọ̀bà in Ọ̀şun are all clearly deified in the plays. The deification leaves a satisfactory impression on the spectators that the suffering and/or selflessness of these characters are appreciated. This psychological satisfaction is, for example, expressed by Mọ̀rẹ̀mi at the death of Olúorogbo:

...

È jẹ́ kí a máa jó, kí a máa yò;

Kí á kọ́ ojúbọ

Fún ìrántí Olúorogbo

...

(Ladipo 1971: 52)

Let's dance and be happy;

We should build a shrine

In remembrance of Olúorogbo

The logic of this reasoning is founded on the Yorùbá metaphysical and philosophical view that the situation of an òrìsà in the other world is a pleasant one.

Similar analysis as the one above can be extended for the dénouemental events in Oba Mórò, Béyif ò Se and Ajagun-ńlá. Though the characters involved in the events, (Ológbo, Baálẹ̀ Apòmù, Oníkòyí and Ajagun-ńlá respectively), are not clearly deified, the textual indices of their òrìsà qualities lie in their heroism and the nature of their death or 'non-death' which are comparable to those of the five characters treated above. Oníkòyí and Ajagun-ńlá transmogrify by dissapearing into the earth under a fig tree and by turning into a hill

respectively. Our extra-textual knowledge of the characters, however, corroborates our considering them as semi-gods, if not gods. They belong to a special class of ancestors worshipped generally by a clan orilẹ rather than an individual family. Ológbo is worshipped by the ológbòjò clan of masqueraders, Oníkòyí and Ajagun-ńlá by the ìkoyí and the Ìgbómìná respectively. These tribes cut across major Yorùbá towns. It is only Baálẹ̀ Àpòmù that is in this sense restricted to Àpòmù.

There is, however, another basis for the tragedy transcending resolution in these plays. The resolution in Obátálá is essentially a happy one despite the tragic trend in the main part of the plot. Obátálá is finally released from prison and on the meta-symbolic level through the deificational evidence his lost glory is restored to him once he has paid dearly for his primordial error. The purpose for which Olúorogbo dies and for which Mọ̀rẹ̀mì loses her only son in Mọ̀rẹ̀mì is achieved. The Ifẹ̀ people finally defeat the Ìgbò. Similarly in Oba Mórò and Ajagun-ńlá the respective troubles that lead to Ológbo's death and Oníkòyí's

transmogrification are ameliorated. Hence the situations can be seen as pleasing despite the tragic price paid for it. In Oba Mórò the Ọyómèsì's malevolent antagonism to Aláàfin Abipa's noble move is finally crushed and in Ajagun-ńlá the riotous children of Olúgbón and Àrẹ̀sà are calmed and are made to realize the negative effect of their action.

In Bevíf ọ̀ Se, that Aólẹ̀, out of his egocentric vindictiveness gets entangled in similar but more ludicrous tragic situation into which he has initially unjustly put Baalẹ̀ Apòmù cannot but be satisfying to the spectators. After he has received the head of Baalẹ̀ Apòmù from the diviner, Aólẹ̀, imbued with a fresh desire for revenge, asks his army to match against Afọ̀njá, the generalissimo who is constituting a threat to his government. When Afọ̀njá gets wind of the plan he quickly besieges Ọyọ̀ and sends for Aólẹ̀' s head. Aólẹ̀ orders his chief hunter to shoot him down in the market. One realises that it is in order to achieve a pleasing effect on the audience that Duro Ladipo codifies the Yorùbá concept of the law of retributive justice by conjoining his adaptation of the story of the last part

of Aólẹ's life (see Johnson 1921: 192) to the main part of the dramatic plot. This concept is indicated in the prophecy of the diviner to both Baálẹ Apòmù and Aólẹ respectively that "Beyí ò ẹ ọmí ọ ẹ"²⁷, (If this doesn't happen, another will happen") from which the play derives its title.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the deificational basis for the tragedy transcending resolution is not unconnected with the one just discussed as hinted in the case of Obátálá above. It is, for example, because of the final realization and appreciation of the tragic characters' worth that they are deified. The happy and satisfactory tendencies and implications in the dénouements constitute the indices of the tragedy transcending signification. The plays can in this sense be rightly regarded as tragi-comedies. But it should be noted that the tragedy is, in all the plays, not removed but only transcended. The tragic and the non-tragic (or comic) are binarily united.

ADAPTATIONAL STRUCTURE

4.5
 The main focus of this section is the specification of the differences between the plot (signifier system) and the underlying mythico-historical story-line from which it is adapted (signified system) in order to show the extent of the competence involved in plotal construction. The discussion of the general structure of suspense and dramatic irony is also included as aspects of plot adaptation.

There are two general patterns of adaptation in the construction of plays under analysis. In the first one, events that are elaborated in the source story are economically codified, while in the second, events and issues referred to in the source story are elaborated in the plot. Such adaptational steps no doubt imply inclusion and/or exclusion of events in the source story as the case may be. Certain events are at times totally altered for effective dramatic adaptation.

The crowd scenes, and there are quite a good number of them in the eight plays, are for example, usually presented economically on stage by a few people. We can cite an example of where Şangó is expected to kill

many of his subjects towards the dénouement of Oba Kò So (1972: 54). Only a few people are logically presented as killed in the stage performance. A more striking case of economy of detail can be found in Oba Mórò. The Alááfin according to Johnson (1921: 165) sent six brave hunters, (Bóni, Igişubu, Alegbata, Lọkọ, Gbandan and Oloṃọ) to capture the ghost mummers at the Ajáká hill, but in Duro Ladipo's dramatic adaptation only the chief hunter, Olúṣẹ Obéńbélọşù is sent. This economical presentation allows for a more spectacular dramatic presentation of the scene where the six ghost mummers are captured by the hunter through the use of a mesmerising incantation. Such a presentation will no doubt live a lasting impression on the audience. In Béyí ò Se Duro Ladipo contracts what seems like a long story by accelerating the events towards the dénouement. According to Johnson (1921: 188-192) the Oyo army went to Afọnjá in Ilorin on the order of Aólẹ and led him to Iwéré, a naturally fortified town, as the town which he is expected to capture within the conventionally stipulated period of three months. Aólẹ's intention was to force Afọnjá into committing suicide according to

custom, since he would naturally not be able to accomplish the task within the stipulated time. Some disgruntled leaders conspired with Afọnjá and the royal team was massacred at the foot of Íwéré. They then left for Ọyọ where they lay siege and demanded for Aólẹ's head. Dúró Ladipọ in his own adaptation makes Afọnjá and his army lay the siege against Ọyọ even before the royal army has got out of the city, so that the Íwéré episode is left out. Also omitted is the story of the disgruntled leaders of the Ọyọ team. Similarly in the presentation of Aólẹ's death, the historical course ascribed to Aólẹ before his suicide through poisoning and which is considered to be responsible for the diversity among the Yorúbá today, is omitted²³. We should note that whereas Aólẹ committed suicide in Johnson's account by poisoning himself, Duro Ladipọ makes him to order his chief hunter to gun him down in the market place.

A similar adaptation takes place in the dramatic codification of Ológbo's death in Oba Mórọ. In the historical account, Ológbo is said to have been poisoned by the Ọyómèsi while in the dramatic adaptation he is strangled to death by them. In these two cases, the

dramatic codification is more captivating than the historical one.

The common examples of plotal elaboration on sparse information in the source story can be found in the introduction ^{of} events such as those in the Marriage scene in Ajagun-ńlá, the Ghana scene in Obá Wájà, the Ọ̀nì palace scene in Beyìf ò Sẹ, and the Igbó Ajé scene in Oba Kò So. Whereas proper references are, for example, made to the marriage scene (Adebara 1981: 16) and the Ọ̀nì palace scene (Johnson 1921: 189) in the respective source stories, the information on which the Igbó Ajé scene is based is very vague. The information as Hethersett (1941: 52) puts it is "Gbòkǎ mura ... " ("Gbònká prepared ..."). These scenes are structured into the plot not only to serve as links between other parts and to provide information for certain actions but also for the adaptational purpose of creating suspense. The scenes form the climax in plotal development just before the peripeteia. At this crucial point when the audience's focus is directed towards an expected change, the scenes are introduced to delay the materialization of the anticipated event. The example from Oba Wájà

will sufficiently illustrate the situation. When the Alááfin's ghost predicts that Olórí Èlẹ̀ṣin Ọ̀ba cannot escape the fatal consequence of his betrayal, we are intrigued to see the realization of the prediction. Instead, the Ghana scene is introduced to show us how Dáwódù gets to know of Alááfin's death, which also imply his father's death (see Beier 1964: 64-65). This scene is not very crucial to the main events and plotal development of the play. It could, in fact, have been effectively reported without any serious effect on the plotal structure.

A case of elaboration on the source material that should not be left out is that found in Mọ̀rẹ̀mi. All events surrounding the character of the Igbò diviner, Díbía, are improvised by Duro Ladipọ into the plot. It is Duro Ladipọ's attempt to explain the details of how Mọ̀rẹ̀mi gets at the root of the Igbò masquerade secret. A detail not found in any extra-textual account. According to Johnson's account 1921: 147) the Igbò masqued warriors are simply taken as spirits, but Duro Ladipọ's adaptation shows that it is a special charm prepared for the Igbò warriors by Díbía that makes them fearful. It is the secret of this charm that Mọ̀rẹ̀mi obtains from Díbía.

This presentation is no doubt more convincing than the one in the source story.

*** There is no doubt that the popular nature of the story-line from which the plots are developed paves way for a potential dramatic irony in the plays especially during performance. A considerable number of the members of the audience may, for example, be familiar with the mythico-historical stories but how interesting the plotal-line is, will depend largely on the dramatist's adaptational skills. Duro Ladipo, however, taps this potential for dramatic irony competently in his adaptations. Let us illustrate with a few examples from Morèmi, which is considered one of the best adapted plays in Duro Ladipo's repertoire.

Though the audience is aware that in the source story, Morèmi goes to Ìgbò land on espionage, Dúró Ladipo, in an earlier part of his plotal adaptation, creates a brief tension in the audience through the argument that ensues in the royal council as to whether or not they should support her request to be allowed to go on espionage to Ìgbò land. Strong arguments based on custom are advanced against the case but the Oṣoni finally

overruled in favour of Mọrẹmi. There is also dramatic irony at the point where Ọba Ịgbò anxiously awaits his army from Ilé Ifẹ. The audience at this point is however aware that the army is on its way. This irony is, however, removed by Dibia's prediction about the imminent arrival of the warriors. Dibia's warning that Ọba Ịgbò should not keep any of the war spoils creates another brief irony against the background of the audience's knowledge of the story-line. The audience is made to believe that Mọrẹmi who has been taken captive by the Ịgbò warriors will be killed on arrival. This contradicts the story-line. The tension created is further held up when, on arrival, Ọba Ịgbò orders that Mọrẹmi should be killed. She is, however, released almost immediately because Ọba Ịgbò is already infatuated by Mọrẹmi's beauty. He therefore stops his men from carrying out his initial order.

The above explications have no doubt shown clearly that Duro Ladipo displays a high degree of competence in the adaptation of his plots. From the perspective of the analysis presented particularly in this section and generally in the whole chapter, it can be claimed that

Duro Ladipo has not followed his source stories to the disadvantage of dramatic excellence.

CHAPTER FOUR

NOTES

1. The hermenutic code is according to Barthes the code of enigmas or, in Scholes' explanation, code of puzzle, which borders on the reader's desire for "truth", for the answers to the question raised by the text (Scholes 1982: 100). Suspense, dramatic irony, surprise and other aspects of plotal structure are involved in the code. The proairetic code is the code of actions where the lineal arrangement is fully considered (see Barthes 1970: 19).
2. Also, see Jakobson (1960: 364-367) on verse design and delivery design on the one hand and verse instance and delivery instance on the other as an expansion of the langue/parole concept for poetry.
3. Though Scholes' observation is made in respect of Todorov's method, it is applicable to others' too.
4. This problem is not unrelated to the complexity of the dramatic/theatrical texts already referred to. Also, see Elam 1980: 185-207 and Serpieri *et. al* 1981: 165-200 for examples of such analysis of the dramatic text.

5. Oḷadejọ Okediji's Atótó Arére and Ṣàngó are the two examples of Yorùbá prose and dramatic narratives where sequentiality is given a higher priority over causality or consequentiality in an aesthetically dynamic way.
6. The evidence at the National archives, University of Ibadan, shows that the 1946 date of the historical event given in Beier (1964: 54), and which perhaps Ṣoyinka (1976: 6) follows, is incorrect. The correct date is 19th December, 1944. See Daily Times Dec. 21, 1944, West African Pilot of the same date and Akéde Ekó of Dec. 30 1944.
7. See 4.1.2.2 above for the derivational denotation of this name.
8. Classified as others, are the abodes of other characters: the houses of the D.O. and Olórí Èlẹ́ṣin Oba in O bá Wàjà, Oṣun's room in Oṣun and the camps of Oníkòyí and the Èṣṣòs in Ajagun-ńlá. Also belonging to the category are other places such as the beer palor and prison in O bá Wàjà, the place where Ògún and Obátálá drink palm-wine in Obátálá and Èḍe in O ba Kò So. See the discussion in 4.1.2.4 for our views on the vagueness of some of the settings. It can be noted from the table that the frequency of occurrence of Àfin, Igbórò and Ojà is enormously greater than that of all these other settings with a ratio of 19:6 and (8:3) for each of the countings respectively.

9. Following oral evidences from Okè Ilá and Adebara (1981), Ajagun-ílá whose actual name is Fágbáyílá is the first king in Ilá.
10. This presentation has a christian undertone because of the use of neo-traditional musico-poetic structures. The codification can be taken as an iconization of the heavenly throne as recorded in the Bible (Revelation 4). Such iconization is avoided in a similar dramatic context in Edá where traditional musico-poetic structures are employed.
11. See Ladipo 1971: 3-4, 12, 16 for references made to Mọremi as Iyalode oja Ifẹ and Olori Ọrànmiyàn. Also, see Chapter Five (5.2.2).
12. This technical signification is however not limited to the three plays. It is also worthy noting that there are versions of the play in print, of which Beier's (1963) edition is one, that do not include the festive opening scene.
13. This character is either known as Abọbaku or Olókunẹsin in the extra-text. The incident dramatized occurred in 1944 as noted in note one after the death of Alááfin Ládùgbòlù. Both Moses Ọláiyá Adéjumọ and Wọle Ọ́oyinka have also adapted the story as Abọbaku and Death and the King's Horseman respectively after the pioneer attempt of Duro Ladipo.
14. Kalejaye (1982) in his own adaptation of the Ọbátálá myth gives the staining of Ọbátálá's garment a

different symbolic interpretation. He sees it as the "eternal staining of man's life" (1982: 52).

15. The two objects can be seen as signifying certain supernatural powers which Ọbàtálá loses to Ọṣun as part of the punishment for his primordial error. Ijímèrè (1966) version does not include this incident.
16. In fact, such singing and dancing is incorporated into the materialization of the third intrigue of Eṣù and Ọṣun against Ọbàtálá. The handing over of the ẹ̀ẹ̀rìndínlógun is, for example, elaborately codified in the Ifá kíkì and ìyèrè Ifá chanting.
17. Duro Ladipo's and Ijímèrè's versions agree on this point, but Kalejaye's focus is not on the suffering but the symbolic interpretation (see footnote 13). Hence his codification of a hot-tempered Ọbàtálá.
18. For various versions of the story of the conflict between Ọbà and Ọṣun, see Bascom 1976: 149-165.
19. The Ijímèrè 1963 version of the play begins from this point. All the earlier festive scenes and oracular introduction of conflict are sliced off.
20. Aole, according to Johnson 1921: 188 is a cousin, not a son, of Aláàfin Bìṣdún. Duro Ladipo has probably adapted the information the way he has in order to make the situation more ridiculous.

21. The tragedy in *Ọba Wàjà* can be seen from four different angles: the angle of *Ọlori Èlẹ̀ṣin Ọba*, his family, the D.O. and the *Ọyọ* populace.
22. This line may also be poetically translated as "Whatever the case may be, the long arm of nemesis will catch up with the evil doer".
23. The possible reason for such an omission is that that aspect does not fall within his immediate thematic focus.

CHAPTER FIVE

CHARACTERIZATIONAL CODE

5. INTRODUCTORY NOTES

It will not be out of place to begin our discussion in this chapter by iterating, our earlier observation (in 1.2.1.1. above) that we are generally in the realm of iconic significations when treating the characterizational code. The textual characters, it has been noted, are similitudes of the mythico-historical personalities as they are conceptualized among the Yorùbá. The representation and presentation of these extra-textual concepts on stage (or elsewhere) by performers makes the dramatic iconization more apparent.¹

Structuralist activities (right from the formalist phase to the semiotic phase) in the area of character study can be said to demonstrate two major approaches. The first one, considers characterization as a subordinate aspect (a sub-code) of the plotal code. Important among exponents of this approach are Propp, Souriau, Dundes, Greimas and Todorov. They identify characters mainly by their "overall functions" (Elam 1980: 127) within the plot. Propp, Souriau and Greimas' models will suffice as examples in the following discussion.

Propp, the earliest among them, identifies seven "overall functions" which he calls "spheres of action" or "dramatis personae". Greimas and Souriau on the other hand identify six of such "functions" each of which they call "actantial roles" and "dramatic functions" respectively. While Souriau uses astrological concepts in labelling his "functions", Greimas uses linguistic concepts. The concepts used by Propp are the most literary of them. Here is a comparative outline of the three lists of characters' overall functions in a plot.²

Propp	Souriau	Greimas
Villain	Mars (Antagonist)	Opposant (Opponent)
Donor	-	-
Helper	Moon (Helper)	Adjuvant (Helper)
Sought for person/ and her father	Sun (Desired object)	Objet (Object)
-	The Scale (Arbiter, Rewarder)	-
Dispatcher	Earth (Receiver)	Destinateur (Sender)
Hero	Lion (Hero)	Destinataire (Receiver)
-	-	Sujet (Subject)
False hero	-	-

Fig. 8 : A comparison of Propp, Souriau and Greimas' Characters' Overall Plotal Functions.

Just as Scholes has noted in his own comparison of Propp's and Souriau's "overall functions" (1976: 105), a comparison of the three lists, despite the re-arrangement, does not match neatly. This can however, be traced to several factors ranging from the use of different data to differences in individual approach. Whatever the case may be, these writers have been able, through these functions, to categorize characters and derive underlying lineal structures for narratives. The approach does not do more than this. It is not capable of catering (or, more properly, it has not been stretched to cater), for the paradigmatic aspects of the characters, that is their extra-textual relations. Moreover, it should also be noted that not all the functions are relevant to all literary narratives. But the idea of hero and villain (protagonist and antagonist) is generally more relevant to many literary narratives than others. What is, however, clear even from the labels used by the three scholars in their character taxonomy, is that they are not primarily concerned with characters as individuals but with characters as participants in the continuous events of the narrative.

In the second approach the adaptation of semantic componential analysis in linguistics is suggested (See Culler 1975: 235; Fowler 1977: 33-37). The character is treated as a name (a tag) onto which a set or conglomeration of "characteristics" (Tomashevskij 1965: 88), "qualities" (Culler 1975: 235) "features" "traits" or "semes" (Fowler 1977: 34; Barthes 1974: 67) is attached. These features are deducible from both plotal and other spheres of the text. This second approach, as noted by Fowler and Culler, is not as developed as the first one. It is however worth noting that Ogunpolu (1979: 33-37) has applied it in his discussion of the two main characters in a folktale. At the "initial level" of the tale he summarises the attributes of the two characters as follows:

Senior Wife

- + age
- + power
- + wealth
- + peace
- obedience
- silence

Junior Wife

- age
- power
- wealth
- peace
- + obedience
- + silence

and by the end of the story the situation has changed to

Senior Wife

- + age
- power
- wealth
- peace
- silence

Junior Wife

- age
- + power
- + wealth
- + peace
- + silence

Though not more than a mere summary of the situations, as Ogunpolu himself clearly indicates, there is no doubt that the presentation is pedagogically and analytically very useful. It presents the situations at a glance and further deductions can easily be made. It is, however, as Ogunpolu himself realises, a means to an end.

Ogunpolu's data being a very simple one lends itself easily to such an analysis. The problem of systematization arises in a more complex text where a character has many features and where there are many characters to consider for oppositional possibilities. The character's set of traits may also change several times. These are the problems to which the present writer has no immediate answer and which has probably kept this approach from being utilized by others too.³ We are therefore only going to adopt the concept of the approach in our analysis and marry the first approach to it by treating overall

plotal function as a characterizational feature. This step will allow us to consider characterization as a full-fledged code and characters as individuals while not neglecting the first approach totally. The character himself can be taken as a big sign or text while the traits or features used in characterizing him can be seen as smaller signs. There is therefore a complex interplay of significations in the iconization of characters.

In the following discussion, we will first of all consider some of the iconizing features in general before we go on to discuss their particular structures and significations in the iconization of some selected characters.

5.1.0 CHARACTERIZATIONAL FEATURES

The features, as far as the characters are concerned, form the signifier/signified interplay in which the characters are iconised. A feature as our analysis will further show can either be a signifier or a signified in the code. We shall discuss below character identificatory features, overall plotal function, and behavioural features. The social role features as will be shown are manifest in both the identificatory and behavioural categories. They are therefore not treated separately.

5.1.1.0 Characterizational Identificatory Features

By character identification is meant the recognition of the obvious features that differentiate one character from another. These features are collectively referred to as "the mask" by Tomashevskij (1965: 188). He considers the mask as "the development of concrete motifs in harmony with the psychology of the character". Examples of such concrete motifs include external appearance, clothes, and the furniture in the character's apartment. The mask according to Tomashevskij need not be applied only to visual appearance of a character; it may take other forms. 'The very name of the hero may serve as his mask' (1965: 88-89).

There are scholars who do not consider character identification as part of characterizational method. Garvey (1978) is such a scholar. He writes (1978: 63):

We must distinguish identification of character from characterization. Identification involves simply the attribution of a name (e.g. 'the lonely stranger') to an argument of a narrative deep structure proposition. Characterization on the other hand, invests an identified character with an attribute or sets of attributes (also called 'traits', 'qualities' or

'characteristics') which add descriptive material of a particular sort to the argument node.

However, Yorùbá attitude to names, general appearance, including costume, and one's surroundings, as indices of the character's personality coupled with the semiotic basis of this work does not encourage us to share Garvey's view.

5.1.1.1 Names

The name, to the Yorùbá, and to Africans in general, is a double plane semiotic system. On the first plane, the name as an identifying signifier denotes the person or character (the signified) who answers to the name. This plane of name semiotics is a universal one. On the second plane, the name is also believed to be the signifier of the historical, sociological and psychological behavioural patterns of the character.⁴ This latter plane, which might have been, like the first one, universal in diachrony, is today no more popular in industrialised communities. It is, however, still widely accepted in many non-industrialised societies. Since Garvey is from an industrialised society one is,

therefore, not surprised about his view.

The semiotic relevance of names among the Yoruba is apparently indicated in the phono-syntactic and semantic structures of their names. Most, if not all, Yoruba names are derived nouns, that is, most names are compressed sentences or phrases. When the phrasal sentential or morphological pattern of a name is not recognisable, the most probable reason is that such a pattern is lost in diachrony or hidden in dialectal variants. The morpho-syntactic structures of names are revealing of aspects of the personality of a character.

The three types of names that are common in the iconization of characters in the plays under examination include "christening" names (orúko abiso), title and other role names (orúko oyè/ipò) and praise names/nicknames (oríki/inagije)⁵. Examples of christening names include Qmọlọlá in Ajagun-ńlá, Aólẹ̀, Adépońnlé and Ifábòdé in Béyí ò Se. Title and other role names are more preponderant than the other two types.

Examples include Olúgbón, Arẹ̀sà and Olúkòyí in Ajagun-ńlá who are lords of Igbón, Ìrẹ̀sà and Ìkòyí towns respectively as indicated in the syntactico-semantic structure

of Olúgbón < olú Igbón (lord of Igbón) and Olúkòyí < Olú Ikòyí (lord of Ikòyí). Other examples include Başòrun, Aşípa, Lagùnnà Akinikù, Bísà and Ológbo in Oba Mòrò. The first four are title names of members of the Qyómèsl royal council of Qyó. Also prominent is the title name Aláàfin in Oba Kò So, Oba Mòrò, Qbàtálá and Qsun. Aláàfin is the supreme ruler of Qyó town (and its kingdom in the past). There are role names such as Olúòdẹ in Oba Mòrò and Beyíí ò Se which indicate the chief hunter [Olú àwon ode (lord of the hunters)] and Awo a shortened form of babalawo (Ifá priest) in Ajagun-ńlá, Beyíí ò Se (and Mòrèmi).⁶

Some examples of praise names have been treated in Chapter Three. Oríkì is usually a corpus of praise names of which nick names are part. Such names usually emphasize behavioural and physical features of the character. Şàngó as shown in Chapter Three is for example Ewégbèmí < ewé gbè mí (Herbs-favour-me) and Awúrelà < A + wú + òrè + là (He-who-prospers-by-saying-incantative-prayers) and Mòrèmi is Ajàşorò < A + jà + şe + orò (One who fights as if performing a ritual) and Abòjẹ-pòpòpò < Abi + òjẹ pòpòpò (One-with-very-long-sash). These names

are emphasizing the herbal knowledge of Şàngó and Mọrèmi's patrotic zeal and maternal qualities respectively.

Whereas the christening name is given at birth, the title and other role names and the praise names are acquired during one's life. It should be noted at this juncture that the names of certain archetypal characters (the òrìṣà to be specific) are generally not easily classifiable into one of the groups discussed above. But taking into consideration the fact that the Yorùbá, especially in their mythologies, usually lay greater emphasis on the life of the òrìṣà than his nativity and childhood, one will probably not be wrong to classify the names of the òrìṣà as praise names. Examples of such orìṣà include Şàngó, Mọrèmi, Qya, Qṣun, Qbà, Eṣù, Qbàtálá and Ajagun-ńlá.

Our analysis of how the syntactico-semantic signification of some of the names further helps in a clear iconization of the characters will be considered in our treatment of individual characters below. It suffices to say here, that the phono-syntactic roots of these names are very relevant to the behavioural codification of the characters bearing them in the plays. This

serves as a supportive basis for reaching the conclusion about classifying the names of the òrìṣà as acquired names. One cannot, but note at this point that hyper-signification is involved in the use of names in character iconization where a character is identified with more than one name. This method which is a carry-over from the extra-textual experience allows for an economical codification of many aspects of the character (see Bamgboṣe 1974: 78-79; Iṣṣàlá 1978: 170ff).

5.1.1.2 Costume, Make-up, Props and Setting

The fact that semiotic inferences about one's personality can be drawn from one's general appearance and surrounding is universal (see Fouquier 1982 and Eninger 1984). There are sayings among different people all over the world that confirm this (See Fouquier 1982: 181 for a list of such sayings). Examples of such sayings among the Yorùbá include:

Ìrínisí ní isọnilójò

One's appearance determines the type of reception one gets.

and

Bí a bá tí rín là á kóní

It is the way one conducts oneself that determines how other people perceive one.

General information (signifieds) that is usually codified through characters appearance in our texts derives from the professional and social class of the characters, the occasion of their appearance and other behavioural abilities.

The warriors in Qba Kò So, Ajagun-ńlá and Béyí ò Se are usually iconised in the traditional hunter outfits since hunters are also warriors in Yorùbá pre-colonial tradition. This explains the uniformity in the iconization of the warriors and the two chief hunters in Béyí ò Se and Qba Mórò respectively. Prominent among their paraphernalia are the smart jacket (gbérí oḍe) and the knee length trousers (dígò) for which full length trousers or knickers are sometimes substituted. Charms and other medicinal preparations are usually hung on the costume and appropriate hand props such as dane guns, bow and arrow (Timl) horns full of medicine (Gbònkáà and Oníkòyí), sacred wand (Ajagun-ńlá), clubs, cutlasses and spears are also held. These elements are, however, usually more pronounced in the iconization of the

war-lords (Ajagun-ńlá, Olúkòyí, Olúgbón, Arẹ̀sà, Tímí and Gbònkáà) than in the general iconization of the war boys. These iconizing features are appropriate in the general war contexts of the plays and in indicating the military and hunting professions of the respective characters. One can also say especially in the case of the war-lords that these identificatory features are meto-symbolic indices of their bravery and general martial expertise.

The costumes of the kings and his chiefs in the plays are generally alike. They are made up of the large flowing gown made out of the traditional woven material with appropriate trousers (usually *kẹ̀nbẹ̀*) and the abetí ajá or ikòrì cap to match. The king may at times wear the beaded crown. The chiefs usually hold large leather hand fans while the king holds a horse tail whisk. The embroidery on the king's garment is usually more elaborate. The same thing applies to the use of beads by the king and chiefs. This iconization is found in all the plays under consideration.

Female characters such as Mọ̀rẹ̀mí, Ọ̀yá and Ọ̀bà are usually made up of a wrapper (ìró) made from traditional woven material, an additional long piece that is sometimes

thrown over a shoulder as iborùn or tied over the wrapper as ipèlé with or without a head gear, (gèlè). The iró is usually wrapped round most of their body leaving the shoulders bare as is done by the extra-textual olori. The female notables also usually have beautiful hair-do when the head gear is not used and strung-beads are also used as neck-laces and bracelets. The costume, and hair-style of other female characters, who do not use beads, are generally not as rich and colourful as those of the royal wives.⁷

It can be seen from our discussion that the war-lords, kings and royal wives are constantly foregrounded through full, rich and beautiful costuming against the background of the war-boys, chiefs and other female characters, whose costumes are not as full, rich, and colourful. This helps a memorable iconization of the foregrounded characters.

5.1.2 Overall Plotal Function and Behavioural Features

The overall plotal function and behavioural features are based on the actions and reactions of the characters. The behaviour summarises the constant actions and/or reactions of a character within related situations.

The overall function, as the name suggests, is, on the other hand, a total summary of the actions and reactions, or in other words, a summary of the behavioural features. The two overall plotal functions (or actantial roles) treated in this work are those of the protagonist and antagonist. The two roles are crucial to plotal development. The protagonist's decision, struggles and actions, in general, usually form the primary pivot on which the plot rotates. Şàngó, Mọrèmi, Qbátálá, Baálẹ̀ Apòmù, Olúkòyí, Abíípa and Olórí Èlẹ̀şin Qba belong to this class in the eight plays being analysed. The antagonist, on the other hand, is the major character that stands in an oppositional relation to the protagonist. His actions usually constitute problems for the protagonist. The Qyómèşì, Qba Igbò, Eşù, D.O., Aólẹ̀ and Qbà constitute this group in our data. The two features are very useful as a categorizational tool. They do not only give a total picture of the characters' actions; all other characters can, in many cases, also be classified according to the two overall plotal functions.

Before we can conclude that a character has a certain behaviour, we should ideally take more than one evidence from his actions and/or reactions within logically similar situations. The compressed nature of actions in dramatic texts (in comparison with those in other forms of literature and life in general), however, makes a relaxation of this ideal necessary for our purpose. A major action or reaction that is of dynamic importance to a relationship between characters or to plotal development, even when it occurs only once, can still be seen as a signifier of a character's behaviour. Extra-textual evidence may, however, be used as supportive signifiers of the behavioural trait where such evidence exists.

Examples of behavioural features codified in the plays under analysis include warlikeness, versedness in herbal knowledge, irrationality, maternal love, slyness, diplomacy, arrogance, vindictiveness, patriotism, intrigue-scheming, blackmail, humility, considerateness, coquettishness, endurance, chastity, carefree attitude and light heartedness etc. The list, it should be noted, is not comprehensive. The evaluative categorization of these behavioural traits into positive (good) or negative

(bad) runs into problem in the context of most if not all the plays.

In most cases opposing behavioural features are codified in the iconization of a character. One of them, is, however, usually dominant. So that if the negative one is dominant, we tend to see the character as bad and when the positive one is dominant we tend to see him as good. The protagonist in most cases is dominantly usually codified in the positive behaviour while the antagonist is also dominantly usually codified in the negative behaviour. We therefore tend to see the protagonist as the hero and the antagonist as the villain. But it should be stressed that the concept of villainy codified in the plays, is not that of a completely bad person. The antagonists are, from their own angles of the situations, justified in their actions. The protagonists are, in most cases, either directly or indirectly responsible for the antagonistic actions they receive. Hence we are forced to exercise great restraint in referring to the antagonists as villains.

The binary oppositional factor operating in the character codification of the plays allows for balanced characterization. We should also note that the behavioural

features emanate from the "fulfilment or non-fulfilment" of social roles in which the characters are codified (Işçla 1978: 116; Izevbaye 1981: 170). It is however in the analysis below, of selected individual characters that the full picture of our discussion above will be adequately illustrated.

5.20

THE PROTAGONISTS

The four protagonists selected for detailed study here are Şàngó, Mòrèmi, Qbátálá and Baálè Apòmù. It should be mentioned that the recurrences of a character in plays where he is not a protagonist are treated along here in as much as such recurrences illuminate our understanding of the character. This procedure is also in principle applicable to our subsequent discussion of the other category of characters.

5.2.1 Şàngó

Though Şàngó features in three of the plays under study, it is only in Qba Kò So that he is a protagonist. He is a non-antagonist in the other two plays, Òşun and Qbátálá. His social status as the supreme war-lord and

ruler, however, remains constant in the three plays. Şàngó is theatrically always iconised by Duro Ladipo himself before his demise. As expected, the stout physique and other idiosyncratic features of Duro Ladipo have been stamped into the character of Şàngó. These features are missing in recent performances of Qba Kò So where Ajéwọlé (Bàbá Ijẹṣà), who is considerably smaller in stature now plays the role.

The physical identificatory features with which Şàngó is codified include a jacket called ẹ̀wù owó (cloth of money) because cowry shells which served as currency in the past, are sewn all over it. There is also the long red skirt on which some cowries and flaps of clothes are sewn (làbà Şàngó). The plaited hair (Oṣù Şàngó) is iconised in the carved head-gear worn by the iconiser. The Oṣé (the carved double-edged wooden axe) and seéré (pendulous gourd rattle) are also attached to Şàngó as hand properties. The emission of fire from the mouth is another of such identificatory features. All these features, with the exception of the head-gear, are directly borrowed from the extra-textual elégùn Şàngó (Şàngó empathiser) context. The oṣù Şàngó is, however, indirectly borrowed through the eégun alaré iconization

of the plaited hair (see Götrick 1984: 97, 102).

Since in the extra-textual ritual context the elégùn Şàngó is himself a meto-symbolic iconization of Şàngó, the theatrical iconization of Şàngó on stage through the elégùn paraphernalia can therefore be seen as an indirect iconization. The third level of the iconization process can be seen in the use of the carved plaited hair, which is already an indirect iconization. There is therefore a double indirect iconization at this level.

These iconizing identificatory features when taken as signs in themselves are on a meto-symbolic level revealing Şàngó's behavioural nature. The features can be patterned into a binary system so that features on one side of the binarism are seen as signifying "masculinity" while features on the other side are seen as signifying "femininity".

The osé, sééré, èwù owó, the predominant red colour of the costume, emission of fire from the mouth and the lrùkèrè (horse-tail whisk) are all meto-symbolic iconisers of Şàngó as a king with a deep knowledge of Yorùbá metaphysics and herbal science. All these elements are predominantly attached to masculinity (òkùnrin) among

the Yorùbá. On the behavioural level, Şàngó is also partly codified as a tough, powerful, warlike and unpredictable character. These behavioural features are also generally attached to masculinity.⁸ Hence our submission that the identificatory features can be seen as meto-symbolic signifiers of the behavioural features. The identificatory masculine features of Şàngó are common to the three plays. But the behavioural ones are predominantly found more on the musico-poetic code level in Oba Kò So than on the plotal code level. Apart from the praise names already analysed as signifying Şàngó's herbal knowledge above, there are other poetic descriptions used in codifying his supernatural power. He is for example described as

Akọkọlúkọ ẹbọ tí í pagun lẹrù

(Ladipo 1970: 2)

Enormous sacrifice too much for the vulture

(Ladipo 1970: 68)

and

Orişà tí í bológbò lẹrù

(Ladipo 1970: 2)

The god who frightens cats

(Ladipo 1970: 69)

Igún (vulture) or eye (bird) in general and ológbò (cat) are meto-symbolic signifiers of witches among the Yorùbá.⁹ If Şàngó (signified) is both the enormous sacrifice and the frightful deity (signifier) then the appropriate interpretation of the hyper-signification is that Şàngó is out of the reaches of the witches and even more powerful.

All the examples of Şàngó's character codification cited above are ironical if the general trend of Qba Kò So's plot is taken into consideration. This ironical situation is however restricted to Qba Kò So.¹⁰

In Qbátálá Şàngó is seen leading his men to war not caring much about what happens at home. He is restless, highly impatient and unpredictable in handling even state matters. These behavioural signifieds are codified when Şàngó hastily orders the imprisonment of Qbátálá even before setting his eyes upon him. This behaviour is against the Yorùbá norm codified in the following axiom - "agbéjò-ẹnikan-dá, àgbà òşikà" ("one-who-listens-only-to-one-side-of-a-case-in making-judgement, is a

wicked elder"). Şàngó after this incident restlessly leads his men to war. When the complaints about the drought and famine that result from the unjust imprisonment of Qbàtálá are brought to Şàngó on his return from war, like a concerned leader he sends for the diviner to investigate the cause. He also decides to further investigate when it is oracularly revealed that the hardship is due to the imprisonment of an innocent person. But he suddenly changes his mind without any reason and decides rather to go on a fresh military campaign than to find a solution to the pressing problem before him. He says:

Ifá èé puró
 Bí í bá tí í rí ni ó wíí
 Ta a ni ì báà şe?
 Taa laláìşe,
 Tí ... ñ bẹ lánhámó?
 Tí ó mọ á fìyà jẹ á lóde Ọyó?
 Bó bá jẹ bẹẹ
 A á wádí ẹ ni
 Ọya ò !
 Orírl!!
 Toguntogun ní ñ şe mi
 Ì ñ loogun
 Bébi ó pa ín
 Ó pa ín

an unseen power directing him - a sort of empathy or trance - that usually grips people who are deeply knowledgeable in herbal practice and are power-drunk (it is called páàgùn among the Yoruba.¹¹ Şàngó's oríkì (those referred to above and others that signify his toughness) agree with this type of actions described above.

It is also a similar type of irrational behaviour on the part of Şàngó that throws the royal household into pandemonium in Òsun, when Şàngó openly displays his love for Òsun, a new wife, in the presence of her senior co-wives and even rearranges the cooking roster. This is, as said above (4.3.1.1), contrary to Yorùbá practice in a polygamous context.¹²

This codification of Şàngó's character seems to support the common belief that Şàngó in Dúró Ladipọ's plays, especially Ọba Kò So, is tyrannical (Adedeji 1973b: 71; Şoyinka 1976: 56). From another perspective expressed in Şàngó's oríkì and other aspects of Şàngó's character, one however wishes to exercise restraint in agreeing totally with Adedeji and Şoyinka. The oríkì is as follows:

You think the worm is dancing
 -but that is merely the way it walks
 You think Şàngó is fighting you
 -but that is merely the way he is.¹

(Beier 1964: 8)

Şàngó's tough nature cannot but be related to his warlike nature. Warriors are by the nature of their profession not gentle in character. They are toughened by the inhuman and brutal aspects of war. If the military profession is seen as patriotic and if the toughness of the military man is considered as psychologically rooted in the binarism of the patriotism accompanying the brutal inhumanity of war then Şàngó's irascibility and general toughness should probably be tolerable. It should, however, also be borne in mind that the militarism of Şàngó in which his toughness is anchored is socio-politically conditioned. If a powerful image is not built up for Ọyó, other powerful external forces may subdue her. It is, however, the other side of Şàngó's character that makes his toughness more tolerable.

The other side of Şàngó has to do with the identificatory features signifying femininity. The identificatory features are the plaited hair and làbà which are, outside

ritual context predominantly identified with femininity (obinrin). The làbà is, for example, outside the Şàngó and general ritual contexts yèrì (skirt), which are worn mainly by females. Similarly the plaited hair which is called oşù in the Şàngó ritual context is also àgogo hair-style usually worn by brides in the extra-Şàngó ritual context. The one which Qya wears has no ritual signification; it signifies the àgogo hair-style. These significations can in turn also be seen as indicating the gentle and considerate behaviour in which Şàngó is also codified because women are known more for these behavioural traits than men.

It is, however, in Qba Kò So that this aspect of Şàngó is more behaviourally codified than in the other plays. He is codified as a king who loves and does his best to satisfy the yearnings of his people. If the expansionist programme carried out by his two warlords is primarily considered as patriotic, then his initial opposition to his subjects' request, that the campaign should stop is understandable. Şàngó probably sees the people as ingrates who do not appreciate the grandeur of expansionism and the self sacrifice involved in such

programme. Şàngó's aggression, however, later gives way to the other side of his nature when he accepts Qya's advice to listen to his people's yearnings (Ladipo 1970: 11). Şàngó therefore goes to the extent of begging his warlords not to go on fresh military campaigns, but to no avail (Ladipo 1970: 12-13). The adamant reaction of the warlords and Şàngó's commitment to satisfying his people's yearnings make him take advice from both Qya and the Qyómèsi at different times on how to get rid of one or both of his war-lords (Ladipo 1970: 15, 24, 32). Unsuccessful intrigues are hatched against the war-lords and it becomes clear along the line that Şàngó is unable to control the situation (Ladipo 1970: 46-54). He therefore commits suicide by hanging.

The binary oppositional analysis can be presented diagrammatically as follows:

	FEMININITY	MASCULINITY	Signified
Identificatory Features	Plaited hair long skirt	Spitting of fire, Predominant red colour, <u>Osé</u> , <u>Sééré</u> <u>Irùkèrè</u>	Signifier ↓ Signified
Behavioural Features	Considerateness Gentleness	Metaphysical and herbal knowledge, Irrationality, Warlikeness	
	FEMININITY	MASCULINITY	Signified

Fig 9: The Binary oppositional analysis of the codification of Şàngó's character.

Şàngó's tragedy lies in the fact that his commitment to satisfying his people is from all angles not appreciated until after his death. His commitment to his people even goes beyond his death. He promises to continue to serve the Ọyó people even in death if they worship him (Ladipo 1970: 60). The Yorùbá proverb "bí a bá kú là á dèrè, èyàn ò sunwọ̀n láàyè" ("It is after one's death that one's god-like quality is appreciated, one is considered bad

while living") is clearly illustrated in Duro Ladipo's codification of Šàngó's apotheosization.

If the three plays where Šàngó features are viewed as a trilogy and the last lap of Šàngó's life presented in Oba Kò So is seen against the background of his youthful exuberance presented in the other two plays, Šàngó's tragic nature in Oba Kò So will become clearer. It will then be clear that it is the expansionist programme that Šàngó has built in his youthful warring days as codified in Obàtálá that backfires during his later years as codified in Oba Kò So when he decides to listen to his people and let their voice override his own. The irony in the fact that the programme can be seen as a patriotic one makes the tragedy more serious.

Taking the diachrony of the trilogy postulated above into consideration, the binary oppositional analysis of Šàngó's character can also be employed in explaining his tragedy. As a Yorùbá monarch, Šàngó is expected to strike a balance (ìwòntunwònsì) between the feminine and masculine signifieds. A balance between these two aspects is not struck in any of the three plays. In Obàtálá and Ọsun where Šàngó displays more of the masculine features, he tends more towards being tyrannical and his behaviour

contributes to the calamity of his people. On the other hand, in Oba Kò So where Şàngó displays more effeminate traits he tends towards being a weakling. He is, however, the one consumed in the tragic situation unlike in the other two plays.

5.2.2 Mòrèmi

The role of Mòrèmi has been constantly iconised by Biḡdun Duro Ladipḡ since the introduction of Mòrèmi into the Duro Ladipḡ repertory. The identificatory features in which Mòrèmi is iconised foreground her as a beautiful and rich royal wife (see 5.1.1.2 above). This iconization of Mòrèmi's beauty agrees with the extra-textual mythico-historical presentation and it is also plotally motivated (see 4.3.2.1.2 above).

Though textually presented as a royal wife after Johnson (1921: 47), Mòrèmi's relation to the throne is that of a princess (or at least a native of Ifè) according to Abírí (1970). Duro Ladipḡ follows the more popular account that Mòrèmi is from Òfà. This account makes the Patriotic gestures in which Mòrèmi's character is behaviourally codified striking. According to Adedeji

(1972: 131-132), Mọrèmi offered herself as hostage to save Qlófà (ruler of Ọfà) who was ordered to give himself as a ransom for planting cotton against Aláàfin's injunction. When Qrànmiyàn later came to Ọyó and questioned the Aláàfin's behaviour, the Aláàfin offered Mọrèmi in recompense. Mọrèmi therefore followed Qrànmiyàn to Ilé-Ife as wife. It is clear from this account that Mọrèmi is inherently patriotic.

Mọrèmi's patriotism and overall success as codified in the play can, however, be explained by the traditional legacy of the Ọfà indigenes. Ọfà progenitors and their successors are brave fighters. They are never defeated in wrestling and war. This fact is a major theme in the Qlófà lineage poetry, some of which says:

Atọkùnrin Ọfà
 Atobìrin Ọfà
 Nílé Onímọká o
 Èyí tí ò bá le jà ló yòlẹ nílé wa
 Ìjà pẹkí abẹ òwú
 Qmọ Qlálọmí aríjàsorò
 (Babalọla 1967: 111)

Both males of Ọfà
 And females of Ọfà
 In Onímọka's household
 It is he who can't fight that is lazy in
 our household
 Face to face fight under the cotton tree
 Ọlálọmí's offspring, whose ritual is fighting.

Mọrèmi is also praised textually and extra-textually as àjàsòrò (one who fights skilfully as if performing a ritual). This appellation is probably a carry-over from the Ọlọfà lineage poetry as reflected in the extract above. The conclusion that it is the Ọlọfà lineage traits in Mọrèmi that make her embark on the "suicidal"¹⁴ but highly patriotic venture successfully seems plausible in the light of the above explication.

Mọrèmi's patriotism is behaviourally codified in the play through a binary oppositional element for which she stands. In achieving her commendable patriotic goal of saving Ifẹ from complete ruin in the hands of the Ìgbò masqued invaders, Mọrèmi employs certain immoral methods. She has to be tough and blunt and she employs blackmail too.

We consider her bluntness in pointing out the truth to Q̄ṣni Aláyém̄ṣṣ and his chiefs too harsh and rude for someone newly installed as a chief. She speaks out of dissatisfaction and annoyance:

Etí yín melòó?
 È ní jó, è ní jẹ, è ní mu
 Ogun ti kó kete Ifẹ
 È dákẹ ni, è ní wò ni?
 Ogun ti kó kete ọmọ yín lọ!
 Ọgèdẹ ní bàjẹ, è ní ní pọn
 Ayé ní tojú yín bàjẹ, è ní ní dára
 Nígba ayé ọkọ mi Ọrànmiyàn
 Kò mà sóhun tó jorú èyí o;
 À ní filé pọntí, à ní fọnà rokà
 Akàrà wá dórí akáhn
 Ọ deegun

(Ladipo 1971: 12)

Attention!
 You are dancing, you are eating and drinking
 Wars have taken all Ifẹ into captivity
 Are you just going to keep mute, will you
 just look on?
 Wars have taken all your children away
 into captivity
 The banana is getting rotten
 You say it's ripening
 The world is in ruins in your time
 but you say it's getting better

During the reign of my husband Ọrànmiyàn
 There was nothing like this
 Then we stored the house with drinks
 and ate ọkà to our satisfaction
 When it is now the turn of the toothless
 one to eat àkàrà
 The àkàrà has become a bone

The devastating effect of Mọrèmi's challenge on the chiefs is expressed by their reaction stated in the "stage direction"¹⁵ that follows Mọrèmi's speech

Àwọ̀n ìjòyè bẹ̀rẹ̀ sí wo ojú ara wọ̀n,
 ìtíjù àtí ẹ̀rù dé bá wọ̀n, ìpayà sí dé
 sí inú ọkàn wọ̀n.

The chiefs start looking at one another;
 they become ashamed, and they are
 troubled in mind.

Mọrèmi has, through this speech prepared the ground for her progressive request which would have invited opposition.

Despite the fact that one of the chiefs supports Mọrèmi's request to investigate the secret behind the Ìgbò masquerade while the other argues in opposition that according to tradition it has never happened in Ifẹ̀ that

a royal wife should become a captive, Mọrẹmi intentionally infers that they are looking down on her because she is a woman.

Kín ni ọkùnrin fi ẹ̀e orí
 Yàtọ̀ sí obìnrin
 Ẹ̀ má ẹ̀e bomi tútù sí àníyàn mi
 Bí ọkùnrin bá le lẹ̀, ẹ̀ yan ẹnìkan
 Bí ẹ̀ kò bá fura
 Pé Ifẹ̀ lẹ̀ parun nípa àkíyèsára yín

(Ladipo 1971: 16-17)

What is the difference between
 A man's head and a woman's
 Do not discourage me from my resolve
 If a man can go, appoint one
 If you don't suspect
 That Ifẹ̀ can fall as a result of your
 carelessness

Thus we see Mọrẹmi using subtle blackmail and sarcasm on the chiefs to force them into supporting her plan.

A more serious blackmail is employed by Mọrẹmi to force the secret out of the reluctant Díbíá.

Díbíá! Díbíá!! Díbíá !!!
 Kín ni o wá ẹ̀e lódò emì ayaba?
 Ẹ̀e o fẹ̀ rí ìhòhò mi ni?
 O kò gbọ̀dò lẹ̀ níhìn-ín

Ìwọ àgbàlagbà aláínítíjù yí
 Bí o kò bá sọ kíákíá
 Agbára oògùn llayà tí o ẹ
 Èyí tí ó ní ẹ ẹrù ba èniyàn
 Oògùn tí ó wà lára egúngún Igbò
 Èmi yóò purọ mọ ọ lóḍḍọ ọba
 Pé o fẹ fi agbára rí ihòòhò mi
 Ọba yóò si pa ọ lónlí. (Ladipo 1971: 12)

Díbíá! Díbíá!! Díbíá!!!
 What do you want near me, the queen?
 Do you want to see my nakedness?
 You must not leave this place
 You this shameless old man,
 If you don't tell me immediately
 About the fearful magical charm
 That makes one afraid
 The charm used by Igbò masquerades
 I will lie against you before the king
 That you want to see my nakedness forcibly
 And the king will kill you today

These codifications of Mọrèmi's character are probably Duro Ladipo's innovations. But the coquettish dealings which Mọrèmi has with Ọba Igbò is carried over from the extra-textual characterization of Mọrèmi. During the 1986 Edí Festival at Ilé Ifẹ an Èmésẹ (court attendant) described Mọrèmi to us as afòbòsétè (One-who-overcomes-

a-crisis-through-her-female-organ). Considering the immediate micro-context of these actions, M̀orèmi is ethically immoral. But the ultimate macro-contextual goal, to save her sovereign land from ruin is highly commendable. This uncomplimentary aspect is played down in as much as it contributes to the articulation of a more noble goal.

When considered against the Yorùbá cultural value for children (especially male children) the gravity of M̀orèmi's patriotism is realised. The Yorùbá being patrilineal, usually pray for a decent heir.¹⁶ Barrenness and sterility are therefore tragic situations among them. Apart from this, a mother is also usually believed to be more sentimentally attached to the child than is the father because the child has its early life as a foetus in the mother's womb for nine months before it is born amidst child-birth pains (ìkúnlẹ̀ abiyamọ̀), and also because of the breast feeding and the special attention given to a child during its first few years.¹⁷ [M̀orèmi employs the child birth pains to appeal to Èsìnmínrín while pleading for Olúorogbo's life (Ladipo 1971: 21)]. In the light of these facts, one realises that M̀orèmi

makes one of the greatest sacrifices a Yorùbá mother can make, by offering her only son to the Èsalinrin river goddess who has assured her of success in the dangerous mission to Ìgbò land.¹⁸

If the name Mọ̀rẹ̀mí is derived from Omó rẹ̀ mí (I love children), then the name may be seen as ironical in the context of Olúorogbo's sacrificial offering. But if the whole of Ifẹ̀ is seen as her children as is, in fact, codified in one version of the source story (Abírí 1970: 35), then the meaning of the name will no more be ironical. Her social role status as olorí (royal wife) and iyálóde ojà Ifẹ̀ (leader of the Ifẹ̀ market women) qualifies her as the mother of the whole Ifẹ̀. In this larger context one can say that Mọ̀rẹ̀mí loves the people of Ifẹ̀ so much that she does not consider offering her biological child too much a sacrifice to make in order to save them from complete ruin. Whatever be the case, it should be noted that this presentation of Mọ̀rẹ̀mí as a ^{son} mother who wilfully offers her only/ to save her people is Duro Ladípọ̀' s innovation. According to Johnson's account (1921: 147) which Oyín Adejọ̀bí follows in his own dramatic adaptation, Mọ̀rẹ̀mí is "tricked" into the

tragic situation. But in Dúró Ladipọ's version the action is voluntary.

This point of departure makes Duro Ladipọ's codification of Mọrèmi's character more tragic than its presentation in the mythico-historical source story as well as in Oyin Adejọbi's version. In her patriotic moves to defend her sovereign land, she loses the most precious thing to her. The audience's traumatic experience is voiced out by Aláyémọrẹ:

Njẹ̀ èyí ni yóó jẹ̀ ẹ̀san fún Mọrèmi
Pé ó ní láti pàdánù
Ọmọ rẹ̀ kan ọ̀so?

(Ladipọ 1971: 47)

Is this Mọrèmi's reward
That she should lose
Her only child?

One can say that Duro Ladipọ has developed Mọrèmi from a tragic victim to a tragic heroine in his own dramatic adaptation.¹⁹

5.2.3 Qbátálá

The chastity or purity of Qbátálá is the signified to which all the characterizational signifiers are correlated. From this perspective, the desecration of Qbátálá, signified in his error and the subsequent trials which he undergoes help to set in relief his positive attributes with the result that balanced characterization can be argued for him.²⁰ Both the identificatory and behavioural features, as codified in his interaction with other characters, foreground the re-attainment of Qbátálá's purity of character. Other signifying and signified aspects of his characterization are kept at the background.

Qbátálá is primarily codified as a primordial emissary with the mission to create the world. Apart from his codification as an archetypal figure, Qbátálá is also codified as a royal figure, an qba, who is the central personality of a yam festival celebration scene at an early part of the plot (see 4.3.1.1 above). This codification is probably in order, as it accords with the meaning of the prefixing morpheme qba- in Qbátálá's name, which is probably etimologically derived from qba (king)

as suggested by Idowu (1962: 71) Idowu traces the derivation of the name to Qba tí ó níńlá (The king who is great) and Qba tí ààlà (The king in white clothing). The codification agrees also with the Yorùbá conceptualization of most of the archetypal figures as kings or important chiefs. Qbátálá is for example "Èní tí a bí lóde Ìgbò tó lẹ jọba lóde Iràńjé ("He who is born at Ìgbò town and goes to Iràńjé town to become king") (see Idowu 1962: 75). The greatness being referred to in the meaning of the first derivation is not unconnected with the purity of Qbátálá's character. This purity of character is also meta-symbolically signified in the white costume in which Qbátálá is clad throughout the play.

The restoration of Qbátálá's immaculate purity is connected with his suffering. It is the series of assaults heaped on Qbátálá through the machination of Èṣù without even an attempt at retaliation on his part, that marks Qbátálá out as a chaste person capable of controlling his emotions. Despite the fact that he has all the powers to retaliate, Qbátálá realizes that the assaults are the price he has to pay for his mistakes, and takes the mortifications with great humility (see 4.3.2.1.1. above for the nature of the assaults). Olódùmarè's acceptance

of Qbátálá's silent suffering as index of his total repentance is in turn indicated in the famine that plagues the length and breadth of Òyó where Qbátálá has been unjustly imprisoned. It is in the attempt to solve the problem of the famine that Qbátálá is discovered languishing in jail and released unconditionally.

From the decodification presented above Qbátálá may also be seen as a tragic figure in the occidental sense. His drunkenness will then be seen as the tragic flaw occasioning his sufferings. It is, however, the personal, rather than the communal, aspects of the tragedy that are foregrounded. This is ^{unlike} the case with Mọrèmi and Şàngó. One can therefore correctly say that the initial codification of Qbátálá as an oba is secondary in the general context of the play.

5.2.4 Baálẹ̀ Apòmù

As a baálẹ̀, Baálẹ̀ Apòmù is codified as a subordinate monarch under superior monarchs; the Alááfin of Òyó and the Qòni of Ifẹ.²¹ The behavioural codification of Baálẹ̀ Apòmù as a courageous man who offers his head to save Apòmù from destruction follows historical account

(Johnson 1921: 188-189). But his codification as light-hearted and care-free (as reflected in the way he participates actively in the merry-making and festivity in the opening palace scene and in his unwise disregard of oracular warnings) is Duro Ladipo's invention. According to Biṣṣun Duro-Ladipo "Aláfẹ ni Baálẹ Apòmù" ("Baálẹ Apòmù loves merriment). It is this trait in Baálẹ Apòmù that spells his tragedy. He takes the oracular prediction of doom lightly and refuses to offer prescribed sacrifice. Consider his reply to the diviner:

Awo

...

Kín nibáà ẹe?

Kò sóhun tí ó ẹe

Kò sóhun tí ń bọ lókè tílẹ o

gbà

Awo

...

What's it that will happen?

Nothing will happen

There is nothing falling from above
that the ground cannot take.

In the same way, he fails to deliberate on prince Aólẹ's case before punishing him. Aólẹ reminds him that a lesser chieftain has no power to punish an Ọyọ prince. Baálẹ Apòmù should have referred the case to Aláàfin Abíọdún himself. His unwise action constitutes the tragic mistake for which he has to offer his head fourteen years later to save Apòmù after Aólẹ has ascended the Ọyọ throne. What, however, makes Baálẹ Apòmù's situation pathetic is that it is Aláàfin Abíọdún, Aólẹ's father, who has given the order which he is enforcing when he punishes prince Aólẹ. But all the same, and as already mentioned, the baálẹ should have given the punishment of the heir apparent a second thought. The Ọ̀nì of Ifẹ expresses the Yorùbá philosophy that should have guided him.

Bá a bá ránmọ níşẹ ẹrú
A fi jẹ tọmọ

When one is sent on an errand as a slave
One delivers it as a free born.

5.3.0

THE ANTAGONISTS

Ọba Ịgbò in Moremi, Èşù in Ọbàtálá and Ajagun-ńlá, Aólẹ in Béyif ò Şe and the Qyómèal in Ọba Kò So and Ọba Mórò are chosen for scrutiny under this category.

5.3.1 Ọba Ịgbò

Unlike other monarchs in the other plays, Ọba Ịgbò is uniquely dressed in the obi traditional royal regalia of the Igbo of Eastern Nigeria. He has a wrapper over his shoulder, wears a feather on his head and holds an ostrich-feathered hand-fan. His face is spotted with white chalk and he is generally backgrounded by the uniform dressing of his warriors in raffia-made outfit. Some of the warriors wear masks while others paint their faces with chalk and charcoal. He is also attended to by two wives dressed in short àdírẹ skirts and their plaited hair is decorated. These peculiar identificatory iconizations are meant to distinguish the Ịgbò from the Ifẹ.

The brutal zeal and tactics with which Ọba Ịgbò launches successful attack against the Ifẹ people indicate Ọba Ịgbò as a strong ruler. But the ways he scolds the weary warriors for not bringing enough booty from the Ifẹ

raids (in the television performance) indicates him as a selfish, inconsiderate tyrant.²² Despite all these tough qualities, Qba Ìgbò has a soft spot for beautiful women, which leads to his tragedy and that of his people. Though Qba Ìgbò decides spontaneously, and wisely too, to take Dibia's aracular advice to decline all booty from the Ifẹ raid, he is easily attracted by Mqrèmi's beauty and he goes back on his words. Within the context of the Yorùbá philosophy of royal integrity, Qba Ìgbò's action is indexical of weak leadership. He makes Mqrèmi his favourite wife and fails to keep an eye on her. He also allows Díbíá, an Ifẹ captive free access to Mqrèmi. These lapses give room for Mqrèmi's initial success in discovering the secret about the Ìgbò masquerades.

If as certain mythico-historical sources have revealed (see Atanda 1980: 5-6), the Ìgbò were the aborigines of Ifẹ before they were driven out by Odúduwà, then the Ìgbò raids, as represented and presented in Mqrèmi can be said to be an expression of self-determination. The raids may be seen as attempts to regain their land. But their loss of the final battle through which they become subject to Odúduwà's successors is catastrophic and tragic. If considered this way, Qba Ìgbò's attack

on Ife will not be seen as villainous.

From another extra-textual mythico-historical perspective, Qba Ìgbò is a successor of Qbátálá who led the Ìgbò people out of Ifè when Odùduwà came.²³ Qba Ìgbò is therefore a meto-symbolic signification of Qbátálá who is usually extra-textually praised as òsèrèràgbò (The divinity of Ìgbò), (see Idowu 1962: 75). Qba Ìgbò's final defeat may therefore be seen as the final stage of the Qbátálá tragic continuum which originates from his primordial drunkenness at the period of creation. It is the tragedy of this pristine fault as we have already argued in 5.2.3 above, that constitutes the primary background of Qbátálá's purity of character. Qba Ìgbò's fall can be traced to his lust for beautiful women. The tragedy of the Ìgbò's final defeat, like that of Qbátálá, implants humility a primary factor in achieving purity of character into Qba Ìgbò. He travels right down to Ifè to reconcile with the Qòní.

The happy reconciliation at the dénouement tends to reduce the tragic weight of Qba Ìgbò's collapse on the denotative plane. A tragic meaning can however, still be read into the situation from an ironical perspective on the connotative level. The picture created of Qba Ìgbò

is that of a happy tragic figure.²⁴

5.3.2 Èṣù

Èṣù is directly iconised in Qbàtálá and meto-
symbolically iconised in Ajagun-ńlá. One is made to
believe that Alejò is a reincarnation of Èṣù whose power
is earlier on activated by the insulted diviner at the
exordial part of the plot. It should be noted that
Èṣù's character is associated with that of Òrúnmílà in
the two plays in consonance with extra-textual reality.
It is through the babaláwo, the Òrúnmílà surrogate, that
we first come across Èṣù (within divinatory contexts) in
the early part of both plays. One of the iconising and
identifying signifiers used, at least in Qbàtálá, is the
traditional bi-coloured (black and red) costume of Èṣù.
The meaning of the name Èṣù is not unconnected with
aspects of Èṣù's behavioural codification. If the
derivation È + ṣù > Èṣù (One who moulds) is accepted
as correct as the saying "nńkan ṣúṣùu l'Èṣù ń ṣù" ("Èṣù
usually moulds confusion") tend to suggest, then the
meaning of Èṣù as the one who causes or perpetrates
trouble is relevant to Èṣù's trickster behaviour.

Èṣù is codified playing fatal tricks on the protagonists in Ọbàtálá and Ajagun-ńlá. As discussed in 4.3.2.1.1. the tricks are hatched through a series of intrigues which leads to tragedy for the protagonists in each play. There is the general tendency to consider Èṣù as a villain in this antagonistic role. The fact that Èṣù displays felicity in mischief-making is a probable index of this tendency. Èṣù for example usually bursts out into derisive laughter at Ọbàtálá whenever an intrigue is hatched:

Aááááàààà
 Ọwọ tẹ wèrè

Ha ha ha ha ha
 The fool is in trouble.

One therefore tends to see Èṣù as a sadist, an embodiment of the Satan or Devil of the Christian and Islamic scriptures.

We however, refrain from taking this stand because Èṣù in the Yorùbá conception supports the righteous or upright and those who are obedient to divinatory injunctions - "Èní rúbọ l'Èṣù ú gbè" ("Èṣù supports anyone who performs sacrifice"). Like other divinities, Èṣù has his

own cult. Just as other divinities, such as Ògún and Şàngó can overplay their fierceness, Èşù can also overplay his tricks and intrigues. This is the sense in which one should understand Èşù's general antagonism. Èşù is, nevertheless, justified in his antagonistic role in both Obàtálá and Ajagun-ńlá. The protagonists in the two plays suffer in the hand of Èşù as a result of their fatal errors. They are, however, made to come to terms with their tragic flaws in the process of their suffering and are left better off than before in the final analysis. This ultimate result of Èşù's antagonism can be seen as indicative of the fact that he is not satanic after all. We can see a binary fusion of the good and the bad in the trickster character feature of Èşù.

5.3.3 Aólẹ

Aólẹ is codified in two different social roles, one after the other. He is first of all seen as an Òyó prince, the heir apparent. He is finally codified as the alááfin in the second part of the play. Aólẹ is behaviourally codified as a proud and vindictive person. The royal blood in him makes him pompous and arrogant. He insults

his subjects, including chiefs, for no good reason. The way in which he comports and carries himself at the slave market where he barter his loyal attendant into slavery, and his encounter with Baálẹ̀ Apòmù are all indices of these behavioural significeds.

Aólẹ̀ is fond of insulting his subjects with
Ìwọ̀ gọ̀

You are stupid.

He says it to the slave master at the market for merely interrupting him. He twice addresses the Başòrun, his immediate lieutenant, in the same words for advising him not to send the Ọyọ̀ army against Apòmù and Ìlọ́rín respectively. Aólẹ̀, as prince, is proud of introducing himself as the son of Aláàfin Abíọ́dún. He does it in the market scene, and in Baálẹ̀ Apòmù's palace where he is arraigned for slave trading.

Aólẹ̀: Baálẹ̀ Apòmù
Kilẹ̀ fáwọ̀n játijàti wọ̀nyí
Pé....
Ọ ọ̀ mọ̀ mí ní?
Baálẹ̀: Ta ní ọ̀?
Aólẹ̀: Èmí Aólẹ̀

Baálẹ̀: Aólẹ̀?

Aólẹ̀: Ọmọ Abíọ́dún, Aláàfin Ọyọ
 Bó o bá tí gbóókọ un
 O yẹ kí o mọ pé Iran baba rẹ
 Ní í ẹẹrú baba mí

(Awọn òhòràn hó láti fí iyálẹnu wọn hàn sí ọrọ ẹ̀kà ẹ̀kà yíí).

Aólẹ̀: Baálẹ̀ Apòmù
 Warn these insignificant people
 That...
 Don't you know me?

Baálẹ̀: Who are you?

Aólẹ̀: I am Aólẹ̀

Baálẹ̀: Aólẹ̀?

Aólẹ̀: The son of Abíọ́dún, the Aláàfin of Ọyọ
 As soon as you hear that name
 You should know that your ancestors
 Are slaves to my own fathers

(The spectators exclaim out of surprise at the heaviness of the insult).

Aólẹ̀' s vindictiveness is indicated in an early part of the play. After taking twenty four strokes of the cane, he reminds Baálẹ̀ Apòmù that though the baálẹ̀ holds the reins of power at the moment, he Aólẹ̀, will hold it in future.

Baálẹ̀ Apòmù
 Ìwọ̀ lo lònif
 Èmi ni mo lẹ̀la
 Kọ̀ ọ̀ gbọ̀ dáadáa

Baálẹ̀ Apòmù
 You hold sway today
 I will hold sway tomorrow
 You, take good note of that

And he also sings, "O ògbèyìn kẹ̀ ẹ̀ tó ma kíkanjú" which roughly translates as "He that laughs last laughs best". Aólẹ̀ surely revenges the disgrace he has suffered in the baálẹ̀' s hand by asking for his head on becoming the Aláàfin. Aólẹ̀' s tragedy is, however, rooted in his vindictiveness. Having satisfied himself about Baálẹ̀ Apòmù he plans to descend on Afọ̀njá, his generalissimo. But ^{he} /himself gets caught up in the game and he has to kill himself to save Ọ̀yọ̀ from Afọ̀njá' s threat.

If Aólẹ̀' s character is considered against the background of his time, one may say that he is quite in order for taking revenge on Baálẹ̀ Apòmù who can be said to have exceeded his powers in punishing the prince. The Ọ̀yọ̀ monarchical system did not allow the Baálẹ̀ to punish a heir apparent and Aólẹ̀' s revenge would be acceptable by

the system. When a new Aláàfin is installed he should name an enemy community to be dealt with by the Ọyọ army (see Johnson 1947: 188). Aólẹ has to name another town, once Baálẹ Apòmù has saved his town by taking his life. He names Afònjá who brings about Aólẹ's death. What one is trying to show is that, the system contributes immensely to the making of Aólẹ's personality and to his tragic end. One could have pitied him by this token, had it not been that Duro Ladipọ, the creator of the play, offers him a chance to make a choice through the sane advice of Başòrun. Neither the warnings of Başòrun nor the oracular predictions of the diviner are able to make Aólẹ see the impending doom. The royal power which he allows to intoxicate him generates arrogant vindictiveness which leads to his fall.

5.3.4 Ọyómẹsì

The Ọyómẹsì constitutes the cabinet chiefs of the Aláàfin of Ọyọ. Though they feature prominently in three of the plays it is only in Ọba Mórò and Ọba Kò So that they antagonize the Aláàfin. The Ọyómẹsì can be seen as the meto-symbolic representation of the people. This view is strongly corroborated in Ọba Kò So where the Ọyómẹsì

are specifically identified as Ará Ọ̀yọ́ (The Ọ̀yọ́ People). But Ẹ̀ngó himself, however, refers to them as Ọ̀yọ̀mẹ̀sì (see Ladipo 1970: 10).

The prominent behavioural signification in which the Ọ̀yọ̀mẹ̀sì are collectively codified is found in their high diplomacy and slyness at handling issues. This signification has an extra-textual basis. The Ọ̀yọ́ people are usually regarded as cunning by other Yorùbá groups. Of the Ọ̀yọ́ people the following is usually said:

Ọ̀yọ́ ayọ̀mọ́lẹ̀

Ọ̀yọ́ that cunningly fails/betrays people

Ọ̀yọ́ dọ̀bálẹ̀

Inú ẹ̀ lóṣòó

The Ọ̀yọ́ prostrates himself

His mind squats

About the Ọ̀yọ̀mẹ̀sì in particular, Fálétí comments through

Ọ̀yáàbí ní Basorun Gáà

Ẹ̀bí wọ̀n sọ p'Ọ̀yọ́ ọ̀ mẹ̀sì ...

Bẹ̀ẹ̀ Ọ̀yọ́ sí mẹ̀sì nítòótó

Idáhùn ní kò ní mú wá

Níjọ́ Ọ̀yọ́ mẹ̀sì tí kò mẹ̀sì wá

Ohun tí m̀bẹ̀ nínú ^{wm} m̀bẹ̀ nínú wọ̀n

tí wọ̀n fẹ̀ ẹ̀

Ọ̀yọ̀mèsì

(Faleti 1971: 109)

How come they say that Ọ̀yọ̀ do not know
the appropriate reply?

The Ọ̀yọ̀ know the appropriate reply

They wouldn't just bring forth the reply

The day the Ọ̀yọ̀ know the appropriate reply
and would not bring it forth

What they want to do remains
locked up in their mind.

The Ọ̀yọ̀ know the appropriate reply.

Taking our cue from Adébáyọ̀ Falétí's poetic analysis of the name, we can conclude that the name Ọ̀yọ̀mèsì is derived from Ọ̀yọ̀ mọ̀ èsì (The Ọ̀yọ̀ know the appropriate reply). The poetic word-play on the name also shows clearly how the meaning of the name is connected to the behavioural feature of the Ọ̀yọ̀mèsì. This feature is clearly codified in Oba Mórò. After the Aláàfin has informed the Ọ̀yọ̀mèsì of his plan to shift his capital to Àjàkà, rather than openly declare their opposition, the Ọ̀yọ̀mèsì only promise to deliberate on the matter.

A gbọ bí o ti wí o
A ó ronú sí i

We've heard what you said
We'll think about it.

They do not give the Aláàfin any reply. Instead they go straight to plot against the plan. The Òyómèsi in Qba Kò So initially directly confront Şàngó with regard to the excessive military activities of his war-lords which are having grievous consequences on the community. When they realise that Şàngó is not ready to co-operate on the matter they withdraw their advisorial services. When Şàngó later decides to listen to them and asks for their advice on his unruly war-lords, the Òyómèsi walk out on him. It is, however, in the way the Òyómèsi finally change sides when events turn against Şàngó that their slyness is accentuated. One can, however, say that the Òyómèsi have a good case for their antagonism in both Qba Kò So and Qba Mórò even if their approach tends to be too harsh. They are in both cases serving as the mouth-piece of the people of Òyó who bear the brunt of the monarch's actions.

In conclusion, our decodification in this chapter has shown clearly that both the protagonists and antagonists in the plays are balanced in portraiture. This is

inspite of their being archetypes. This codification upholds the Yorùbá axiom, "Kò sí adára-má-kù-síbikan", ("There is no good person without his own flaws"), which reaffirms the entrenchement of the concept of binarism in Yorùbá philosophy.

CHAPTER FIVE

NOTES

1. The performers are, for example, usually remembered by the audience, and called by their stage names outside performance context. Examples of Duro Ladipo called Şàngó, Kọla Ogunmọlá, Làńké Ọmu and Moses Ọlályá, Bàbá Sàlá readily come to mind.
2. The table presented here is derived from both Culler (1975: 233) and Scholes (1974: 104). Elam (198: 126-131) has also been found very useful in the same respect.
3. Both Culler (1975: 232) and Fowler (1977: 35) have clearly indicated that structuralists have really not developed this approach beyond the stage of mere suggestion.
4. The following sayings show that the name is one of the lenses through which the personality of a character can be viewed among the Yorùbá:

Orúkọ tí a bá sọ ọmọ ní í ro ọmọ

It is the name given to a child that
affects the child

Orúkọ ẹnì ní lǎnú ẹnì

One's name is one's caution

Also see Adéoyè (1969: 1-2) and Ọlátúnjì (1984: 68) for an extended poetic version of the former saying and its translation respectively.

5. The only type of Yorùbá name that is not common in the plays is orúkọ àmútorunwa/abáwáye (names given by observing the circumstance and nature of birth). The only example in the plays is Abíípa A + bí + sí + ípa (He who is born by the way path).
6. The name Díbíá means 'diviner' in the language of the Igbo of Eastern Nigeria. This is the context through which the character is codified.
7. The following Yorùbá costume could be given the following indexical significations.
 - Ipèlé - womanhood
 - Iborùn - elderly woman (if put over the left shoulder) membership of the Oṣùgbó cult (if put over the right shoulder).
 - író àrókanlẹ̀ - royal wife
 - abetí ajá cap - old age (men)
 - dígò trousers } preparedness for rigorous
 - gbérí jacket } assignment.
8. In the few cases where such features are attached to females, such females are regarded as obínrin bí ọ̀kúnrin [man-like (courageous) women]. Mọ̀rẹ̀mi in our data, Efuṣetan Aniwura and Tinubu both of Ibadan and Ègbá fame respectively belong to the group.
9. Hubert Ogunde in his films Avé and Jáyósinmi makes clear uses of the two symbols respectively.
10. An explanation of this ironical ambivalence has been attempted in Chapter Three. Another explanation is to see the ambivalence in terms of the codification

of the two aspects of Ẹ̀sàngó: Ẹ̀sàngó as a mythical figure and as an historical figure. Adéoyè (1979: 30) has in fact, pointed out that the historical figure, Alááfin Babáyemí Ìtíolú, contrary to popular belief, is not the same as the mythical Ẹ̀sàngó. He is according to Iṣṣòlá (1984: 31) apparently a staunch adherent of Ẹ̀sàngó.

11. Ajagun-ńlá is also clearly codified in this feature.
12. Such a husband will definitely take a large share of the blame if the case should be settled under customary regulations before elders.
13. This adaptative translation by Beier which expresses clearly the aspect of Ẹ̀sàngó being discussed is that of

Kòkòrò, kòkòrò fíjò ẹ̀yàyà 0
Kòkòrò, kòkòrò fíjò ẹ̀yàyà 0
(Ladipo 1970: 3)
14. Suicide is used here purely as a technical term for denoting the act of taking one's life. The derogatory connotations are not implied.
15. It should be noted here that the stage directions are derived from performances.
16. Ọ̀dúnjọ's poem "Ọ̀mọ Nìgbẹ̀yìn Ọ̀là" (Ọ̀dúnjọ 1961: 5) and Ambrose Campbell's song "Bá a bá lógún ẹ̀rú; Bá a yáwọ̀fa ọ̀gbọ̀n ... Ọ̀mọ lądèlẹ̀" express this Yorùbá attitude.

17. This concept is usually iconised by our traditional (and modern) sculptors who usually carve a kneeling mother holding her breasts or carrying a baby (see Oj6 1979: 337).
18. This looks like an extreme case of patriotism among the Yorùbá people and there is the tendency to regard it as anti-culture if the Yorùbá general attitude to the situation is considered. A Yorùbá parent especially the mother would rather die than allow her child to do so. It is tragic for parents to outlive their children in Yorùbá land. Occasional instances of actions depicted in M̀p̀r̀emi's myth are however found. Consider Alááfin Abíípa's case who offered his new born child as sacrifice so that there may be peace in Òỳỳ (See Johnson 1941: 167). Baş̀orun Ògúnm̀ólá of the Ibádán fame is according to oral information from Adébáyò Palétí also known to have done a similar thing.
19. Her situation conforms to a great extent, with the Aristotelian/Shakespearean tragic concept. She is a royal figure, and it is in her aspiration to solve a state problem that her tragedy lies.
20. This agrees with the Yorùbá proverb
 Nínú ikòkò dúdú lẹ̀kọ funfun gbé ń jáde
 It is out of a black pot that the white
 corn porridge emerges.

21. The Olówu of Ówu is also included in this list in Johnson's account (1921: 188-189). Also see Mabogunje and Omer-Cooper (1971: 40).
22. He makes the warriors prostrate themselves while he beats them with a rod. This we, however, think is probably an instance of over-acting which usually occurs in the theatrical tradition within which Duro Ladipo operated.
23. Historically speaking, the contemporary Yorùbá Obas are, in most cases, not indigenes of the land they now govern. Mythologically too Ọbàtálá was the first emissary sent to do the work of creation on earth but he got drunk and the work was eventually accomplished by Odùduwà. This implies that Odùduwà probably met Ọbàtálá in Ilé-Iṣẹ (see Elúyemi 1975: 125).
24. The codification is probably meant to be an aetiological explanation of the existence of the Ígbò masquerade (Elúyarè) in Ifẹ today. The masquerades still parade Ifẹ streets during the Edì festival and according to Eluyemi (1975: 123) during the Pòkúlere festivals.

CONCLUSION

The protagonists and antagonists in the mythico-historical plays are archetypal characters. They represent the collective values of the Yorùbá. Though there are two types of these characters - the òrìṣàs (gods) and the ancestors (semi-gods) - the values for which they stand are the same¹. Generally speaking the archetypal essence hangs on the fatalism of the characters as well as on other exemplary qualities. Patriotism is the highest of these heroic values. But in most cases the characters' flaws constitute a hindrance in the achievement of perfection in their exemplariness and this leads to anagnorisis, a point of self-awareness, when the limitation of human powers is fully appreciated (Ọlatunji 1982: 49-50). It is at this point that "suicide" and/or "transmogrification" sets in and deification follows as a gesture of final appreciation from the people.

Such cases of suicide or transmogrification can, from occidental perspectives, be seen as instances of escapism; a kind of escape from the consequences of

one's tragic fault². But from the Yorùbá perspective, such a step in order to save and enhance one's integrity is allowed and considered a brave act. It is for example, usually said that "ikú yá ju ẹ̀sín" ("death is preferable to shame"). The heroism of the archetypal figures teaches us therefore to face the fatal consequences of our frailties squarely.

The acceptance of one's fault as a leader does not however, remove the tragedy that issues from it. It may limit to a personal tragedy what might otherwise have been a social catastrophe. The effort to avert a social tragedy need not arise from attempts at coming to terms with one's flaw. It can, as in the case of Mọ̀rẹ̀mi, come out of a general patriotic zeal. Patriotism at any level involves hardship and fatal loss. But a person who is able to take such a step will forever be remembered in the history of his community - a way of immortalization just like deification. The apotheosization of the archetypal figures after their "suicide", death or "non-death" and transmogrification is actually a means of holding up their values to the people as worthy of emulation. It is clear from our discussion in this work

that the concept of archetypal essence, which is crucial to mythico-historical plays cannot be separated from that of the tragic, the heroic, the suicidal and even transmorgrification. In fact, all these other concepts can be appropriately seen as integral to the concept of archetypal essence.

The process of archetypalization is a continuous one in history. Each era has its own set of archetypal figures. Balógun Ibíkúnlé and Başòrun Ògúnmólá, Ààrẹ Látòósà and Balógun Ògèdèngbé belong to the group of archetypal figures of the Yorùbá wars of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. Though they are not deified like the mythico-historical figures, they are still remembered today for their heroic values. Their status now decorate important places in our cities and towns.

It is perhaps the lack of heroic values in our contemporary leaders that is responsible for our many social problems. Our leaders are in most cases only partially patriotic and they are not prepared to come to terms with the consequences of their frailties. The catalytic anagnoristic experience crucial to archetypal upliftment has consistently eluded them.

So the people continue to bear the fatal burden of their arrogance.

It is with regard to this thematic relevance of the plays to contemporary Yorùbá, Nigerian and African situations that one can confidently join Adedeji (1973a: 72) in saying that Duro Ladipo

uses theatrical art to interpret the Yorùbá past but with a view towards emphasizing those points which seem relevant to, or which reflect contemporary situation.

Another aspect of the relevance of Duro Ladipo's plays to contemporary situation can be found in his apparent concern with cultural re-education. The effects of colonialism, and religious and general cultural imperialism are still very much with us. Some people are undergoing complete alienation from their roots. There are very few others nowadays who are adapting the traditional culture to modern or, more properly, Western culture. There is hardly any aspect of Yorùbá culture which is not undergoing a sort of transition. The present generation knows little about the traditional

culture and the coming generation may know nothing about it. Duro Ladipo is, however, one of those making efforts to keep the dying culture for posterity through dramatic activities. There are, for example, not many elders to tell to the new generation folktales, not to talk of myths and legends. But Duro Ladipo gives life to the dying gods in his dramatic creations through the extensive use of cultural materials. We are through the thematic codification treated above, for example, made to realize, that the moral values which the new religions are teaching are indeed not new.

Duro Ladipo is, however, not dogmatic in his traditionalism. The structure of his plays especially on the musico-poetic level, points to a certain degree of eclecticism in his traditionalism. Duro Ladipo's orientation towards cultural rejuvenation can be seen as a radical reaction to the historical factor of the religious oppression in which he grew up as a child. Others may want to criticize him for his limited eclecticism, that it is rather regressive than progressive³. We would, however, wish to refrain from taking such a stance because we think Duro Ladipo

should first and foremost be assessed through the parameters he has set for himself⁴. The type of awareness that leads to progressive eclecticism, where the status quo is challenged, can be said to have somehow eluded him because of the environment in which he grew up.

The fact that Duro Ladipo did not make much in terms of financial gain when he could have easily made it with less efforts like some of his contemporaries shows the extent of his commitment to the cultural rejuvenation and re-education of his people. It is in this fact that Duro Ladipo's contribution as a nationalist lies. Posterity can never forget him for this role. In addition to the criticism of the **socialist critics**, other dramatists are already re-examining the status-quo - the obaship institution and other aspects of traditional culture and beliefs. The subtle but pungent farce on the obsolete abobaku (die-with-the-king) tradition in Oyó by Moses Olaiya Adejumo in his Abobaki and Oladejo Okediji's use of the obaship institution in exposing the feudal/capitalist method of oppressing the masses in Réré Rún, come readily to mind.

Our study has, however, clearly shown that Duro Ladipo is not just a mythico-historical recorder. He is highly innovative at every level of codification. His plays are very successful as an art of spectacle. The backcloths, costumes and hand props used in his performances are usually richly designed by specialists from the M̀bárí M̀báyò cultural centre. Special attention is also usually paid to the structuralization of the dance movements that accompany singing and instrumentation. In fact, Duro Ladipo's is a total theatre, where all aspects of the theatrical art are innovatively structured for entertaining purpose. It is through the entertaining significations which are universally understood that Duro Ladipo is able to establish a primary link with his non-Yorùbá-speaking audience both in Nigeria and abroad.

That Duro Ladipo is not as popular as Ogunde among the cosmopolitan audience of, say, Lagos, as noted by Eḃun Clark (1979: 140), does not necessarily mean that Duro Ladipo is less competent as a dramatist. Duro Ladipo's attempt in trying to strike a balance between entertainment and the instructive purpose (the

popular and the aesthetic) is probably responsible for this. As a show business man that he is, Ogunde emphasizes the entertaining aspects of drama more than the instructive. When an attempt is made to instruct, in Ogunde it is often done directly. But in Duro Ladipo's case the two aspects are binarily fused. Instructions are, as shown in our discussion above, indirect. The audience has to infer them from the play itself. Since the entertaining value is immediate, it tends to be transient while the aesthetic value (in which the entertaining and instructive aspects are balanced), which is not immediate, endures the test of time. Duro Ladipo is to the best of our knowledge, however, the most literary oriented of the dramatists in the Ogunde dramatic movement. This is not only proved by the fact that he has more published texts than any other practitioner in the movement today but also by the analysis presented in this study. As far as dramatic and theatrical competence goes there is no doubt that Duro Ladipo occupies an important place in Yorùbá and Nigerian theatre. His fame even extended to the international scene. This work has proved that fact

in a large measure, and the many prizes and honours he received are witnesses to **his fame**.

Our treatment of the theatrical aspects side by side with the literary has been made possible by the semiotic approach used. The semiotic methodology of breaking the sign down to signifier and signified has helped in the clear and detailed discussion of meaning at the three major levels of codification. The semiotic frame-work has helped us to realize that meaning is not limited to an underlying semantic or connotative level. Rather, the meaning of a structure or element may also be found in its relationship to other structures, in its functional position within a net-work of relationships. The eclectic principle of the semiotic frame-work is able to cope adequately with the eclecticism of the plays, and allows for indepth analysis. The approach has helped us to concretize aspects of Duro Ladipo's work that have earlier been marginally indicated. We have been able to determine and discuss the nature and significations of the important patterns that form the structure of his mythico-historical plays. The result of our findings will, no doubt be applicable to the study

of other mythico-historical plays. Being a pioneering work in the application of the semiotic frame-work to Yorùbá texts, this thesis, we hope, has shown that Yorùbá literature in general can benefit a lot from the semiotic enterprise.

This work, we would like to believe, has no doubt set a pace in the critical study of Duro Ladipò's plays in particular and of plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition in general. The scripted plays in the Ogunde dramatic tradition available for critical study are very few. This may in turn be seen as ^{having been} responsible for the existence of few critical analysis of plays in the tradition. More plays of Duro Ladipò in particular and those of others in the dramatic tradition should therefore as a matter of urgency be published. The responsibility of transcribing the plays has to be shared between the artist and the scholar. The two have to co-operate in the project. It is after this has been done that proper academic study can continue. This does not necessarily mean that the study of performance is going to be neglected. Such a study will in fact benefit from the existence of written plays. In fact, we are aware of

a doctoral musicological study of Duro Ladipò's plays currently being carried out⁵. More studies of his plays and those of others in the same tradition⁶ should also be considered from other perspectives: purely theatrical, receptionist, linguistic, historical and the collective creational.

NOTES

1. Belonging to the first group are Şàngó, Ọbàtálá, Mọ̀rèmi, Ọşun, Ọbà, and Èşù and to the second group are Ajagun-ńlá, Oníkòyí, Olúgbón, Arẹ̀sà, Ológbo, Baálẹ̀ Apòmù, Aólẹ̀, Olórí Èlẹ̀şin Ọba, Ọba Igbò and Ọyómẹ̀sì. The prominent concern in the plays is to show the archetypal essence of the characters. The archetypal essence of Èşù and the Ọyómẹ̀sì is unlike in the others, tied to their overall feature as antagonists.
2. This may be so, especially in the case of Şàngó and Oníkòyí.
3. From the socialist perspective Duro Ladipo, by presenting the deification of monarchs (feudal lords) and other sacred beliefs of the Yorùbá will be seen as upholding an unprogressive status quo system under which the masses are endlessly oppressed.
4. See Ladipo (1970: IV), for his personal pronouncement on his aesthetic commitment to the cultural rejuvenation and re-education of the people.
5. Reference here is to Christopher Brooks of the University of Texas, U.S.A. He was in Nigeria in the 1985-86 session on a Fulbright scholarship to

collect data. He came back in the summer of 1987 to do a follow-up.

6. The works of Ogunde himself probably need urgent attention. The present writer is not aware of any published text of Ogunde's plays. Egun Clark's work on Ogunde's works is more historical than analytical.

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_____ Oba Kò Sò, WNTV/WNBS (now NTA), Ibadan.

_____ Aiasun-ílá, LTV, Lagos.

APPENDIX
LIST OF INFORMANTS

NAME	ADDRESS	DATE
1 Oyin Adejōbi	6, Gbaemu Street, Oşogbo	19-7-81, 22-8-81 5-6-86.
2 Dayo Adekunle	Cultural Centre, Mokoła Hill, Ibadan.	1985
3 Adebisi Adeleke	Music Department, The Polytechnic Ibadan.	1987
4 Dapo Adelugba	Dept of Theatre Arts Univ. of Ibadan, Ibadan	2-5-83, 17-12-85
5 Adeşina Adetoyi	Cultural Centre, Mokoła Hill, Ibadan.	19-2-86, 25-2-86, 2-3-86.
6 Ulli Beier	Ile Ife (During a short visit to Nigeria)	1986
7 Chief Akogun	Ile-Ife (near Oranyan Shrine)	8-11-85
8 Ojēniyi Amo	Cultural Centre, Mokoła Hill, Ibadan	2-2-85, 2-4-86
9 Biḡdun Duro-Ladipo	Bode Wasimi, Başorun Ibadan.	26-9-86, 1-10-86 11-10-86
10 Toła Duro-Ladipo	NTA, Agodi, Ibadan	1985
11 Adebayo Faleti	Orogun/Ojoo, Ibadan	1986
12 Adebisi Faşaanu	Kajola Barbing Saloon Born Photo, Isale-osi, Ibadan.	3-4-86
13 Yemi Elebuubon	Oluode's Compound, Oşogbo.	19-2-85

NAME	ADDRESS	DATE
14 Lasisi Gbebqlaja	Cultural Centre, Mokqla Hill, Ibadan	2-10-86
15 Tayo Ogunmqla	Osgogbo	1982, 8-6-86
16 Işqla Ogunşqla	Olomi-Academy, Ibadan	5-9-82
17 Qrangun of Oke-Ila	Oke-Ila	1985
18 Muraina Oyelami	Department of Music Obafemi Awolowo University, Ilé-Ife.	16-1-86
19 Abidoye Ojo	Oke Are, Ibadan	5-1-86, 26-3-86
20 Kayode Olaiya (Aderupqko)	Oluyoro Oke-Qfa, Ibadan	16-2-85.
21 Olowomojuore (Bábáa Géébú)	Yemetu, Alawada Ibadan.	5-9-83.